

Ontario Biology Day

37th Annual Conference

Carleton University

March 22-23, 2025

Land Acknowledgement

We would like to acknowledge the Algonquin nation whose traditional and unceded territory we are gathered upon today.

Contents

Land Acknowledgement	2
Ontario Biology Day – 2025 – Sponsors	4
Welcome to Ontario Biology Day – 2025	5
Our Conference Speakers	6
Schedule – at a glance	8
Concurrent Oral Presentations.....	9
Poster Presentations	15
Oral Presentation Abstracts	19
Poster Presentation Abstracts.....	73
The Conference Venue.....	108

Ontario Biology Day – 2025 – Sponsors

Thank you!

Department of Biology

Faculty of Science

Welcome to Ontario Biology Day – 2025

On behalf of the Department of Biology at Carleton University, we would like to welcome you to the 37th Annual Ontario Biology Day undergraduate student research conference. This annual conference brings together students from across Ontario to present their research in the biological sciences, from the level of molecules and the cell, to ecology, evolution and behaviour. This year, we are delighted to welcome more than 200 delegates from 15 universities to our province. The quality and diversity of research completed by you, our next generation of scientists and educators, is truly remarkable and we would like to congratulate you on your achievement. We wish you success in your presentations and look forward to this weekend of science and socializing.

Our conference this year will be opened with talks by Dr. Thomas Kazmirchuk and Dr. Bahram Samanfar. Our conference banquet will be held on campus at Oliver's Pub located in Nideyinàn (formerly the University Centre) and will feature a talk by science journalist and journalism professor at Carleton, Dr. Sarah Everts. Following our two days of talks and posters, our conference will close with talks by Dr. Emily Curren and Dr. Eugene Fletcher. We encourage you to explore their biographies in our program booklet.

We would like to acknowledge the support of all persons, institutions and organizations that have contributed to making this conference possible this year. The Carleton Undergraduate Biology Society (CUBS), numerous graduate students, post-doctoral fellows, research associates, staff and faculty members from Biology and Biochemistry and other departments at Carleton have all dedicated their time to prepare for this conference. We are also grateful for our talk and poster judges attending our conference from universities across Ontario. The generous support from our sponsors and the Faculty of Science at Carleton has allowed us to welcome so many of you to our campus.

This conference is a celebration of your hard work, and we look forward to learning about your ideas and research discoveries.

Best wishes for a great conference!

The 2025 Ontario Biology Day Organizing Committee –

Jeff Dawson
Haiyun Bo
Roslyn Dakin
Thomas Kazmirchuk
Heath MacMillan
Iain McKinnell
Tim Xing

Our Conference Speakers

Dr. Thomas Kazmirchuk

Designing the Future of Medicine

Dr. Kazmirchuk is currently a MITACs post-doctoral fellow in the department of Biology at Carleton University. He received his Ph.D in Cellular and Molecular Biology at Concordia University in Montreal, QC. He is also an alumnus of Carleton, having completed both his B.Sc and M.Sc in Carleton Biology. His current award-winning research involves the intelligent design of peptides that act as both therapeutics and diagnostics for rare bleeding disorders. He loves to teach and mentor all stages of students, from undergraduate to doctoral. Through his international academic and industrial collaborations, Tom is actively laying the foundation for the future of medicine. In his off time, he loves being out in nature taking photos of wildlife.

Dr. Bahram Samanfar

Functional Genomics of Soybean (I am not a breeder, but I love working with breeders)

Dr. Samanfar is a Research Scientist at AAFC, Ottawa-RDC and an Adjunct Professor at Department of Biology, Carleton University. He is a molecular geneticist and applied genomicist with expertise in allele-specific molecular marker developments, recombination mapping, marker-assisted selection (molecular breeding), functional genomics, transcriptome-wide (RNA-seq) approaches, computational biology and bioinformatics, particularly in relation to Soybean. Dr. Samanfar received his Ph.D. from Carleton University and holds an M.Sc. degree from Paul Sabatier University (France) and M.Sc. and B.Sc. degrees from University of Tehran (Iran).

<https://bahramsamanfar.wixsite.com/samanfarlab/lab-members>

Sarah Everts

Sarah Everts is an award-winning science journalist and journalism professor at Carleton University based in Ottawa. Her work has appeared in Scientific American, New Scientist, Smithsonian, Guardian, Time, Chemical & Engineering News and others. She is also the author of the book, The Joy of Sweat: The Strange Science of Perspiration, which the New York Times called “crisp and lively... an entertaining and illuminating guide to the necessity and virtues of perspiration.”

Dr. Emily Curren

Understanding coastal pollution in the 21st Century: insights from the tropics

Emily Curren is a postdoctoral research scientist from the National University of Singapore. She works on coastal marine pollution, specifically harmful algal blooms and microplastics. Emily profiles the diversity and distribution of tropical marine cyanobacteria, with focus on characterizing toxic and novel species. She also studies the plastisphere and evaluates the impact of microplastic pollution on human health and food security. Emily is also a committee member of the IOC-WESTPAC Harmful Algal Blooms work group and has ongoing international collaborations with partner universities in Japan and Malaysia.

Dr. Eugene Fletcher

Solving big problems with a tiny organism

Dr. Eugene Fletcher is an Assistant Professor at the Department of Biology, Carleton University. Prior to joining Carleton in the summer of 2023, he was the Research and Development (R&D) Lead at Escarpment Laboratories, a yeast company based in Guelph, Ontario. At Escarpment Labs, he spearheaded an active research program to develop yeast strains for craft brewers in Canada and abroad.

Eugene got his PhD in Cell Biology from the University of Edinburgh, Scotland. After completing his PhD in 2014, he pursued postdoctoral training at Chalmers University of Technology in Gothenburg (Sweden), Technical University of Denmark, and the University of Ottawa.

His research program at Carleton focuses on developing better yeasts for industry. In addition to his academic and industry experience, Eugene holds a 2023 US patent and is passionate about moving ideas from the lab bench to market.

Schedule – at a glance

Day	Time	What's Happening
Saturday March 22	10:00 AM - 12:00 PM	Registration – Richcraft Hall, 3 rd Floor
	12:00 PM – 1:00 PM	Welcome Message - Richcraft Hall RM 2200 Talk by Dr. Thomas Kazmirchuk Talk by Dr. Bahram Samanfar
	1:15 PM - 2:15 PM	Concurrent Sessions
	2:15 PM – 2:30 PM	Coffee Break
	2:30 PM – 3:15 PM	Concurrent Sessions
	3:15 PM – 3:30 PM	Coffee Break
	3:30 PM – 5:00 PM	Concurrent Sessions
	5:00 PM – 7:00 PM	Poster Session – Nideyinàn (formerly the University Centre) – 4 th Floor Atrium
	6:00 PM – 9:00 PM c. 6:30 PM c. 7:00 PM c. 7:30 PM	Conference Banquet - Ollie's Pub in Nideyinàn Building (formerly the University Centre) The banquet venue will open at 6:00. Light appetizers will be available with our meals being served soon after. Talk by Sarah Everts to follow our meal
Sunday March 23	8:00 AM – 9:00 AM	Coffee Break
	9:00 AM – 10:15 AM	Concurrent Sessions
	10:15 AM – 10:30 AM	Coffee Break
	10:30 AM – 11:45 AM	Concurrent Sessions
	12:00 PM- 1:30 PM	Awards Presentation & Closing Remarks Richcraft Hall, RM 2200 Talk by Dr. Emily Curren Talk by Dr. Eugene Fletcher Lunches will be available
	12:30 PM-1:00 PM	Business Meeting (Optional)

Concurrent Oral Presentations

Richcraft Hall (3rd Floor)

Ontario Biology Day 2025

Saturday 1:15 - 2:15 PM

Start time	Room 3224 Urban Ecology - I	Room 3202 Health - I	Room 3220 Agriculture and Forestry	Room 3228 Microbiology - I	Room 3201 Animal Ecology - I
1:15 pm	59 Callia Collard: Effects of anthropogenic noise in Paris on the European Robin	5 Basak Korkmaz: Studying the role of Ubiquitination in Clathrin-Mediated Endocytosis During Replicative Aging	12 Isabelle Venzon: Impact of EcoWool on crop quality	24 Nour Elshobary: Investigating and disrupting antibiotic repression by the global regulator wbla in <i>Streptomyces venezuelae</i>	22 Emily Laver-Shareski: The effects of warming on predator-prey interactions using microarthropods as a model
1:30 pm	26 Ishaan Bhatthal: Examining changes in Tree Swallow (<i>Tachycineta bicolor</i>) gut microbiome as a result of pollution across Southern Ontario	37 Amber Austin: AMPK is vital for the regulation of skeletal muscle fibrosis in cancer cachexia	13 Angel Lainscek: The influence of position and colour of sticky traps on leafhopper detection in organic vineyards	20 Intesar Shah: The impact of heat and hydroxyurea on reactive oxygen species level in <i>Schizosaccharomyces pombe</i>	1 Gabby Kohut: Perceived human presence alters coyote behaviour, reducing activity and foraging
1:45 pm	58 Madison Bygrove: Impacts of human-made noise on the presence and song structure of Eurasian blackcaps (<i>Sylvia atricapilla</i>)	44 Anneliese Schall: Effects of chronic AMPK activation on age-associated muscle loss	47 Kiersten DeViller: Caught in the act: Assessing lure type effects on Japanese beetle (<i>Popillia japonica</i>) trap capture	97 Yamamah Al-Jumaili: Investigating gene dysregulations associated with antifungal resistance in <i>Candida</i> strains from Northern Ontario	18 Kennedy Jamieson: Do elephants in protected areas know that they are protected? An experimental analysis of antipredator behaviour in African Elephants
2:00 pm	64 Kristine Kamensky: The effects of anthropogenic noise on the song structure and habitat occupancy of the Eurasian Wren (<i>Troglodytes troglodytes</i>)	92 Claire McInroy: Inflammation as a driver of age-related DNA methylation	4 Niamh Moreton: Temporal dynamics of mountain pine beetle (<i>Dendroctonus ponderosae</i>) population structure over an outbreak	15 Ummuhan Canatan: Mother-daughter protein asymmetry during budding yeast replicative aging	98 Lorriana Broglio: Forensically important insects in forests of Greater Sudbury: Investigating implications for forensic entomology

Break 2:15-2:30 PM

Saturday 2:30 - 3:15 PM

Start time	Room 3224 Urban Ecology - II	Room 3220 Plant Biology - I	Room 3201 Animal Ecology - II	Room 3228 Microbiology - II	Room 3202 Health - II	Room 3112 Animal Behaviour - I
2:30 pm	38 Ruby Tsz Ying Yip: Using citizen science to study plant invasions in Churchill, Manitoba	39 Maria Proskurina: Drought stress detection in conifers: linking vegetation indices, pigment changes, and scales	63 Lama Farah: Assessing the impact of environmental noise on auditory hair cell density in bluegill sunfish (<i>Lepomis macrochirus</i>)	10 Sofya Rudovskaya: Characterization of queE-dependent filamentation in <i>Escherichia coli</i> and <i>Yersinia pseudotuberculosis</i>	91 Olivia Norman: Investigating the role of CHRFAM7A in the immune response of human macrophages	61 Rana Elkafarneh: The relationship between social calls and flight behaviours in big brown bats
2:45 pm	71 Amesh Wickramasinghe: The heartbeat of river ecosystems: exploring indicators of ecological health in urban Windsor-Essex rivers	52 Spenser Morouney: Seeds of change: Impacts of permafrost disturbance on tundra shrub reproduction	65 Zain Khan: Biotic and abiotic influences on fish diversity and distribution in the St. Lawrence river using environmental DNA	6 George Raymond Thomas: Host-virus-viophage dynamics: virophage-mediated protection of freshwater haptophyte algae	84 Josée McDavid: Examining the impact of colitis on intestinal inflammation and L-cell physiology in mice	62 Natalie Emerick: What's all the buzz about: Habitat use overlap in bats and aerial insectivore birds
3:00 pm	17 Britt Petersen: Shining a light on the shadows: Examining the cascading effects of pollinator gardens on nocturnal pollinators and their predators	105 Austin McGonegal: Does size matter? Effect of neighbor functional traits on flowering	56 Eryn Wolfe: Testing the effects of hypolimnetic aeration in a polluted northern lake	69 Genie Nehruji Effect of QACA/B efflux pumps on povidone-iodine resistance in <i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i>	41 Ahmed Khalil: Bacterial translocation and immune cell interactions in a mouse restraint stress model	68 Tamjeed Nawaz: Continuous or bimodal: Investigating variability in moth evasive responses to bat predator cues

Break 3:15-3:30 PM

Saturday 3:30 - 5:00 PM

Start time	Room 3112 Animal Behaviour - II	Room 3220 Plant Biology - II	Room 3228 Infection and Immunity	Room 3201 Animal Ecology - III	Room 3202 Health - III	Room 3224 Late Entries
3:30 pm	70 Chris Sankaral: Effects of handling stress on post-swim stress physiology in juvenile lake sturgeon (<i>Acipenser fulvescens</i>)	95 Kayla Twilley: Influence of nutrient availability on senescence in wetland monocot species with differing nutrient economies	27 Rosa Adams: Cuticular cues involved in locust infection by the insect specialist <i>Metarhizium</i>	79 Hazel Barr: Corridor ecology: animal activity near shorelines in the Lake Laurentian Conservation Area (LLCA), Sudbury, Ontario	94 Emma Mageau: Investigating the role of prostaglandins and isoprostanes mediated by dysregulation of inflammatory enzyme PTGS2 in radiation resistance of triple negative breast cancer cells	60 Michael Anthony Douaihy White shark scarring in Australian waters: Wound classification, distribution and Accumulation rates.
3:45 pm	14 Margaret Kitney: The effect of sex on the thermoregulatory behaviour of the guppy (<i>Poecilia reticulata</i>)	96 Mackenzie Hobbs: Elemental composition of Ostrich fern (<i>Matteuccia struthiopteris</i>) fiddleheads in Sudbury-Manitoulin Districts, Ontario	11 Andrea Fernandes: Horizontal transmission of modified Negevirus via oral ingestion of spiked sugar meal	30 Madelaine Picard: Native intertidal biodiversity plays a role in resisting the establishment of the invasive European green crab, <i>Carcinus maenas</i>	74 Olivia Wahby: Circadian regulation of intestinal homeostasis: how period gene mutations affect stem cell differentiation and turnover	109 Sharifa Lomiyey Effects of PIKfyve lipid kinase inhibition on endoplasmic reticulum in the context of ER-remodeling
4:00 pm	53 Maryem Naimee: Wavelengths of influence: Blue light and its role in memory and mate-choice in fruit flies	90 Sirui Tong: Rhizosphere effects on enzyme activities in red pine (<i>Pinus resinosa</i>) stands	83 Sabrina Lepage: Patterns of parasitism in urban rodents and effects of ectoparasite diversity on body condition	80 Shannon Crockford: Forest succession 2003-2024 and animal activity in Lake Laurentian Conservation Area in Sudbury, Ontario, Canada	76 Akudo Eze-Onuorah: Investigating the involvement of kaiso in chemotherapy drug sensitivity of triple-negative breast cancer cell lines using knock out cells	
4:15 pm	49 Avneet Kahlon: The role of male body size and eye color in female harassment dynamics in <i>Drosophila melanogaster</i>	104 Joel Lucenay: How post-successional understories, their mycorrhizal associations, and their connection to coniferous/deciduous-dominated stands change with rising temperatures	40 Christina Bethune: Effects of TLR4 genetic diversity on song sparrow mate choice and survivorship	66 Renil Kooplicat: Gene transcription profile response to hybrid breakdown and temperature stress in chinook salmon (<i>Oncorhynchus tshawytscha</i>)	2 Maira Chaudhry: Assessment of frailty index in 5xfad mice during disease progression: a neurological perspective	
4:30 pm	103 Kristian Gapp: Individual distinction and microgeographic variation in Black -Throated Green Warbler song	3 Alyssa McInally: The impact of climate change on temperate broadleaf forests in the Niagara region	19 Harnoor Gahir: The role of uropathogenic <i>Escherichia coli</i> filamentation on resistance to clinically relevant antibiotics used to treat urinary tract infections	57 Kyle Banwell: eDNA & scDNA as a tool for characterizing piscivore feeding ecology in lake St. Clair	77 Kyle Kim: Kaiso-depletion regulates androgen receptor downstream target genes associated with increased cell proliferation in triple-negative breast cancer	
4:45 pm	100 Ruth Ogiri: White-throated Sparrow song length variation across singing contexts			67 Reese Miller: Exploring the biases of baited remote underwater videos for aquatic ecology	16 Kevin Kattathara: Studying the effects of cellular aging on clathrin-mediated endocytosis in human cells	

Poster Presentations and Banquet 5:00 -9:00 PM

Sunday 9:00 - 10:15 AM

Start time	Room 3224 Community and Landscape Ecology	Room 3112 Genotypes to Phenotypes	Room 3202 Neuromuscular Biology	Room 3228 Animal Cell Biology
9:00 am	46 Erin Ricaloglu: Balancing generalist and specialist interactions for biodiversity conservation in fragmented landscapes	89 Owen Allard: Maternal genetic background influence on phenotypic variation in <i>Drosophila melanogaster</i>	9 Adam Sutoski: Evaluating the therapeutic potential of MK-8722 in enhancing skeletal muscle regeneration in Duchenne muscular dystrophy	21 Dorcas Adewumi: Can the PreSens OxoDish be used to calculate oxygen consumption rate (OCR) in cell culture?
9:15 am	45 Alyssa Tinella: Taking the permafrost's pulse: Plant community responses to permafrost thaw	7 Maha Jahangir: Modifying antithetic integral feedback (AIF) based on theoretical predictions for enhanced regulation and noise suppression in gene expression	43 Willamina MacDonald: Identification of monoaminergic and cholinergic pathways in cutaneous sensory cells of developing zebrafish	81 Joshua Freimanis: The role of reactive oxygen species in chemotherapy-dependent ribosomal RNA degradation and death in A2780 ovarian tumour cells
9:30 am	85 Kate Pappin: Recovery trajectories of boreal lake zooplankton communities in the face of multiple stressors	75 Holly Stibbe: Potential regulation of the Rac exchange factor PREX1 by the transcription factor Kaiso	42 Guoria Sun: Investigating the role of ARPC4 in human neurodevelopment disorders	25 Grant Booth: Generation of a 5-channel fluorescent imaging technique through the insertion of a long Stokes shift fluorescent protein allowing for the complete imaging of the notch transcriptional activation complex
9:45 am	93 Decklyn Brodersen: Tardigrade diversity and community composition of an Ontarian forest	107 Taha Cheema & Jaskarn Bola: Computational assessment comparing the standard genetic code's ability to minimize error across 54 amino acid properties with an optimized genetic code	8 Erlin Espina: Pharmacological AMPK activation influences skeletal muscle catabolism in cancer cachexia	48 Logan Dammer: Refining cell culture test methods for environmental protection
10:00 am	106 David Storms: The role of tree community functional diversity and water legacy in the fruiting of soil macrofungi		108 Ricky Hong Neuromuscular junction morphology is modestly influenced through AMPK activation in aged mice	34 Deandra Dixon: Development of sex-specific cell culture media

Break 10:15-10:30 AM

Sunday 10:30 - 11:45 AM

Start time	Room 3220 Plant and Fungal Cell Biology	Room 3201 Development and Morphology	Room 3202 Stress	Room 3228 Toxicology and Immunology
10:30 am	31 Shahrzad Rahmani: The effect of autophagy on circadian rhythmicity via target of rapamycin (TOR) pathway in <i>Neurospora crassa</i>	32 Alexandra Weber: A functionally jawless mutant of the zebrafish <i>Danio rerio</i>	28 Robin Brown: Muscle adaptation to high altitude in the world's highest dwelling mammal, <i>Phyllotis vaccarum</i>	86 Ellis Albrecht: Chloride pollution impacts in Boreal lakes: An investigation of physicochemical interactions and biological responses using zooplankton communities as bioindicators
10:45 am	33 Amiel Terrenal: Cycloheximide modulates Target of Rapamycin (TOR) pathway activation in <i>Neurospora crassa</i>	82 Matteo Vocaturo: More on bite force and encephalization in the Family Canidae and in wolverines (<i>Gulo gulo</i>)	23 Kaylyn Montoya: The effects of skeletal muscle-specific AMPK on exercise-induced mitochondrial remodelling	29 Iman Nemar: Impacts of microplastic fiber pollution on benthic invertebrates: biological and environmental implications
11:00 am	101 Amna Arif: Do shade and <i>Vinca minor</i> affect mycorrhizal fungal abundance	87 Naomi Naokwegijig: Meso-carnivores: investigating the diets of the bobcat (<i>Felis rufus</i>) and eastern wolf (<i>Canis lupus Lycaon</i>)	35 Sally Adil: Acute oxygen-dependent epigenetic regulation in rainbow trout liver: Is H3K4me3 linked to induced metabolic genes?	50 Ravleen Kaur: Chronic sublethal neodymium toxicity to Fathead Minnows (<i>Pimephales promelas</i>)
11:15 am	102 Kumar Pokharel: Lipid polyester profiling in stigmas of tobacco (<i>Nicotiana tabacum</i>) mutants	88 Miah Wildschut: The effects of urbanization on the morphology of American toads (<i>Anaxyrus americanus</i>)	51 Mustajab Khalid: The effects of venlafaxine and hypoxia on rainbow trout	78 Cameron Lefebvre: Gastrointestinal parasite influence on glucocorticoids in wild deer mice (<i>Peromyscus maniculatus</i>)
11:30 am	99 Diya Prajapati: Isolation and quantification of lipid polyesters classes in developing stigmas of <i>Nicotiana tabacum</i>	36 Lucy van Haften: Examining the cause and patterns of ultraviolet-induced fluorescence in northern and southern flying squirrels in Ontario, Canada	54 Najiba Soudi: The Role of Claudin-14 in mediating the protective effects of water calcium hardness in fish exposed to high pH water	55 Shakiraa Suntharalingam: Exploring phosphorus concentrations in <i>Tigriopus californicus</i> saltwater habitats and their prolonged effects

Lunch, Featured Talks, and Presentation of Awards 12:00-1:30 PM

Poster Presentations

Nideyinàn Atrium (4th floor) – 5:00 PM to 7:00 PM
Ontario Biology Day 2025

#	Presenter	Poster Title
30	Celeste Abraham	Exploring the efficacy of probiotic treatments in reducing <i>Pseudogymnoascus destructans</i> concentrations in bats affected by white-nose syndrome
57	Hanin Al-Ezzi	A genetic approach to understanding phage-rhizobium interactions
11	Sophia Anazia	Regulation of gsk3 β in nutrient starvation and cellular differentiation via clathrin-mediated lysosomal pathways
1	Emily Archambeault	Using novel physiological indicators to detect investment in and timing of breeding in an arctic-breeding seaduck
68	Washma Arshad	The behavioural effects of artificial light at night in birds: a meta analysis
6	Daniel Bekele	Investigating the role of UGD in <i>Shigella flexneri</i> Polymyxin B resistance through PmrAB-dependent regulatory system
65	Roxanne Bergeron	Effects of soil biota on Ontario tree species
46	Saniya Bhalla	Identifying equivalent genes across the <i>E. coli</i> pangenome
62	Alicia Bruni	Phenotypic variation in pollen Germination and Tube Growth in Stigma Lipid Mutants of Tobacco (<i>Nicotiana tabacum</i>)
59	Emily Chacchione	Microbially-mediated impacts of contaminants present in reclaimed water and biosolids on green pea growth
45	Qing Gui Chung	Investigating a dual-fluorescent mCHERRY-GFP system for tracking salmonella viability during phagosomal maturation
19	Anastasia Cornea	Concentration dependent effects of benzalkoniumchlorides on freshwater benthic invertebrate communities
4	Eric Deaconu	Spatial gene expression patterns of digestive cysteine proteases in <i>tetranychus urticae</i>
44	Connie Di Raimo	Investigating the role of PIKfyve inhibition on lysosome-mitochondria co-migration
51	Alyssa Dupuis	Lights, fish, action: Investigating the effects of light settings on attracting different fish species and sizes
55	Zahava Dworkin	Exploring the mechanisms of <i>Rhizobium leguminosarum</i> biofilm formation upon exposure to bacteriophage: Agricultural applications
40	Abby Eaton	Estimating parasympathetic nervous system involvement in the seabird food-stress response
47	Shahmeen Farooqi	Investigating the role of chromatin remodelling complex component actin-related protein 6 (ARP6) in temperature regulated plant immunity in <i>Arabidopsis</i>
23	Raina Fatima	The role of SHP-1 in macrophage phagocytic capacity during Fc γ RIIB-mediated inhibitory signalling

61	Kendra Favaro	Effects of ionic salts on the physiological and behavioural olfactory responses of aquatic invertebrates
37	Chilyn Fenton-Stickle	Two-eyed seeing in the arctic: Orca-narwhal interactions and threats to Inuit traditions
8	Alizée Fieffé-Bédard	The effect of TNF on density and morphology of microglia in the CA1 region of the brain
41	Nicolas Fragoso Wandurraga	Characterizing the developmental birth windows of PM neurons
66	Haiely Frasier	Does seed predation by granivores in an old-field community differ among plant species?
28	Priscilla Fung	Characterizing the function of the AKNA gene using deletion and knock-in CRISPR methods in the zebrafish
24	Simer Gill	The effects of exercise acclimation treatment on estrogen-related receptor expression and mediation of tumour progression in zebrafish (<i>Danio rerio</i>)
70	Lucy van Haften	An analysis of glaucous gull (<i>Larus hyperboreus</i>) diet from Cornwallis island, Nunavut
14	Ben Harrison	Impact of SERT knockout on surfacing behaviour in <i>Danio Rerio</i>
63	Kristin Hillier	Rapid identification of species at risk habitat use with birdnet
39	Anya Hu	Phosphoenolpyruvic acid (PEP) synthesis in mature chloroplasts of <i>Arabidopsis thaliana</i>
36	Kristen Huang	Implicating the serotonergic system in feeding and growth in zebrafish (<i>Danio rerio</i>)
52	Tiffany Huang	Undergraduate student knowledge, attitudes towards science, perceptions, and experiences with vaccines and recreational IV drips
34	Laiba Jamal	What is the impact of flexible grading schemes on the learning environment and classroom dynamics in science courses?
2	Hania Kusznirewicz	Silk nanoparticle drug delivery of double-stranded RNA as an epithelial ovarian cancer treatment
7	Veronica Langdon	Biomechanical analysis of force production and skating efficiency in female varsity hockey players
21	Sharifa Lomiyev	Effects of PIKfyve lipid kinase inhibition on endoplasmic reticulum in the context of ER remodeling
32	Danielle MacNeil	Exploring the ecological niches of European starlings (<i>Sturnus vulgaris</i>) and tree swallows (<i>Tachycineta bicolor</i>) and insect communities through stable isotopes analysis across PFAS-contaminated and non-contaminated sites in southern Ontario
10	Amasha Malawiya Arachchige	Does microbial function vary with stream health? Comparison of Don River and East Humber tributaries with poor to good quality conditions
15	Shruti Manna	Investigating the impacts of replication stress upon wild-type and GSK3Δ MDA-MB-231 cells in presence and absence of pyruvate
12	Christina Meier	Time-of-Day differences in cell composition in chronic pain

53	Laura Middleton	Does structural enrichment affect the growth and behaviour of captive-reared chinook salmon?
49	Morgane Brading	A bacterial vaginosis model: Following disease progression
22	Shikha Narula	Investigating Pmk1's roles in the fission yeast cell cycle
54	Linda Nguyen	Perceptions of climate change learning among undergraduate students and instructors
5	Alexandria Ojha	Evaluating dimethoate resistance of spider mite populations from southwestern Ontario soybean crops
56	Sofiyyah Oladipupo	The effect of interstrain competition on the nodule occupancy of green pea plants
60	Vaidehi Patel	Amplifying BIRDNET's species identification: is confidence score related to song characteristics?
50	Katrina Pegg	The importance and site of WssF in phenotypic expression of acetylated biofilm cellulose
69	Anton Peter	Assessing swimming performance of the Eastern Sand Darter following hard and soft release techniques
29	Pakin Pongpaiboon	Analysing sex-dependent effects of monocrotaline (MCT) through glycogen storage
58	Olivia Robillard	Resilience in symbiosis: How rhizobia surviving phage attacks enhance plant growth
17	Pooja Samaraweera	Elevated direct bilirubin does not predict elevated conjugated bilirubin in neonates
25	Tayin Seeton	The effects of paternal pre-fertilization THC exposure on fertilization success and early embryonic development
9	Ornella Shaikovsky	The role of a fluorescent Wbox2 peptide in clathrin-mediated endocytosis: Assessing specificity with ikarugamycin
26	Nojan Shishechiha	Effect of arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi on bacterial metabolism in an active hydroponic green wall system
42	Niha Sohail	Synergistic effects of Spz2 and GDI N7-3 mutations on development of the neuromuscular junction in <i>Drosophila melanogaster</i>
27	Arianna Stanley-Harrison	Species in feces: examining the effects of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances on the gut microbiome of mice
35	Ayesha Siddiqua Syeda	The effect of <i>de novo</i> mutation on the phototactic rate of <i>Chlamydomonas reinhardtii</i>
13	Brianna Tapia	Identifying and expressing pip-boxes and HRP-boxes upstream of T3SEs in <i>Xanthomonas</i> and <i>Pseudomonas</i> genomes
3	Vanessa Vashishth	Melanin's impact on chemotherapy efficacy in luminal a breast cancer
67	Audrey Verra	The influence of hard versus soft release methods on Eastern Sand Darter (<i>Ammocrypta pellucida</i>) burrowing behaviour in response to a predator

31	Sydney Williams	Conflict and opportunity: exploring the impact of interference competition on food access in ruby-throated hummingbirds (<i>Archilochus colubris</i>)
33	Benjamin Winchester	Antibiotics and their effects on deer mice (<i>Peromyscus maniculatus</i>) small intestine histomorphology
16	Jessica Yemen	Control of pulmonary vasculature in deer mice (<i>Peromyscus maniculatus</i>)
18	Alacea Yerxa	The role of adaptor protein complexes in phagocytosis of opsonized particles
38	Mutsuko Yoshida	Electrical impedance tomography in divers
64	Bryanna Zimbaro	Investigating the role of multiple factors on tear meniscus height in dry eye disease

Oral Presentation Abstracts

001

PERCEIVED HUMAN PRESENCE ALTERS COYOTE BEHAVIOUR, REDUCING ACTIVITY AND FORAGING

Gabby Kohut

Western University

Coyotes are highly adaptable to urban environments and now inhabit most North American cities, highlighting the need to understand their behavioural responses to human interactions. Humans play a dual role in shaping coyote behaviour, posing risks through direct and indirect predation while simultaneously providing abundant, easily accessible food sources. This creates complex risk-reward trade-offs that coyotes must balance when navigating environments where humans are present. My research investigates these trade-offs by examining how coyotes alter their activity patterns and foraging behaviour in response to perceived human presence. We conducted a manipulative field experiment by broadcasting localized, long-term, predator (human) and control (native frog) vocalizations at 13 independent study sites across the Buffer Nature Preserve in Northern Florida, USA, where we recorded animal behaviours at bait stations using motion-triggered camera traps. Under human vocalization treatments, coyotes were significantly less likely to approach bait stations and spent less time foraging than when under the control treatment. Additionally, we observed differences in coyote behaviour between the vocalization treatments. Our findings demonstrate that coyotes exhibit significant behavioural shifts in response to human presence, providing crucial insights for wildlife management and conservation. As coyote management becomes increasingly necessary, these insights can inform strategies to manipulate their spatial and temporal activity patterns, mitigate human-wildlife conflicts and guide conservation efforts where coyote predation on vulnerable prey requires intervention.

002

ASSESSMENT OF FRAILITY INDEX IN 5XFAD MICE DURING DISEASE PROGRESSION: A NEUROLOGICAL PERSPECTIVE

Maira Chaudhry, BScH Biochemistry and Biomedical Sciences with a minor in Psychology

† Departments of Psychology and Biology (Behaviour, Cognition & Neuroscience Program) University of Windsor Windsor, Ontario, N9B 3P4 Canada,

† Department of Chemistry and Biochemistry University of Windsor, Windsor, Ontario, N9B 3P4 Canada

chaudh54@uwindsor.ca

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a major cause of neurodegenerative morbidity and death globally, affecting cognitive and functional capacities, especially in the elderly. Given its profound effects on memory and cognitive abilities, Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a serious public health concern. Gaining a deeper knowledge of AD is crucial as the population ages. The 5xFAD mouse model, which is well-known for its severe Alzheimer's pathology and quick development, offers a great foundation for researching both cognitive decline and related frailty, a multifactorial disease that many elderly people experience. Research on early-onset AD benefits greatly from the use of the 5xFAD mouse model, a genetic mimic of familial Alzheimer's disease that shows increased amyloid deposition from an early age (Smith & Jones, 2020). Frailty is a medical condition often seen in older adults, characterized by a decline in multiple physiological systems, which results in an increased vulnerability to stressors and a diminished ability to maintain or regain health after an illness or injury. The primary objective of this study is to contribute to the development of a validated frailty index for 5xFAD mice, enhancing the tool's accuracy and applicability in modeling Alzheimer's disease progression. This will involve adapting the comprehensive frailty assessment techniques established by Dalhousie University, which have been widely recognized for their effectiveness in quantifying frailty across various health and aging studies (Rockwood et al., 2005; Pulok et al., 2020).

003

THE IMPACT OF CLIMATE CHANGE ON TEMPERATE BROADLEAF FORESTS IN THE NIAGARA REGION, CANADA.Alyssa McNally*, Micheal Pisaric¹, and David Goldblum².

Department of Biology, Brock University, St. Catharines, Ontario, Canada, L2S 3A1.

Climate change is altering forest ecosystems by shifting temperature and precipitation patterns, increasing competition among tree species, and intensifying disturbances such as wildfires and pest outbreaks. This study investigates how managed (burned) and unmanaged temperate broadleaf forests in the Niagara Region respond to these changes. Fieldwork was conducted in forests under the jurisdiction of the Niagara Parks Commission and Parks Canada, where three 20 × 20 m plots were established in each forest type. Within each plot, all trees were identified to species and cored using an increment borer, yielding a total of 165 samples. Dendrochronological techniques were used to assess tree growth patterns and determine how management practices influence resilience to climate change. It is hypothesized that trees in the managed forests will show greater resilience, benefiting from prescribed burns that reduce competition and improve resource availability. The results of this study will contribute to understanding the role of forest management in mitigating climate change impacts and supporting long-term forest health.

004

TEMPORAL DYNAMICS OF MOUNTAIN PINE BEETLE (*DENDROCTONUS PONDEROSAE*) POPULATION STRUCTURE OVER AN OUTBREAKNiamh Moreton*¹, Zach Balzer¹, Catherine Cullingham² David Coltman¹¹Department of Biology, Western University, London, Ontario, Canada N6A 3K7²Department of Biology, Carleton University, Ottawa, Ontario, Canada K1S 5B6

Climate change has the potential to drastically change the distributions of species, which can lead to changes in population structure, which is the partitioning of genetic differentiation, of expanding populations. A case study for this is the mountain pine beetle (MPB), which is a small insect native to British Columbia. Populations of MPB oscillate in size over time in four phases: endemic, incipient-epidemic, epidemic, and post-epidemic. Spatial population structure is often examined during range changes, whereas temporal dynamics of the same change are rarely studied, and differences between outbreak phases remain a large gap in the vast knowledge of the MPB system. The purpose of this project was to investigate the change in population structure and genetic distance between the epidemic and post-epidemic phases using whole genome sequence (WGS) data. Population structure was analyzed by examining genetic clustering of individuals and by an analysis of molecular variance (AMOVA), and genetic distances among sampling sites were used to characterize isolation by distance. Populations were moderately spatially structured, with an F_{ST} value from the epidemic phase samples of 0.03 and an F_{ST} value from the post-epidemic phase samples of 0.08. Along with this, populations showed clear isolation by distance patterns in both the epidemic and post-epidemic outbreak phases. From this, we found that genetic differentiation between sites was driven by space and weakly differentiated by time. This provides insight into the temporal dynamics of MPB outbreaks, and thus the recent MPB expansion, supporting further research into spatial dynamics.

005

STUDYING THE ROLE OF UBIQUITINATION IN CLATHRIN-MEDIATED ENDOCYTOSIS DURING REPLICATIVE AGING

Korkmaz, Basak*, Kenneth Gabriel Antenor, Mojca Mattiazzi Usaj

Toronto Metropolitan University

Clathrin-mediated endocytosis (CME) is an essential and highly conserved cellular process where external materials and plasma membrane (PM) components get internalized into the cell. Internalized cargo is recycled back to the PM, sorted to other organelles, or degraded in vacuoles/lysosomes. CME involves the sequential recruitment of proteins from several functional modules, including early proteins, coat proteins, WASp/myosin, actin and amphiphysin. Ubiquitination plays a role in CME by marking cargo for internalization, with α -arrestin family proteins acting as adaptors for the ubiquitin ligase Rsp5. Deubiquitinases counteract this by removing ubiquitin, thus recycling the CME machinery. We have shown that CME progressively declines during replicative aging, and this depends on vacuolar pH and the TORC1-Npr1 signalling pathway. In this project, we aim to determine the effect loss of ubiquitination/deubiquitination has on CME in replicatively aging budding yeast cells. We constructed single and double mutants of ubiquitination and deubiquitination genes, and fluorescently tagged the Sla1 coat protein to monitor CME dynamics. We used wheat germ-agglutinin, a lectin that binds to chitin-rich bud scars, to determine the replicative age of individual cells. We then prepared imaging samples of our strains grown in control condition, in lifespan-expanding caloric restriction condition, and treatment in the V-ATPase inhibitor concanamycin-A. We acquired real-time movies using spinning disk confocal microscopy, extracted quantitative data on endocytic patch formation, and evaluated differences in CME dynamics between young and old cells. With this project we aim to understand how ubiquitination/deubiquitination defects affect endocytosis during replicative aging in budding yeast.

006

HOST-VIRUS-VIROPHAGE DYNAMICS: VIROPHAGE-MEDIATED PROTECTION OF FRESHWATER HAPTOPHYTE ALGAEGeorge R Thomas¹, Ichiro Inamoto¹, Gurshan S Bajaj¹, Steven M Short¹¹Department of Biology, University of Toronto Mississauga, Mississauga, Ontario, Canada, L5L 1C6

Several giant dsDNA viruses and their putative virophages that co-infect their host cells are known to parasitize the globally distributed, freshwater haptophyte alga *Chrysochromulina parva*. This study examined the influence of the virophage CpVV-Moe on the growth of *C. parva* and CpV-BQ3 replication. Triplicate experimental infections were set up with variable ratios of Moe:BQ3 (10:1, 900:1, 1000:1) at a constant multiplicity of infection for BQ3 (~0.01 viruses per cell). Each infection was monitored over 20 days using bright-field microscopy and quantitative PCR to estimate cell and virus/virophage abundances, respectively. Our results demonstrated that Moe protected *C. parva*'s growth in the presence of BQ3, but the effect depended on the ratio of Moe to BQ3. At higher Moe-to-BQ3 ratios (e.g. 1000:1), BQ3 replication was suppressed and its final abundance did not exceed the initial $\sim 5.5 \times 10^4$ units/mL inoculum. In the same treatment, *C. parva*'s abundance after 20 days ($\sim 2.07 \times 10^6$ cells/mL) was comparable to that in the no-infection control ($\sim 2.27 \times 10^6$ cells/mL). Conversely, when infected with BQ3 alone, *C. parva*'s abundance was observed at 2.8×10^5 cells/mL while BQ3's abundance increased 3,000-fold reaching $\sim 1.55 \times 10^6$ units/mL. At lower Moe-to-BQ3 ratios, the protective effect of Moe was negligible, and infections with Moe alone demonstrated that it did not replicate without BQ3, confirming its obligate dependence on BQ3 for its replication. These findings define the role of CpVV-Moe in this tripartite infection system, highlighting the influence of virophages on algal virus dynamics and primary production in aquatic ecosystems.

007

MODIFYING ANTITHETIC INTEGRAL FEEDBACK (AIF) BASED ON THEORETICAL PREDICTIONS FOR ENHANCED REGULATION AND NOISE SUPPRESSION IN GENE EXPRESSIONMaha Jahangir*¹, Matthew Newman¹, David McMillen¹¹Department of Chemical and Physical Sciences, University of Toronto Mississauga, Ontario, Canada L5L 1C6

Precise regulation of gene expression is crucial for creating stable and reliable biological systems, fundamental to synthetic biology advancements. Controlling gene expression finely tunes cellular functions, leading to predictable and efficient outcomes. Antithetic Integral Feedback (AIF) is a biochemical feedback mechanism that regulates intracellular molecular species in *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*). However, traditional AIF implementations often increase noise, complicating precise regulation. Recent theories suggest robust regulation and minimal noise can be achieved under specific conditions. This research aims to experimentally validate these predictions by replicating and modifying the AIF system to enhance performance. Modifications involve altering the feedback network to reduce the target species' production, thereby decreasing noise levels. The study includes designing and assembling DNA constructs using molecular cloning techniques, and integrating these constructs into *E. coli* strains, and verifying functionality through PCR. Fluorescence microscopy will measure protein expression levels, followed by data analysis to assess gene expression fluctuations. The objective is to demonstrate that the modified AIF system can achieve near-perfect regulation with reduced noise, enhancing gene expression systems' stability. This research will contribute to developing reliable engineered biological circuits, offering insights into designing efficient gene regulation mechanisms in synthetic biology.

008

PHARMACOLOGICAL AMPK ACTIVATION INFLUENCES SKELETAL MUSCLE CATABOLISM IN CANCER CACHEXIAErlin B Espina^{1*}, Magda Lesinski¹, Andrew I Mikhail¹, Saumyaa Rishi¹, Rozhin Raziee¹, Irena A Rebalka², Luca J Delfinis³, Christopher GR Perry³, Thomas J Hawke², Vladimir Ljubicic¹¹Department of Kinesiology, McMaster University, Hamilton ON, Canada²Department of Pathology and Molecular Medicine, McMaster University, Hamilton ON, Canada³School of Kinesiology & Health Science, Muscle Health Research Centre, York University, Toronto ON, Canada

Cancer cachexia is a muscle wasting syndrome affecting more than half of people with cancer and characterized by the loss of skeletal muscle mass, adipose tissue mass, anemia, anorexia, and loss of strength. These energetic and functional deficits impact treatment efficacy, thereby worsening patient prognosis. AMP-activated protein kinase (AMPK) plays a key role in cellular energy homeostasis and muscle preservation and has been implicated in cancer cachexia. We investigated the impact of direct pharmacological AMPK activation via MK-8722 (MK) in mice inoculated subcutaneously with Lewis Lung Carcinoma (LLC) cells. LLC mice received oral administration of MK (LLC^{MK}) or PBS (LLC^{PBS}) starting 7-days post-LLC inoculation and tissues were collected 21-days thereafter. Skeletal muscle protein quantification with western blotting identified increases in LC3I and LC3II in LLC^{MK} compared to LLC^{Veh} and PBS^{Veh} respectively, while p62 accumulated in LLC^{Veh} but decreased in LLC^{MK}. In response to cancer cachexia, immunofluorescent staining of the extensor digitorum longus muscle (EDL) demonstrated a significant increase in p-ATG16L puncti in LLC^{Veh} and LLC^{MK} compared to PBS^{Veh} (p=0.0027 and p<0.0001, respectively), indicating phosphorylation of ATG16L by ULK1, a kinase activated by AMPK. MK treatment in LLC mice did not restore p-ATG16L levels to baseline and remained elevated. Although, cancer-related increases in MURF1 and Atrogin1 mRNA content improved with MK treatment. Collectively, the data suggests that MK treatment influences catabolic processes during cancer cachexia, as indicated by improvements in markers of autophagy and atrophy. Future aims include assessing mitochondrial morphology and mitophagy to better understand muscular adaptations in cancer cachexia.

009

EVALUATING THE THERAPEUTIC POTENTIAL OF MK-8722 IN ENHANCING SKELETAL MUSCLE REGENERATION IN DUCHENNE MUSCULAR DYSTROPHY

Adam Sutoski

McMaster University

Introduction: Duchenne muscular dystrophy (DMD) is the most common form of muscular dystrophy, characterized by chronic muscle damage due to mutations in the dystrophin gene. The loss of functional dystrophin protein causes muscles to experience continuous injury and impaired regeneration, leading to the replacement of muscle by fibrous and fatty connective tissue. Pharmacological stimulation of adenosine monophosphate-activated protein kinase (AMPK) has shown promise in mitigating DMD pathology. In an acute investigation, treatment with the AMPK agonist MK-8722 (MK) promoted a slow, oxidative muscle phenotype with heightened disease resistance. Considering this finding, this study aimed to determine the therapeutic potential of MK on skeletal muscle regeneration in DMD. Methods: Five-week-old male D2.mdx and DBA/2J control mice (n = 8) were administered MK (5 mg/kg) or a vehicle solution daily for seven weeks via oral gavage. Following treatment, the triceps muscles were harvested for analysis of muscle regeneration. Immunofluorescence was used to investigate the presence of muscle fibres expressing embryonic myosin heavy chain (eMHC) and centrally located nuclei. Results: We found that MK treatment reduced the number of eMHC-positive fibres ($p < 0.05$) but did not significantly alter the amount of centrally nucleated fibres in the triceps muscles compared to genotype-matched, vehicle-treated mice. Conclusion: These results indicate that pharmacological AMPK activation via MK administration attenuates dystrophic muscle damage, demonstrating its potential as a therapeutic intervention for DMD. Future directions for this study will assess the role of MK on muscle quality by measuring inflammatory cell infiltration and collagen deposition.

010

CHARACTERIZATION OF QUEE-DEPENDENT FILAMENTATION IN *ESCHERICHIA COLI* AND *YERSINIA PSEUDOTUBERCULOSIS*Sofya Rudovskaya*¹, Gozel Atakgayeveva^{1,2}, Roberto J. Botelho^{1,2}, Joseph McPhee^{1,2}.

1. Department of Chemistry and Biology, Toronto Metropolitan University, Toronto, Ontario, Canada M5B 2K3

2. Graduate Program in Molecular Science, Toronto Metropolitan University, Toronto, Ontario, Canada M5B 2K3

Bacterial pathogens like *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*), *Salmonella*, and *Yersinia pseudotuberculosis* (*Y. pseudotuberculosis*) are all *Enterobacteriaceae* that can cause foodborne illnesses. The immune system protects against these infections through antimicrobial peptides (AMPs) like LL-37, which disrupt bacterial membranes. However, bacteria have evolved countermeasures like filamentation, a process where cells elongate without dividing. Our lab has shown that filamentation helps bacteria survive LL-37 attacks. QueE, an enzyme involved in queuosine biosynthesis and cell division control, regulates filamentation. The PhoQ/PhoP system controls *queE*, and while the gene is conserved, its function varies by species. In *E. coli*, *queE* orthologs from *Salmonella* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, induce filamentation, but those from more distant species like *Yersinia pestis* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* do not. Here, we investigated the role of *queE*_{Ec} and *queE*_{Yp} in cell division control in both *E. coli* and *Y. pseudotuberculosis*. In *E. coli*, overexpression of *queE* orthologs from closely related species induces filamentation. However, overexpression of *queE*_{Ec} and *queE*_{Yp} in *Y. pseudotuberculosis* did not induce filamentation. A positive control using *sulA* from *E. coli*, a component of the SOS system, induced pronounced filamentation in *Y. pseudotuberculosis*. As an enterobacter, *Y. pseudotuberculosis* provides a valuable model for comparing filamentation regulation with *E. coli* and related species, helping to identify differences in cell division control. These results highlight species-specific regulation of filamentation and offer insights into bacterial adaptation under host stress.

011

HORIZONTAL TRANSMISSION OF MODIFIED NEGEVIRUS VIA ORAL INGESTION OF SPIKED SUGAR MEAL.

Andrea Fernandes*

Department of Biological Science and Health Sciences, Brock University, St. Catherines, Ontario, Canada L2S 3A1

Vector-borne diseases (VBDs) pose significant public health challenges, with mosquitoes acting as primary vectors for arboviruses such as dengue, Zika, and chikungunya viruses. *Aedes aegypti*, in particular, is a key transmitter due to its close association with human populations. While traditional vector control strategies have focused on reducing mosquito populations, insect-specific viruses (ISVs) have emerged as a promising alternative for disrupting arbovirus transmission. Negevirus, a newly identified group of ISVs, can potentially interfere with arboviral replication, providing a novel biocontrol approach. This study aims to assess the horizontal transmission efficiency of a modified Negevirus in *A. aegypti* mosquitoes via oral ingestion of a sugar meal. Using a Negevirus construct containing a green fluorescent protein (GFP) marker and a 2A self-cleaving sequence, we seek to establish its ability to infect and persist in mosquito populations. *A. aegypti* mosquitoes were reared under controlled laboratory conditions and exposed to a sucrose solution containing the modified Negevirus at the adult stage. The infection rates were quantified using two-step quantitative PCR (qPCR) after 14 days post-infection, confirming viral genome presence within the mosquitoes. This study will enhance our understanding of mosquito-virus interactions and pathways of transmission and assess Negevirus as a potential biocontrol agent. By evaluating its ability to infect *A. aegypti*, our findings would support the development of ISV-based vector control strategies, paving the way for environmentally sustainable and targeted approaches to mitigating arbovirus transmission.

012

IMPACT OF ECOWOOL ON CROP QUALITYIsabelle Venzon*¹, Vaughn Mangal², and Liette Vasseur¹.¹Department of Biological Sciences, Brock University, St. Catharines, Ontario, Canada L2S 3A1²Department of Chemistry, Brock University, St. Catharines, Ontario, Canada L2S 3A1

In order to reduce environmental impact, sustainable agriculture is reliant on organic amendments to improve soil fertility and promote plant growth. Sheep wool as an amendment is slowly being researched more, but further research is needed to determine its effects on nutrient levels and plant growth within a greenhouse setting. This project explores the impact of sheep wool pellets from EcoWool Canada on the growth and uptake of nutrients in various crops including perpetual spinach, roquette arugula, and White Icicle radish. Each of these crops were grown in a greenhouse at Brock University and treated with five different treatments including 3% EcoWool (T1), 5% EcoWool (T2), 10% EcoWool (T3), synthetic fertilizer (T4), and water as the control (T5). The plant tissues were analyzed for chlorophyll and various nutrients, and results showed that in many cases nutrient uptake was affected by EcoWool additions, but this was also often crop dependant due to different plant needs and compositions. In arugula crops there was an increasing linear relationship between chlorophyll levels and EcoWool percentage which could be due to increasing nitrogen levels with EcoWool additions. Copper concentration in all crops also increased as percent EcoWool increased likely because copper is present in sheep wool and is essential for production and development of plants. The use of EcoWool as an amendment could enhance soil health and plant productivity, reduce synthetic fertilizer use, and promote a more sustainable option for agricultural practices.

013

THE INFLUENCE OF POSITION AND COLOURS OF STICKY TRAPS ON LEAFHOPPER DETECTION IN ORGANIC VINEYARDSAngel Ayele Lainscek*¹, Liette Vasseur¹, Kiyoko Gotanda¹¹Department of Biological Sciences, Brock University, St. Catharines, Ontario, Canada, L2S

Leafhoppers are sap-sucking insects that have become prominent pests in Canadian vineyards. They damage crops, and some species can spread plant diseases through their feeding habits. As a result, effective monitoring of leafhopper presence is crucial for vineyard management. They damage crops, with some species spreading plant diseases through their feeding habits, making effective monitoring crucial for vineyard management.

This study used sticky traps to monitor leafhopper populations in three organic vineyards in the Niagara Region. Three coloured sticky traps (yellow, red, and green) were placed at three different height levels within the same panels of grapevine rows, positioned at the edge or in the middle of the rows. Rows were classified as internal (surrounded by other grapevine rows) or external (next to open land on one side). The traps were set up for three days in August and three days in September, and the collected invertebrates were identified in lab.

The results suggest that trap colour, trap height, and the row's position (internal vs. external) has a tendency of influencing leafhopper presence. However, the trap's position within the row (edge vs. middle) and the cover crop treatments showed more inconclusive effects on leafhopper abundance.

014

THE EFFECT OF SEX ON THE THERMOREGULATORY BEHAVIOUR OF THE GUPPY (*POECILIA RETICULATA*)

Margaret Kitney

Department of Biological Sciences, Brock University, 1812 Sir Isaac Brock Way, St. Catharines, Ontario, Canada L2S 3A1

Animals thermoregulate to maintain a core body temperature that is within their optimal physiological range. As ectotherms, fish must rely on external conditions to regulate their body temperature and primarily do this by changing their behaviour. Studies have found that the temperatures that fish select and tolerate change based on the animal's health, sex, and reproductive state. However, few studies have focused solely on the effect of sex on thermal preference. The current study assesses the thermoregulatory behaviour of guppies (*Poecilia reticulata*) in a dual-chambered shuttle box system to determine whether male and female fish have different thermal preferences. We found that there was no significant difference between the temperatures that male and female guppies selected in the shuttle box. These results differ from previous work that suggested that male and female guppies do have different thermal preferences. This study provides background for further work on whether gravid female guppies select different temperatures than non-gravid females and males, which would add to the growing research on how gravidity affects thermoregulation in a diverse range of species.

015

MOTHER-DAUGHTER PROTEIN ASYMMETRY DURING BUDDING YEAST REPLICATIVE AGING

Ummuhan Canatan*, Quinlan Cotnam, Neroshan Sritharan, Mojca Mattiazzi Usaj

Department of Chemistry and Biology, Toronto Metropolitan University, Ontario, Canada M5B 2K3

Budding yeast *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* undergo asymmetric cell division, where an aging mother cell produces a rejuvenated daughter. During this process, damaged cellular components are usually retained in the mother, while rejuvenating factors are enriched in the daughter. As yeast progress through their replicative lifespan (number of cell divisions before senescence), they lose the ability to produce rejuvenated daughters. One of the consequences of asymmetric inheritance is the uneven distribution of proteins during cell division. However, there is limited information on how protein asymmetry changes as the cells age. Using high-throughput microscopy, we aim to observe the effects of replicative aging on asymmetrical localization and abundance of individual proteins. First, we have compiled a list of 174 proteins with reported asymmetry between mother and daughter cells. This includes proteins enriched in mother or daughter cells, asymmetry generating genes (AGGs) and long-lived asymmetrically retained proteins (LARPs). Next, we used the synthetic genetic array (SGA) method to introduce cytosolic and nuclei fluorescent markers into strains expressing GFP fusion constructs of our asymmetric proteins of interest. We then acquired fluorescence micrographs of the constructed strains with an automated high-content imaging system. Quantitative analysis of cell features will allow us to assess changes in protein abundance and localization between aging mothers and their daughters. This data will provide insights into the role of protein asymmetry in cellular aging and help identify new aging and rejuvenation factors.

016

STUDYING THE EFFECTS OF CELLULAR AGING ON CLATHRIN-MEDIATED ENDOCYTOSIS IN HUMAN CELLS

Kevin Joe Kattathara, Allie Spangaro, Mojca Mattiazzi Usaj

Department of Chemistry & Biology, Toronto Metropolitan University, Toronto, Ontario, Canada, M5B 2K3

Aging is a complex process that leads to cellular senescence, a state of irreversible growth arrest accompanied by extensive cellular changes. Senescence is characterized by alterations in trafficking pathways, affecting various cellular functions. Clathrin-mediated endocytosis (CME) is critical in maintaining cellular homeostasis by regulating nutrient uptake, receptor recycling, and signal transduction. However, its dynamics in aging and senescent cells remain largely unexplored. This study aims to investigate CME in aging and senescent cells by examining the morphology and dynamics of clathrin-coated pits (CCPs) using live-cell total internal reflection fluorescence (TIRF) microscopy. To investigate the effects of senescence on CME, we used ARPE-19 cells stably expressing GFP-tagged clathrin. Senescence was induced by activating the DNA damage pathway with the drug doxorubicin, or by inducing oxidative stress with hydrogen peroxide. We observed that senescent cells exhibit unevenly distributed CCP clusters, a striking contrast to the non-senescent controls. To determine if these structures correspond to bona fide CME sites, we performed immunofluorescence staining for Adaptor Protein 2 (AP2), a key component of CME. Image analysis confirmed signal overlap between clathrin and AP2 in these clustered structures. Next, we are serially passaging cells to determine when CME alterations first appear during aging, and which mechanistic steps in forming clathrin-coated pits (CCPs) are affected. By elucidating how CME is altered during cellular aging, this study seeks to provide insights into the molecular mechanisms underlying senescence and identify potential early markers of age-related cellular decline.

017

SHINING A LIGHT ON THE SHADOWS: EXAMINING THE CASCADING EFFECTS IN NATIVE GARDENS ON NOCTURNAL POLLINATORS AND THEIR PREDATORS

Britt Petersen*, Sarah Jamieson, Cayleih Robertson

Department of Biology, Trent University, Peterborough, Ontario, Canada K9L 0G2

Native gardens are planted in urban areas to attract and support pollinators such as moths, but limited research has examined the cascading effects native gardens have on moth predators. Using non-invasive acoustic technology, I recorded the presence of bat species at 90 native gardens and 90 control sites in Peterborough, ON between May – October 2024. These recordings were taken within two hours of sunset during the optimal foraging time for bats. I then analyzed the data using a general linear mixed model to account for potential variables such as Julian date, light intensity, and time after sunset. Results showed the presence of tri-colored bats (*Perimyotis subflavus*), silver-haired bats (*Lasionycteris noctivagans*), little brown myotis (*Myotis lucifugus*), and big brown bats (*Eptesicus fuscus*) increased at native garden sites compared to control sites located 100m away. In contrast, eastern red bats (*Lasiurus borealis*) had an increased presence at control sites compared to native garden sites. Hoary bat (*Lasiurus cinereus*) results were inconclusive, and neither northern long-eared myotis (*M. septentrionalis*) nor eastern small-footed myotis (*M. leibii*) were detected during the study. These results suggest that native gardens attract several endangered species of insectivorous bats found in urban environments. Conversely, there may be unknown factors attracting eastern red bats to other landscape covers.

018

DO ELEPHANTS IN PROTECTED AREAS KNOW THAT THEY ARE PROTECTED? AN EXPERIMENTAL TEST OF ANTIPREDATOR BEHAVIOURS IN AFRICAN ELEPHANTS, *LOXODONTA AFRICANA*.

Kennedy Jamieson*, and Liana Zanette.

Department of Biology, Western University, London, ON N6A 5B7, Canada

African elephants, *Loxodonta africana*, are of major interest to the South African National Parks Service due to their endangered status and the disruptive activities of their increasing local populations. Previous experimental evidence has demonstrated that elephants utilize ecological knowledge to adjust their antipredator behaviour according to the level of perceived predation threat. Using 1,421 videos collected via Automated Behavioural Response systems, we analyzed eight different elephant behavioural responses after exposure to auditory playbacks of human vocalizations, lion vocalizations, tourist sounds (engine noise or engine noise mixed with human vocalizations), and control noise (bird calls). The playbacks were broadcast across two regions with contrasting ecotourism levels within Greater Kruger National Park (GKNP), South Africa. The results demonstrate that the strength of elephant antipredator behaviours differed significantly across playback treatments, whereas ambient ecotourism level did not have a significant effect on behaviour. Specifically, elephants were more likely to respond aggressively to lion vocalizations and evasively in response to human vocalizations regardless of ecotourism activity. This suggests that social trauma from past culling in GKNP has a long-lasting influence on elephant antipredator responses, making them more fearful of humans than lions, even when vocalizations are associated with benign tourism. This provides experimental support for utilizing human playbacks as a non-lethal elephant management tool in African protected areas.

019

THE ROLE OF UROPATHOGENIC *ESCHERICHIA COLI* FILAMENTATION ON RESISTANCE TO CLINICALLY RELEVANT ANTIBIOTICS USED TO TREAT URINARY TRACT INFECTIONSHarnoor Gahir*¹, Joseph McPhee²

Department of Chemistry and Biology, Toronto Metropolitan University, Toronto, Ontario, Canada M5B 2K3

Uropathogenic *Escherichia coli* (UPEC) is the primary cause of urinary tract infections (UTIs), affecting 150 million people worldwide annually. In severe cases, UPEC infections can progress to pyelonephritis and urosepsis, causing death in 10-30% of the infected population. Upon entering the bladder epithelium, UPEC cells can undergo filamentation — a morphological change that enables growth without the occurrence of cellular division. Previous research in the McPhee lab has shown that filamentous cells exhibit enhanced resistance to elements of the host innate immune system. Given the high failure rates of current treatments, and that certain antibiotics induce filamentation, we wanted to investigate whether genetically induced filamentous UPEC cells would result in altered susceptibility to drugs commonly prescribed for these infections. In this study, filamentation was induced in wild-type *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*) through the overexpression of QueE and SulA, both of which use different mechanisms to interact with FtsZ polymers at the mid-cell site to inhibit cellular division. The susceptibility of each strain to antibiotics was assessed through minimum inhibitory concentration assays. Although no statistically significant alteration in susceptibility was observed for ciprofloxacin or trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole, *E. coli* expressing QueE showed a statistically significant increase in susceptibility to nitrofurantoin when compared to control strains. Nitrofurantoin is a commonly prescribed antibiotic with an unusual multi-target mechanism of action. This work suggests that the induction of filamentation can alter susceptibility to a routinely administered antibiotic and provides key evidence for studying this further.

020

THE IMPACT OF HEAT AND HYDROXYUREA ON REACTIVE OXYGEN SPECIES LEVEL IN SCHIZOSACCHAROMYCES POMBE.Intesar Shah*¹, Venezia Benvenuto² Sarah Sabatinos^{1,2,*}¹Department of Chemistry and Biology, Toronto Metropolitan University, Toronto, Ontario, Canada, M5B 2K3²Yeates School of Graduate Studies, Toronto Metropolitan University, Toronto, Ontario, Canada, M5B 2K3

*www.SabatinosLab.com

Cells constantly encounter environmental stresses that can disrupt homeostasis and threaten viability. Environmental stress including heat can influence cellular metabolites, including reactive oxygen species (ROS). ROS play a variety of functions in the cell, but can cause damage to proteins and nucleic acids when produced in excess. The fission yeast *Schizosaccharomyces pombe* (*S. pombe*) is an effective model organism for studying eukaryotic cell cycle mechanisms. Cds1 and Rad3 are cell cycle checkpoint proteins that are involved in the regulation of the *S. pombe* cell cycle. Work in the Sabatinos lab demonstrated that environmental stress signaling may be similar to oxidative stress responses in *S. pombe*. In this study, we investigate the effects of heat stress and hydroxyurea (HU) treatment on ROS level in *S. pombe* checkpoint deletion mutants. Using an ROS-sensitive fluorescent dye called CellROX Green, we stained cells and assessed ROS level using flow cytometry. We tested the impact of DNA replication checkpoint function by comparing ROS levels in wild type and *rad3Δ* or *cds1Δ* mutant cells. The absence of Rad3 (*rad3Δ*) or Cds1 (*cds1Δ*) makes cells unable to stabilize DNA replication forks in HU causing death. We hypothesized that loss of replication checkpoint would increase ROS level. We compared the effect of HU on ROS with heat treatment. We have previously shown that heat decreases HU effects. We found that ROS increases in heat, but decreases in HU. This research provides insights into how eukaryotic cells modulate redox homeostasis when checkpoint pathways are compromised, contributing to a deeper understanding of oxidative stress biology.

021

DEVELOPMENT OF AN INEXPENSIVE METHOD FOR MEASURING OXYGEN CONSUMPTION RATE IN CULTURED CELLS IN SITU.Dorcas Adewumi*¹, Jacob Wiebe², Ricardo Alva³, Nick Taber⁴, Jeffrey A Stuart⁵.¹Department of Biological Sciences, Brock University, St. Catherines Ontario, Canada L2S 3A1

Oxygen consumption rate (OCR) is a key indicator of cellular metabolism, providing insights into mitochondrial function and metabolic adaptation. Traditional OCR measurement methods for cells in culture have some limitations: the Clark electrode is typically used with stirred cell suspensions, requiring their trypsinization from culture plates; the Seahorse Extracellular Flux Analyzer is used with adherent cells, but it is relatively costly, invasive, and labor-intensive. There is a need for inexpensive and non-invasive methods for measuring OCR in cultured cells in situ. Here I describe the use of the PreSens OxoDish system to continuously monitor OCR in cell culture. The OxoDishes have oxygen-sensitive optodes adhered to the bottom of each well that report local oxygen levels. Fick's First Law was used to calculate cellular OCR in an open system at steady state from this pericellular oxygen level. MCF7 human breast cancer cells were used to validate the method since a number of OCR per cell values have been published and could be used for comparison. For MCF7 cells growing in standard conditions (DMEM with 10% FBS) my method yielded OCR values of 14-32 amol/cell/s, compared to 32.5-39.9 amol/cell/s reported using other methods. This suggests that my method can be applied to OCR measurements of cultured adherent cells, which will be a valuable tool in the field.

022

THE EFFECTS OF WARMING ON PREDATOR-PREY INTERACTIONS USING MICROARTHROPODS AS A MODEL.

Emily Laver-Shareski*, Pedro da Silva Conceição, Zoë Lindo.

Department of Biology, Western University, London, Ontario, Canada, N6A, 3K7.

Climate change is estimated to increase global temperatures between 2°C-6°C within the next century. Warming of this degree will have several effects on how species interact, such as predator-prey relationships. For instance, if predators and their prey differ in their ideal temperature range (T_{opt}), then warming may benefit one while having adverse effects on the other. Using microarthropod models in a lab-based mesocosm warming experiment, the objective of this study was to examine predator-prey interactions under different temperature scenarios. Specifically, this mesocosm warming experiment aimed to understand how warming of +6°C influences predator-prey ratios in samples collected from two systems that differ in their growing season temperatures (cool-temperature = 12°C vs. warm-temperature = 18°C). I found that in the cool-temperature system, warming of +6°C had no effect on predator abundances but increased prey abundances, resulting in a lower predator-prey ratio than in the control temperature. In the warm-temperature system, warming of +6°C had no effect on either predators or prey, resulting in no significant difference in the predator-prey ratio between the two temperature treatments. This experiment demonstrates that warming may lead to thermal mismatches in predator-prey dynamics, particularly in cool-temperature systems.

023

THE EFFECTS OF SKELETAL MUSCLE-SPECIFIC AMPK ON EXERCISE-INDUCED MITOCHONDRIAL REMODELLING

Kaylyn M Montoya*, Andrew I Mikhail, Sean Y Ng, Stephanie R Mattina, Vladimir Ljubicic
McMaster University, 1280 main St. West, Hamilton, ON, L8S 4K1

AMP-activated protein kinase (AMPK) mediates mitochondrial functions like biogenesis, dynamics and mitophagy in response to energetic stress. Its importance in mitochondrial adaptation following chronic exercise remains to be fully elucidated. Previous literature has utilized transgenic mice with germline deletion of skeletal muscle AMPK, which exhibit exercise intolerance interfering with normal muscle development. The purpose of this study is to investigate exercise-induced mitochondrial adaptations in a novel muscle-specific AMPK $\beta 1\beta 2$ inducible knockout (imKO) model. Male and female 16 weeks old wild-type (WT) and imKO mice were treated with tamoxifen daily for five consecutive days. Twelve weeks after the last tamoxifen dose, WT and imKO mice were randomly assigned to sedentary and exercise groups. The exercise protocol consisted of progressive treadmill training 5 days/week over 6 weeks. Subsequently, quadriceps muscles were collected for high resolution respirometry, immunoblotting and transmission electron microscopy (TEM). The basal mitochondrial leak from complex I (CI) showed no significant differences between WT and imKO groups. We observed a significant increase in ADP-stimulated CI-specific and CI+II specific oxygen consumption rates in exercised WT animals. However, no differences were observed in mitochondrial respiration with training in imKO mice. We next quantified IMF mitochondria using TEM. Sedentary WT and imKO mice had similar amounts of IMF mitochondria. Exercise elicited a significant increase in IMF mitochondria in exercised WT animals only relative to sedentary counterparts. Data suggest that AMPK plays a role in exercise-induced mitochondrial upregulation. Future work aims to elucidate the impact of AMPK on mitochondrial morphology and its role in exercise adaptation.

024

INVESTIGATING AND DISRUPTING ANTIBIOTIC REPRESSION BY THE GLOBAL REGULATOR WBLA IN *STREPTOMYCES VENEZUELAE*

Nour G. Elshobary*¹, Lauren A. Tiller¹, Marie A. Elliot¹

Michael G. DeGroot Institute for Infectious Disease Research and the Department of Biology, McMaster University, Hamilton, Ontario, Canada L8S 4L8

Regulating antibiotic production by *Streptomyces* bacteria involves the integration of a myriad of environmental and developmental signals. Recently, the transcription factor WblA has been identified as a global repressor of antibiotic synthesis in multiple *Streptomyces* spp., where disruption of *wblA* results in increased antibiotic production. Due to the increasing incidence of antibiotic resistance, *wblA* is an interesting target to exploit for the discovery of novel antibiotics with unique mechanisms of action. Nevertheless, how WblA controls antibiotic production remains unknown. To determine how WblA exerts its regulatory activity, Chromatin Immunoprecipitation Sequencing (ChIP-seq) in the model *Streptomyces venezuelae* will be conducted. This involved generating a tagged variant of *wblA* and introducing it into a $\Delta wblA$ background. Following this, the tagged WblA can be cross-linked to DNA, the chromosomal DNA sheared, WblA-DNA complexes are purified using tag-specific antibodies, the stabilizing cross-links are reversed, and the associated DNA fragments are purified and sequenced. In parallel, we are designing constructs that will allow us to manipulate *wblA* expression and promote new antibiotic production. We have developed a CRISPR-based interference construct that is intended to disrupt transcription of *wblA* in any *Streptomyces* species, as the *wblA* sequence is highly conserved across this bacterial genus. As *Streptomyces* encode a diverse array of specialized metabolites, introducing the *wblA* CRISPR interference construct has the capacity to relieve repression of novel antibiotics. Collectively, these studies are providing insight into the mechanistic control of antibiotic repression by WblA and generating genetic tools to manipulate it for the purpose of antibiotic discovery.

025

GENERATION OF A 5-CHANNEL FLUORESCENT IMAGING TECHNIQUE THROUGH THE INSERTION OF A LONG STOKES SHIFT FLUORESCENT PROTEIN ALLOWING FOR THE COMPLETE IMAGING OF THE NOTCH TRANSCRIPTIONAL ACTIVATION COMPLEX

Grant Booth*, Aleksandar Necakov

Department of Biology, Brock University, Saint Catharines, Ontario, Canada L2S 31A

In the field of biology, molecular pathways have been discovered, developed, and studied for over 100 years. The principles and foundations developed by molecular biology and biotechnology are utilized to obtain a better understanding of these pathways, which allow for the production of pharmaceuticals, biological products, and medical discoveries worldwide. The localization, activity, and dynamics of these pathways were originally hypothesized, but modern technology, such as fluorescent microscopy and genetic engineering, have allowed for the visualization and quantification of these pathways. The information obtained from these visual models elucidate the mechanisms behind these pathways and the effects that they have on the cells in which they occur. Techniques such as multi-channel image analysis can be used to gain a greater understanding of how these signalling pathways function, and how the individual proteins which comprise these pathways and complexes localize and interact with each other. Unfortunately, many large complexes such as the Notch transcriptional activation complex, simply contain too many elements to be imaged in their entirety by current 4-channel fluorescent image acquisition techniques. This negatively impacts the ability for these techniques to accurately measure and illustrate the dynamics and interplay of the individual proteins of which these complexes are comprised. The insertion of an additional channel using a fluorescent protein, LSSmOrange, should expand this technique to allow for visualization of the entire complex of Notch, while increasing the ability of this technique to obtain accurate data on molecular dynamics and localization.

026

EXAMINING CHANGES IN TREE SWALLOW (*TACHYGINETA BICOLOR*) GUT MICROBIOME AS A RESULT OF POLLUTION ACROSS SOUTHERN ONTARIOIshaan Bhathal*¹, Isabella Ippolito¹, Kim Fernie², Rebecca Doyle¹, Emily S. Choy¹¹ Department of Biology, McMaster University, Hamilton, Ontario, Canada, L8S 4L8² Canada Centre for Inland Waters, Burlington, Ontario, L7S 1A1

Pollution affects diverse ecosystems and species including gut microbiomes. This complex community which evolves throughout an organism's life is essential for processes such as growth, nutrition and ultimately survival. This study aimed to assess the impact of pollution on the gut microbiome makeup of tree swallows across wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) and non polluted reference sites in southern Ontario. Sampling sites across southern Ontario included polluted locations such as Brantford, Woodard and Dundas WWTPs as well as unpolluted reference sites at McMaster Forest Nature Preserve and Mountsberg Conservation Area. Fecal samples were collected directly from 10 day old nestlings. Microbial diversity was assessed through 16S rRNA gene sequencing. Data was mapped against morphometric measurements, including mass, tarsus length and wing chord to explore potential correlations between nestling condition and gut microbial diversity. While morphometric and phylum-level analyses revealed high variation, the phylum *Chlamydiota* was detected at only one site (Dundas Wastewater Treatment) where it exhibited a higher relative abundance than other phyla. As *Chlamydiota* has been linked to bacterial diseases, its presence in a highly polluted site suggests that pollution may influence gut microbiome composition in a potentially harmful manner

027

CUTICULAR CUES INVOLVED IN LOCUST INFECTION BY THE INSECT SPECIALIST *METARHIZIUM*.Rosa Adams*¹, and Michael Bidochka².¹Department of Biological Sciences, Brock University, St. Catharines Ontario, Canada L2S 3A1

Fungal pathogens have evolved sophisticated ways to infect their hosts, but what makes some fungi capable of attacking a broad range of insects, while others are highly selective? *Metarhizium*, known as an insect-pathogenic fungus, exhibits varying degrees of host specificity. Specialists such as *M. acridum* primarily infect orthopteran hosts like locusts (*Locusta migratoria*), while generalists such as *M. anisopliae* can infect a broad range of insect hosts.

This study investigates the role of locust cuticular lipids in fungal infection, examining how these surface components influence *Metarhizium* specialists' ability to recognize and penetrate host cuticles. Specifically, we ask: What chemical cues in *L. migratoria* cuticular lipids enable selective fungal infections, and can they influence infection in non-host insects? Our results confirm that specialists do not naturally infect non-specialist targets, *Tenebrio molitor* or *Galleria mellonella* larvae, unless injected, reinforcing the importance of the cuticle as a barrier. However, exposure to polar cuticular lipid extracts from *L. migratoria* potentially influenced the ability of specialists to infect non-host insects. In contrast, non-polar lipids did not appear to enhance infection, but further research is needed to clarify their specific contributions.

Understanding these mechanisms could have broader implications for biological pest control and microbial interactions and highlights the need for further exploration of cuticular components in fungal pathogenesis.

028

MUSCLE ADAPTATION TO HIGH ALTITUDE IN THE WORLD'S HIGHEST DWELLING MAMMAL, *PHYLLOTIS VACCARUM*.Robin Brown*¹, Ranim Saleem¹, Graham R. Scott¹¹Department of Biology, McMaster University, Hamilton, Ontario, Canada, L8S 4K1

Surviving at extreme altitudes requires physiological adaptations to combat severe hypoxia (low oxygen) and cold stress. Skeletal muscles, which are essential for both shivering and non-shivering thermogenesis, face significant challenges in these conditions due to their high metabolic cost and reliance on oxygen for energy production. We investigated muscle adaptations in the gastrocnemius, a large hind limb muscle involved in locomotion and shivering, in the Andean leaf-eared mouse (*Phyllotis vaccarum*), which has been documented as the highest-dwelling mammal at ~6,739m above sea level. Specifically, we analyzed capillarity and fiber compositions by sectioning 10 µm slices of preserved gastrocnemius tissue using a cryostat. This was followed by histochemical staining to visualize individual capillaries and oxidative capacity of muscle fibers. These analyses allow us to assess structural modification that may enhance oxygen delivery and utilization in high-altitude populations. Preliminary results indicate no significant differences in capillary density or capillary to fiber ratio between high-altitude populations of *P. vaccarum*, its low-altitude conspecific, and a closely related lowland species *P. darwini*. However, differences in fiber-type composition may still play a role in enhancing physiological performance at high altitudes. Ongoing analyses will further examine fiber compositions (oxidative vs. glycolytic fibers) to determine whether structural muscle adaptations support high-altitude survival. These findings will provide valuable insight into the muscle plasticity and metabolic strategies that support survival in high-altitude environments. Understanding these mechanisms could reveal broader principles of physiological evolution in extreme environments. Supported by NSERC.

029

UPTAKE AND EFFECTS OF MICROPLASTIC FIBER ON FRESHWATER SNAILS

Iman Nemar*, Karen Kidd, Quinn Allamby

Department of Biology, McMaster University, Hamilton, Ontario, Canada L8S 4L8

Microplastics are among the most prevalent contaminants in aquatic water systems. While previous studies have shown that microplastics can cause a decrease in nutrient intake, reproductive output, and survival in some macroinvertebrates, the impacts of mixed microfibers on snails are not fully understood. This study explored how a mixture of polyethylene terephthalate and nylon microfibers affects freshwater snail reproduction and mortality. Accumulation of microplastics in snails was also analyzed to determine if ingested microplastics remained in snails post-exposure. 96 specimens of *Planorbella pilsbryi*, a species of freshwater snail, were exposed over 28 days at control, low (100 parts/L), medium (10,000 parts/L), and high (1,000,000 parts/L) concentrations. Snails were then chemically digested using 10% potassium hydroxide to quantify ingestion of microplastics. A Shapiro-Wilk test assessed for normality and a Kruskal-Wallis test and Dunn's post hoc test were used to find significant differences between treatment groups. Results showed that egg cluster production decreased by 18.4% at medium concentrations, and accumulation of microfibers significantly increased at low and high concentrations by 2.1 and 5.6 times compared to controls. Microplastics exposures did not affect mortality in exposed snails. These findings suggest that freshwater gastropods ingest a significant amount of microplastics, and exposure significantly impacted reproductive success. Ingested microplastics also remained after exposure, suggesting that microplastic retention may have long-term impacts on organisms. This experiment contributes to an improved understanding of the risks microplastics pose to benthic macroinvertebrates like snails, which play a key role in nutrient cycling in aquatic environments.

030

NATIVE INTERTIDAL BIODIVERSITY PLAYS A ROLE IN RESISTING THE ESTABLISHMENT OF THE INVASIVE EUROPEAN GREEN CRAB, *CARCINUS MAENAS*Madelaine Picard*¹, and Timothy Hain¹¹ Department of Biology, University of Western Ontario, London, Ontario, Canada N6A 3K7

Invasive species are among the leading causes of global biodiversity loss. Given the ongoing biodiversity crisis, there has never been such necessity for advancements in our understanding of invasion ecology. Such advancements should emphasize prevention and predicting spread, as it is exceptionally difficult to eradicate invaders once they are established. This challenge is heightened in marine ecosystems. One hypothesis that attempts to explain the factors contributing to an invader's success is the biotic resistance hypothesis which proposes that areas with higher biodiversity are more resistant to invasion. The European Green Crab (*Carcinus maenas*: EGC) has previously established populations worldwide and has done considerable damage to local communities. The EGC has recently invaded northern British Columbia (BC) and poses a threat to many native species of cultural and economic importance. This new population offers a unique opportunity to test the biotic resistance hypothesis because the region is still in the early stages of EGC invasion. I surveyed sites across northern BC and documented the presence of EGC and the native intertidal species richness at those sites. I found that sites with EGC tend to have lower native species richness than sites without EGC. Co-occurrence patterns revealed no species-specific relationships that might impact the EGC's ability to establish. These results provide insight into the ecological mechanisms behind the biotic resistance of invasions. The results can also be used to identify sites most vulnerable to EGC invasion, thereby aiding in their management and protecting native biodiversity.

031

THE EFFECT OF AUTOPHAGY ON CIRCADIAN RHYTHMICITY VIA TARGET OF RAPAMYCIN (TOR) PATHWAY IN *NEUROSPORA CRASSA*

Shahzad Rahmani* and Patricia Lakin-Thomas

York University, Department of Biology, 4700 Keele Street, Toronto, Ontario M3J 1P3, Canada

Circadian rhythms regulate essential biological processes, traditionally understood through transcription-translation feedback loops (TTFLs), but recent studies suggest that metabolic pathways, such as the Target of Rapamycin (TOR) signaling pathway, may also contribute to circadian regulation. TORC1 integrates nutrient availability and cellular energy status, promoting growth while inhibiting autophagy under nutrient-rich conditions, and activating autophagy under starvation to maintain metabolic balance. This study explored the interaction between autophagy and TOR activity in *Neurospora crassa*, hypothesizing that autophagy sustains TOR activation by recycling amino acids. Using the autophagy inhibitors Bafilomycin A1 and MRT68921, we measured TORC1 activity through S6 phosphorylation levels under starvation conditions. Additionally, VTA and GTR2 knockout mutants, key regulators of TOR signaling, were analyzed for their role in this feedback mechanism. Our results indicate that inhibiting autophagy reduces TOR activity, as shown by decreased S6 phosphorylation, supporting the idea that autophagy plays a crucial role in sustaining TOR activation. Furthermore, the effects were dependent on VTA and GTR2, suggesting their involvement in the autophagy-TOR regulatory axis. These findings provide new insights into the role of metabolic oscillators in circadian regulation and highlight a potential conserved mechanism across eukaryotes.

032

A FUNCTIONALLY JAWLESS MUTANT OF THE ZEBRAFISH *DANIO RERIO*Alexandra Weber^{1*}, Tetsuto Miyashita^{2,3}¹Department of Biology, Carleton University, 1125 Colonel By Drive, Ottawa, ON, Canada K1S 5B6²Department of Biology, University of Ottawa, 30 Marie-Curie Private, Ottawa, Ontario, Canada K1N 9A7³Beaty Centre for Species Discovery, Canadian Museum of Nature, P.O. Box 3443, Station D, Ottawa, Ontario, Canada K1P 6P4

Zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) are a widely used model organism in molecular genetics and developmental biology. However, both normal and abnormal zebrafish anatomy have been poorly documented, and most phenotypes are only followed to the larval phase. We describe normal and abnormal skull anatomy of zebrafish at the adult phase to: a) provide a resource for late development phenotype analysis; and b) understand the morphological changes that occur in a mutant line with a drastic adult phenotype. We compare wildtype and *nkx3.2*^{-/-} mutant zebrafish, which are functionally jawless (upper and lower jaw fused together). To do this, we developed μ CT-based 3D anatomical atlases for both lines. This allowed for direct visual comparison of the two skulls in each individual element. The most striking changes occur in the mandibular arch, particularly in the palatoquadrate. These changes include the fusion of the dentary, the functional separation of the maxilla and premaxilla from the dentary, and the hyperossified jaw joint. These phenotypes arise through plastic remodeling and facilitate bizarre skull morphology that mimics some extinct jawless vertebrates. Using these models, we will next reconstruct skull kinematics in the *nkx3.2*^{-/-} mutant zebrafish in 3D.

033

CYCLOHEXIMIDE MODULATES TARGET OF RAPAMYCIN PATHWAY ACTIVATION IN *NEUROSPORA CRASSA*Amiel Terrenal*¹, Patricia Lakin-Thomas²¹Department of Chemistry, York University, Toronto, Ontario, Canada M3J 1P3²Department of Biology, York University, Toronto, Ontario, Canada M3J 1P3

We are studying circadian rhythms, the 24-hour clocks that are present in most eukaryotes and some prokaryotes. The clock protein frequency (FRQ) is important in maintaining circadian rhythms in the fungus *Neurospora crassa*. However, rhythmicity persists in FRQ-less strains. Existing evidence in our laboratory suggests that the Target of Rapamycin (TOR) pathway may function as a circadian oscillator in FRQ-less strains. The protein synthesis inhibitor cycloheximide (CHX), affects the phase of the circadian rhythms in *Neurospora*. Interestingly, the TOR pathway can be activated by CHX, although, the mechanism is not fully understood. Therefore, this work aims to test the hypothesis that CHX-mediated TOR activation occurs through regulation by amino acids. Mutant strains that block amino acid signalling to TOR will be used. The phosphorylation states of S6, a protein in the TOR pathway, will be determined using Western blot analysis to assay for TOR activation. Feedback regulation of TOR by protein synthesis and amino acid pools might contribute to the mechanism of a TOR-based oscillator. This work will help us understand TOR regulation and its role in circadian rhythms.

034

DEVELOPMENT OF SEX-SPECIFIC PLASMA-LIKE CELL CULTURE MEDIADeandra Dixon*¹, Jacob Wiebe¹, Ricardo Alva¹, Jeffrey A. Stuart¹¹ Department of Biological Sciences, Brock University, St. Catharines, Ontario, Canada L2S 3A1

Cell culture is widely used to study cells under conditions in which cellular activities can be visualized and measured. Cell culturists have historically aimed to provide their cells with an excess of nutrients to ensure their continued viability and growth. However, this is now understood to affect most cellular functions, including gene expression, metabolism, and growth rates. Recently, Physiological media like Plasmix have been developed and cells cultured in these media have been shown to react differently than in traditional media. Physiological media have been formulated with a population average in mind and do not consider sex, which is not consistent with the Tri-agencies policies to consider sex as a biological variable. My thesis aimed to address this deficiency by developing masculinized and feminized cell culture media, that could be used with cells from male and female donors, respectively. I collected male and female data for 47 human plasma metabolites, from 19 papers and the Human Metabolome Database. The data were from healthy human subjects between the ages of 20-50 years old. I found that concentrations of 21 plasma metabolites were significantly different between males and females ($P < 0.05$). I then formulated a male plasma-like medium (MPLM) and a female plasma-like medium (FPLM). Cells will be cultured in these media and supplemented with male or female human serum to create a full cell culture environment. RNA will be extracted and subjected to RNAseq and gene set enrichment analysis to evaluate the effects of the same cells growing in these different media.

035

ACUTE OXYGEN-DEPENDENT EPIGENETIC REGULATION IN RAINBOW TROUT LIVER: IS H3K4ME3 LINKED TO INDUCED METABOLIC GENES?

Sally Adil*, William Johnston, and Dr. Jan Mennigen

Department of Biology, University of Ottawa, Ottawa, Ontario, Canada K1N 6N5

Environmental hypoxia in freshwater systems is increasing, even more so with climate change. Among freshwater fishes, some are relatively more tolerant to hypoxia, like the goldfish (*Carassius auratus*); others, such as the rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*), are intolerant. Physiological responses to acute hypoxia exposure vary, among them is metabolic plasticity. At least in part, metabolic plasticity is mediated via transcriptional changes in rate-limiting enzymes of metabolic pathways involved in glucose and lipid metabolism. Transcriptional responses are well-known to be mediated via the Hypoxia-Inducible Factor oxygen sensor system. Recent *in vitro* evidence revealed that oxygen-dependant epigenetic machinery may also be involved in direct regulation of transcripts. Here, we probe whether the activating histone modification, H3K4me3, enhanced in hypoxic condition *in vitro*, is linked to metabolic transcript induction by acute 4h hypoxia exposure (50% and 25% O₂ saturation) in the trout liver. Contrary to prediction, results show 25% O₂ saturation induced transcripts involved in gluconeogenesis (*pck1*) and fatty acid synthesis (*fasn*) exhibit a decrease in H3K4me3 modification in the upstream putative promoter region. These observations suggest that under the experimental conditions tested, other O₂ dependent (epigenetic) molecular mechanisms are involved in the induction of these enzymes. Additional studies looking at different hypoxia regimes and O₂ sensitive epigenetic markers are warranted to further address the role of epigenetic regulation on metabolic pathways in hypoxia response in fish.

036

EXAMINING THE CAUSE AND PATTERNS OF ULTRAVIOLET-INDUCED FLUORESCENCE IN NORTHERN (*GLAUCOMYS SABRINUS*) AND SOUTHERN FLYING SQUIRRELS (*G. VOLANS*) IN ONTARIO, CANADALucy van Haften*¹ and Jeff Bowman²¹Department of Biology, Trent University, Peterborough, Ontario, Canada K9L 0G2²Wildlife Research and Monitoring Section, Ontario Ministry of Natural Resources, Peterborough, Ontario, Canada K9L 1Z8

Many animals across several taxa exhibit ultraviolet-induced fluorescence. The pelage of all New World flying squirrels (*Glaucomys* spp.) fluoresces under ultraviolet light, with some variability among individuals. The hypothesized fluorophores responsible are porphyrins – photodegradable compounds produced during the heme production pathway. To further test the porphyrin hypothesis and assess and characterize the variation in flying squirrel fluorescence, I photographed northern flying squirrels (*G. sabrinus*) and southern flying squirrels (*G. volans*) under ultraviolet light at an established field site in Central Ontario. To determine what intrinsic and extrinsic variables might be related to inter- and intraindividual differences in fluorescence, I categorized each set of photos (n = 265) based on whether they showed any of the standard fluorescence patterns I defined. I then performed general linear mixed effects models to determine which variables (species, sex, age, date) predict the presence of each pattern. If porphyrins are responsible, I would expect fluorescence to change around moulting time and be different in juveniles vs. adults due to differing amounts of light exposure to the pelage. I found that nearly all fluorescence patterns were predicted by date, and some were additionally predicted by sex or age. These temporal and age- and sex-based differences could suggest some ecological importance of fluorescence or could simply reflect the photodegradable nature of porphyrins. Future work is needed to assess whether these fluorescence patterns hold ecological importance for species in this genus.

037

AMPK: A Key Player in Combating Skeletal Muscle Fibrosis in Cancer CachexiaAmber S Austin^{1*}, Magda Lesinski¹, Andrew I Mikhail¹, Saumyaa Rishi¹, Rozhin Raziee¹, Irena A Rebalka², Luca J Delfinis³, Christopher GR Perry³, Thomas J Hawke², Vladimir Ljubcic¹¹Department of Kinesiology, McMaster University, Hamilton ON, Canada²Department of Pathology and Molecular Medicine, McMaster University, Hamilton ON, Canada³School of Kinesiology & Health Science, Muscle Health Research Centre, York University, Toronto ON, Canada

Introduction: Cancer cachexia affects 50-80% of cancer patients, causing severe muscle loss, systemic inflammation, and metabolic dysregulation, which significantly reduces patient survival and quality of life. AMP-activated protein kinase (AMPK) is an energy sensing enzyme that regulates various signaling pathways that ultimately influence skeletal muscle morphology and function. Disruptions in AMPK signaling have been documented in cachectic patients suggesting a role for this kinase in maintaining skeletal muscle mass. **Methods:** To study the role of AMPK in this atrophic model, cancer cachexia was induced in 11-week old mice with a subcutaneous injection of 1 million Lewis Lung carcinoma (LLC) cells, with healthy controls treated with PBS. 1 week post-tumour inoculation, LLC mice began daily oral administration of the AMPK activator MK-8722 (LLC^{MK}) or a vehicle (LLC^{Veh}). Mice were sacrificed 4 weeks post-tumour inoculation and the extensor digitorum longus (EDL), quadriceps and blood serum were collected. Skeletal muscle fibrosis was analyzed using Picrosirius Red staining. **Results:** The LLC^{Veh} group had a significantly greater percentage of collagen deposition within the EDL, compared to the control ($p < 0.05$), while MK treatment decreased fibrosis to healthy levels. Serum from LLC^{MK} mice exhibited a significant increase in C-C motif chemokine ligand 2 (CCL2) concentration ($p < 0.05$) compared to the control while skeletal-muscle derived tumor necrosis factor alpha (TNF- α) mRNA was increased in the LLC^{MK} group compared to LLC^{Veh} ($p < 0.05$). **Conclusion:** This study provides evidence that pharmacological AMPK activation can mitigate skeletal muscle fibrosis in cachectic mice despite concurrent increases in systemic and local cancer-related inflammatory markers.

038

A PILOT INTRODUCED-PLANT-FOCUSED CITIZEN PROJECT IN CHURCHILL, MANITOBATsz Ying (Ruby) Yip^{*1}¹BIO399 3rd Year Undergraduate Student, Department of Biology, University of Toronto, Mississauga, Ontario, Canada, L5L 1C6

Plant invasions currently are scarce at high latitudes, likely as a result of low temperatures and short growing seasons, but this may change as the climate warms: temperatures are increasing at up to 4 times the global average in arctic regions. For instance, more than 100 introduced plants already have been recorded in Churchill, Manitoba (58.5° N), an exception to the rarity of introductions in tundra and treeline habitats. Most of these plants have not persisted, but an unknown number of species have established long-term populations. I have been investigating the feasibility of launching a citizen science project on plant invasions in Churchill, in order to allow cost-effective, long-term collection of data on species occurrence and persistence. Introduced plant observations from iNaturalist, although low in number, have helped to identify observation and invasion hotspots. A literature review and investigation of established citizen science projects suggest that the feasibility of launching an introduced-plant-focused citizen science project is low to moderate, mostly due to the low number (870) of residents in Churchill. Nevertheless, I have designed a trial introduced-plant-focused citizen science project for Churchill, "Ecology IN You", including an online training phase and a data collection phase. "Ecology IN You" is expected to be further refined in the summer of 2025, and if successful, could be useful in tracking populations of invasive species. Educational materials on introduced plant are also being developed to help recruit volunteers, and to provide information on non-native species to the local community.

039

EVALUATING THE ACCURACY OF VEGETATIVE INDICES IN TRACKING DROUGHT INDUCED PIGMENT CHANGES IN CONIFERSMaria Proskurina*¹, Anchalya Balasubramanian^{1,2}, Olivia Di Biase^{1,2}, Ingo Ensminger^{1,2,3}¹ Department of Biology, University of Toronto Mississauga, Mississauga, Ontario, Canada, L5L 1C6² Department of Cell and Systems Biology, University of Toronto, Toronto, Ontario, Canada, M5S 3G5³ Department of Ecology and Evolutionary Biology, University of Toronto, Toronto, Ontario, Canada, M5S 3B2

Extreme drought is expected to increase in severity with climate change, posing a serious threat to boreal forest health. Spectral reflectance has streamlined vegetation health assessment by enabling the rapid assessment of plant physiological traits, such as photosynthetic efficiency and water stress. This study aims to evaluate the sensitivity and accuracy of different vegetative indices for detecting drought stress in two abundant Canadian conifer species, *Picea glauca* and *Pinus strobus*. Specifically, we assessed the ability of frequently used indices, including the normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI), the photochemical reflectance index (PRI), and the chlorophyll/carotenoid index (CCI), to detect drought-induced pigment changes. Additionally, we determined the relationship between leaf- and canopy-level measurements, and explored additional indices that may serve as effective drought stress indicators. In response to drought stress, chlorophyll pool sizes were reduced, while photoprotective carotenoid pigments were accumulated. Additionally, the shift towards photoprotection was observed through the increased de-epoxidation of violaxanthin into zeaxanthin through the xanthophyll cycle. The strong correlations between pigment changes and PRI and CCI suggest that these indices are very effective in drought stress detection. Additionally, the strong correlation between leaf- and canopy-level measurements suggests that canopy-level data can effectively represent leaf-level physiological changes. These findings highlight the potential applications of spectral reflectance for forest health monitoring and management in a changing climate.

040

EFFECTS OF TLR4 INDIVIDUAL GENETIC DIVERSITY ON MATE CHOICE AND SURVIVORSHIP IN SONG SPARROWS (*MELOSPIZA MELODIA*)Christina Bethune*¹, and Elizabeth MacDougall-Shackleton¹¹Department of Biology, University of Western Ontario, London, Ontario, Canada N6A 3K7

The ability of natural populations to defend themselves against infectious diseases depends on immune gene genetic diversity. Toll-like receptors (TLRs) play key roles in recognizing pathogens and initiating innate immune responses. In song sparrows (*Melospiza melodia*), although no strong link has been found between individual genetic diversity at Toll-like receptor 3 (TLR3) and apparent survivorship, mating is non-random with respect to TLR3 genotype, indicating that TLR genotypes may influence mate choice. Toll-like receptor 4 (TLR4) recognises lipopolysaccharides, which are common in major avian pathogens. Despite TLR4's importance, little is known about how genetic diversity at this locus affects fitness or whether individuals mate non-randomly with respect to TLR4 genotype. To explore this, I tested how individual genetic diversity at TLR4 affects apparent annual survivorship and social mate choice in song sparrows. Through PCR amplification and Sanger sequencing of the extracellular domain of TLR4, I characterized individual genetic diversity. Using Program MARK, I assessed whether increased TLR4 genetic diversity leads to increased apparent survivorship (inferred from annual encounter histories), potentially due to a greater ability for pathogen recognition. Then, to assess whether mate choice is non-random with respect to TLR4 genotype, I calculated and compared pairwise TLR4 genetic distance (UniFrac) between socially mated pairs to all possible pairings to determine if song sparrows are mating disassortatively at TLR4. Results will be discussed. This research will shed light on the extent to which natural and sexual selection maintain genetic diversity at this innate immune gene.

041

BACTERIAL TRANSLOCATION AND IMMUNE CELL INTERACTIONS IN A MOUSE RESTRAINT STRESS MODELAhmed Khalil¹, Chiko Shimbori¹, Jun Lu¹, Fernando Vicentini¹, Emma Giordano¹, Seven Denha², Siegfried Hapfelmeier³, Giada de Palma¹, Stephen M. Collins¹, Premysl Bercik¹¹ Farncombe Family Digestive Health Research Institute, Department of Medicine, McMaster University, Hamilton, ON, Canada² McMaster Immunology Research Center, Department of Medicine, McMaster University, Hamilton, ON, Canada³ Institute for Infectious Diseases, University of Bern, Switzerland

Bacterial translocation is defined as the migration of bacteria or bacterial fragments from the gut to extraintestinal organs. This process has been implicated in the pathophysiology of gastrointestinal disorders, including irritable bowel syndrome (IBS). Experimental stress models reproduce some features of IBS, showing that gut bacteria can translocate into distal organs. However, the mechanism and impact of bacterial translocation remain unclear. To investigate bacterial translocation in a mouse restraint stress model, focusing on immune interactions in the intestine. SPF C57BL/6 mice were assigned to either the restraint stress group or the non-stress control group. Each group was further divided into two subgroups: one receiving a vehicle and the other inoculated with auxotrophic *Salmonella enterica* serovar *typhimurium* HA630 via oral gavage three times per week during the stress period (n=6-14 per group). We collected jejunum, colon, myenteric lymph node, liver, and spleen samples for histology and performed iterative bleaching extends multiplexity (IBEX) staining and fluorescence in situ hybridization (FISH). We also sampled blood, liver, spleen, and brain for bacterial cultures under aseptic conditions. Our culture and histology data showed that transient colonizer *Salmonella typhimurium* enhanced stress-induced bacterial translocation. IBEX and FISH staining demonstrated that intestinal bacteria invaded the intestinal mucosa and co-localized with goblet cells in the intestines. Further, in the stress + *Salmonella* group, some bacteria were found were in close proximity with CD103⁺ cells and neurons. This study provides mechanistic insight into stress-related disorders and offers new perspectives on the role of the gut microbiota in neuroimmune regulations.

042

INVESTIGATING THE ROLE OF ARPC4 IN HUMAN NEURODEVELOPMENTAL DISORDERSGuoria Sun^{*1}, Navroop K Dhaliwal³, Yun Li^{2,3}¹Department of Biology, University of Toronto Mississauga, Mississauga, ON²Department of Molecular Genetics, University of Toronto, Toronto, ON³Developmental and Stem Cell Biology, The Hospital for Sick Children, Toronto, ON

Mutations in the ARPC4 gene, which encodes a critical structural scaffold for the Actin-Related Protein 2/3 (ARP2/3) complex, have been implicated in neurodevelopmental disorders characterized by microcephaly and speech impairments. The ARP2/3 complex plays an essential role in creating branched actin networks that facilitate cellular movement, vesicle trafficking, and organelle remodeling. Recent clinical findings have identified a *de novo* p.Arg158Cys mutation in ARPC4 as pathogenic, affecting seven individuals who present with severe motor delays, speech impairments, and primary microcephaly. This study aims to further characterize the functional role of ARPC4 in neuronal development through in vitro analysis of neuronal morphology and electrophysiology. We hypothesize that ARPC4 deletions will disrupt the actin cytoskeleton, resulting in reduced neuron size, impaired dendritic outgrowth, and inappropriate synaptic activity. Our research will employ three main approaches: (1) generation of induced pluripotent stem cell (iPSC) lines with ARPC4 deletions, (2) morphological analysis using 2D assays, and (3) development of organoids from clonal ARPC4 mutant human pluripotent stem cells (hPSCs). By comparing these genetically modified cultures with wild-type controls, we aim to elucidate the significance of ARPC4 in neurodevelopment and identify potential therapeutic targets to rescue abnormalities associated with ARPC4 dysfunction or related pathways.

043

IDENTIFICATION OF MONOAMINERGIC AND CHOLINERGIC PATHWAYS IN CUTANEOUS SENSORY CELLS OF DEVELOPING ZEBRAFISH.

Willamina MacDonald*, Michael Jonz

Department of Biology, University of Ottawa, Ottawa, Ontario, Canada K1N 6N5

Many physiological mechanisms are still undescribed in sensory systems of developing vertebrates. Such pathways are essential to our understanding of these species, and the methods by which they sense their environment to maintain homeostasis. One vertebrate of particular relevance to scientific research is *Danio rerio* (zebrafish) as they are commonly used as a model organism. Three important sensory cell types present in the skin of developing zebrafish are neuroepithelial cells (NECs), mitochondrion-rich cells (MRCs) and neuromast cells (NMs). NECs are implicated in sensing and responding to hypoxia, MRCs are important in the maintenance of osmotic homeostasis, and NMs are important for sensing the flow of water to detect predators and prey. Each of these cell types is innervated. Therefore, an important first step in understanding the physiological mechanisms that underlie the function of these cells is the identification of neurotransmitters at their afferent or efferent synapses. Using whole-mount immunohistochemistry, monoaminergic and catecholaminergic pathways were identified in zebrafish between 3- and 7-days post fertilization. Antibodies raised against neurotransmitters and the proteins involved in their synthesis, release, and uptake were assayed. The experiments revealed a novel cholinergic signaling pathway in cutaneous NECs, a novel catecholaminergic pathway in MRCs, and characterized, for the first time, a dopaminergic receptor (the D2 receptor) in NMs. The results not only enhance our understanding of physiology in developing zebrafish but further inform existing applications and give insight into novel uses for zebrafish as a model organism.

044

AGE-ASSOCIATED SKELETAL MUSCLE LOSS IS MITIGATED WITH CHRONIC AMPK ACTIVATIONAnneliese Schall*¹, Andrew I Mikhail¹, Sean Y Ng¹, Stephanie R Mattina¹, Magda A Lesinski¹, Vladimir Ljubcic¹¹ Department of Kinesiology, McMaster University, Hamilton, Ontario, Canada L8S 4L8

Background: Age associated skeletal muscle loss predominantly impacting glycolytic muscle fibers, can result in an increased risk of hospitalization, loss of independence and all-cause mortality. Glycolytic muscle fibers enable quick movements, essential for daily activities. Reduced AMP-activated protein kinase (AMPK), an enzyme supporting muscle homeostasis, may contribute to increased deterioration of muscle fibers with aging. Thus, the purpose of this study is to determine whether chronic AMPK activation can mitigate the age-related loss of muscle mass and cross-sectional area (CSA) in aged mice. **Methods:** Old (~18 months) wild-type C57BL/6J mice, were randomly assigned to receive either 10mg/kg of the small molecule AMPK activator MK8722 (Old-MK) or a vehicle (Old-Veh). Both groups received their respective doses every other day via oral gavage for a duration of 6 months. Young 3-month-old mice were used as a control. The gastrocnemius (GAST) was then extracted, weighed and stained to investigate muscle fiber CSA. **Results:** Muscle mass of the GAST was significantly greater in MK8722 treated animals as compared to Old-Veh mice. Furthermore, we demonstrated a significant decrease in CSA and minimum feret diameter in the glycolytic regions of GAST muscle from Old-Veh mice relative to young mice, which was not observed in treated animals. Observations were due to a rightward shift in the fiber size distribution of Old-MK mice relative to Old-Veh. Oxidative fibers showed no significant difference across all groups. **Conclusion:** Direct AMPK activation via MK8722 may play a protective role in age-related muscle deterioration primarily through the preservation of glycolytic fiber size.

045

TAKING THE PERMAFROST'S PULSE: PLANT COMMUNITY RESPONSE TO PERMAFROST THAW.Alyssa Tinella*¹, Victoria Robertson¹, Evan Kane², Merritt Turetsky³, Catherine Dieleman¹¹Department of Environmental Sciences, University of Guelph, Guelph, Ontario, Canada²School of Forest Resources and Environmental Science, Michigan Technological University, Houghton, Michigan, US³Institute of Arctic and Alpine Research, University of Colorado Boulder, Boulder, Colorado, US

With rapid surface warming, permafrost soils are thawing and releasing vast stores of resources previously sequestered in the frozen ground. Permafrost contains twice as much carbon as the atmosphere, and as it thaws, this carbon and associated nitrogen become biologically available, allowing microbial activity to convert them into greenhouse gases. This release amplifies climate change through a conversion from a carbon sink to a carbon source. Past studies have investigated how this newly available nitrogen will impact vegetation of upland systems, but not yet for a lowland system. This study investigates the impacts of a simulated permafrost resource pulse on plant community structure, biomass, plant available nutrients, and foliar C:N in a nitrogen-limited Alaskan lowland system. The study was conducted in a bog near Fairbanks, Alaska, to examine how nutrient additions at two different soil depths and two different times influence plant response in permafrost plateau and active thaw margin areas. The effects of increased nitrogen availability will be assessed using a combination of vegetation surveys, foliar chemistry analysis, and plant root simulator probes. This study is critical for understanding how resource pulses from permafrost thaw influence permafrost peatlands and to provide insights for predicting global climate change processes through permafrost thaw effects.

046

HOW DO SMALL HABITAT PATCHES SUPPORT HIGHER BIODIVERSITY FOR AN EQUIVALENT HABITAT AREA?

Erin Ricaloglu* and Dr. Jurek Kolasa

Department of Biology, McMaster University, Hamilton, ON, Canada.

Habitat fragmentation is widely recognized as a threat to biodiversity, yet some studies suggest that small habitat patches can support higher species diversity than larger ones. This study explores the mechanisms behind this phenomenon, focusing on spatial turnover (species replacement between patches) and species sorting with local stability (specialists establishing stable populations in small patches). Using a metacommunity model, we simulated landscapes of 25, 81, and 289 patches, maintaining constant ecological parameters such as species reproduction, movement, and habitat suitability. Each scenario was replicated 30 times over 250 generations, tracking species richness (S), total abundance (N), and turnover rates. Results showed small patches supported nearly twice the species richness of large patches. However, turnover increased over time in large patches, indicating species loss, while small patches maintained stable turnover, suggesting compositional stability. Specialist turnover declined faster than generalists, reinforcing their stability in small patches. Habitat suitability influenced richness differently by patch size: generalist richness increased with suitability in large patches, while specialist richness followed a unimodal pattern. In contrast, small patches showed no clear generalist trend but a unimodal specialist response. These findings indicate that species sorting, rather than high spatial turnover, drives biodiversity in small patches. Small patches act as ecological filters, favoring specialists and stabilizing biodiversity. This challenges the assumption that large, continuous habitats are always superior and highlights the conservation value of small, well-connected patches in fragmented landscapes.

047

CAUGHT IN THE ACT: ASSESSING LURE TYPE EFFECTS ON JAPANESE BEETLE (POPILLIA JAPONICA) TRAP CAPTUREKiersten DeViller*^{1,2}, Jeffrey Pepin², Robin Eriksson¹, Quentin Guignard³, Jeremy D Allison³, Erin O Campbell²¹Department of Biology, Carleton University, Ottawa, Ontario K1S 5B6, Canada²Canadian Food Inspection Agency, Ottawa Plant Laboratory, Entomology, Ottawa, Ontario, Canada³Natural Resources Canada, Canadian Forest Service, Great Lakes Forestry Centre, Sault Ste. Marie, Ontario, Canada

Japanese beetle (*Popillia japonica*) is an invasive pest of over 300 host plant species, including ornamental trees and shrubs, nursery plants, and agricultural crops. Recent establishment of Japanese beetle in British Columbia demands an urgent and robust response to prevent its spread. Efficient biosurveillance methods and a thorough understanding of Japanese beetle's biology and behaviour are important for continued management and monitoring of the species. Kairomone and pheromone dual lures are commonly used in Japanese beetle traps and have been shown to result in effective capture, however, little is known about the influence of lure type on the sex distribution and magnitude of trap capture, especially when considering potential phenological patterns. To explore this relationship, we examined catch rate and sex ratio in Japanese beetle traps baited with kairomone, pheromone, and dual lures during the adult activity period (July-August). Our results suggest that lure type influences trap catch rate as well as the sex ratio of the trap capture. Additionally, these effects appear to be connected to phenological patterns in Japanese beetle sex distribution within the population and may provide evidence for early male emergence.

048

REFINING CELL CULTURE TEST METHODS FOR ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTIONLogan Dammer*¹, Stephanie DeWitte-Orr^{1,2} and Jim McGeer¹.¹Biology, Wilfred Laurier University, Waterloo, Ontario, Canada, N2L 3C5. ²Health Science, Wilfred Laurier University, Waterloo, Ontario, Canada, N2L 3C5.

The 2023 revisions to the Canadian Environmental Protection Act (CEPA) have led to commitments to eliminate vertebrate testing. This will pose challenges for Environment and Climate Change Canada seeing as environmental quality guidelines depend on toxicity tests of vertebrates (e.g fish). Alternative methods are the answer to overcoming these challenges. By observing the responses of cultured cells exposed to copper concentrations we can uncover obstacles and work towards solutions. Cell cultures were used as an alternative method to observe the effects of copper and its free ion forms. Cells from the cell line RTG-2 (rainbow trout gonad) were exposed to high and low ranges of copper on a 96-well plate, to effectively measuring the cell viability. Different geochemical variables will be employed to observe the bioavailability of metal ions and corresponding cellular effects. Using simulation programs and free ion electrodes, the free ion concentrations under different environmental conditions will be measured. The cell viability assays showed the toxicity of copper to not be considerably strong when below 160 mg/L. The simulator showed numerous non-toxic products formed from the complexations of copper with components in the growth media, which reduce cytotoxic effects. Regulations in Europe like registration, evaluation, authorization and restriction of chemicals (REACH) drive the reduction in animal use around the world. This research aims to provide reliable metal toxicity data that can be used as an alternative to vertebrate testing for water quality guidelines in Canada. Research supported by NSERC and Environment and Climate Change Canada.

049

THE ROLE OF MALE BODY SIZE AND EYE COLOUR IN MEDIATING FEMALE REPRODUCTIVE DYNAMICS IN *Drosophila melanogaster*.

Avneet Kahlon*, Dr. Tristan Long

Department of Biology, Wilfrid Laurier University, Waterloo, Ontario, Canada N2L 3C5

In *Drosophila melanogaster*, like many species, selection on individual fitness often results in conflicting reproductive tactics in males and females. While both sexes benefit from reproductive success, their optimal mating strategies conflict, resulting in intersexual conflict. This conflict arises because males aim to mate as frequently as possible to maximize reproductive output, whereas females benefit from fewer matings to conserve energy for offspring production and feeding. These conflicting reproductive interests drive costly behaviours. One prominent manifestation of sexual conflict in *D. melanogaster* is male harassment, where persistent courtship and repeated mating attempts disrupt female behaviours and negatively affect offspring production. While the effects of sexual conflict are well-known, there is variation in its expression, potentially due to male characteristics. We investigated two male traits important to harassment dynamics: body size (large males may harass more than small males) and eye colour (being able to locate females more easily may increase harassment). In our first assay, we studied the effect of male eye colour on mate tracking, courting, and harassment. The second assay focused on how male body size influenced harassment intensity and female reproductive success. Surprisingly, female flies housed with males visited food patches more frequently and produced more offspring than those kept alone. This increase was not due to remating or the fecundity boost from accessory proteins (Acps) but likely a social signal associated with male presence. These findings suggest male presence influences female reproductive outcomes through social cues and that sexual conflict dynamics have unexpected dimensions.

050

IMPACT OF CHRONIC SUBLETHAL NEODYMIUM EXPOSURE ON FATHEAD MINNOWS AND ARCTIC CHARR.R. Kaur*¹, A. Thompson¹, E. Leonard¹, D. S.Smith² and J. McGeer¹¹Biology and ²Biochemistry and Chemistry Department, Wilfrid Laurier University, Waterloo, ON, Canada, N2L 3C5

The increasing prevalence of Neodymium (Nd), a rare earth element, in aquatic ecosystems due to industrial runoff necessitates an understanding of its chronic effects on freshwater organisms. This study investigates Nd bioaccumulation in Fathead minnows (*Pimephales promelas*) both adults and juveniles, and Arctic char (*Salvelinus alpinus*) alevins under controlled laboratory conditions. Adult minnows were exposed to sublethal Nd concentrations (100, 200, and 400 µg/L) for 96h in a flowthrough system, maintaining water parameters (80–100 µs/cm, 10–40 mg/L hardness, pH 7.2, and 19–21°C) to reflect natural conditions. Tissue samples from gills, liver, kidney and muscle were analyzed for Nd accumulation. Juvenile minnows were exposed to either 50 and 100 µg/L Nd for 72h under similar conditions, with whole-body samples collected for analysis. Arctic char alevins underwent a 3-week exposure of 7 Nd concentrations (10–640 µg/L) in soft water (200–205 µs/cm, 80–95 mg/L hardness, pH 6.9–7.5, and 7°C), and whole-body samples were examined for bioaccumulation. Findings from this study provides crucial insight into the extent of Nd accumulation across different life stages and species, highlighting potential ecological consequences. By identifying Nd bioaccumulation patterns, this research informs environmental risk assessments and supports the need for regulatory measures for environmental protection. This work is funded by NSERC & Environment and Climate Change Canada with contributions from Stantec and Vital Metals.

051

THE EFFECTS OF VENLAFAXINE AND HYPOXIA ON RAINBOW TROUTM. Khalid^{1*}, Olena Kuntjy¹, Andrew Thompson¹, Natalie M. Nykamp¹, Erin Leonard¹¹Department of Biology, Wilfrid Laurier University¹

Antidepressant prescription rates are increasing, leading to their excretion in a neuroactive form that often bypasses wastewater treatment plants and contaminates surface waters. Within these aquatic environments, multiple stressors exist, including low oxygen levels (hypoxia) resulting from anthropogenic activities like agricultural runoff. Fish detect changes in oxygen using gill neuroepithelial cells (NECs), which use serotonin to engage coping mechanisms. Fish have developed behavioral adaptations like increased opercular movement and aquatic surface respiration to cope with hypoxia. Considering that venlafaxine, a widely prescribed antidepressant, works by inhibiting the reuptake of serotonin and norepinephrine, how might hypoxia tolerance be affected when exposed to venlafaxine? This study investigated venlafaxine's potential impact on oxygen sensing in juvenile rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*). We exposed fish to control, two environmentally relevant concentrations of venlafaxine (0.1 and 1 µg/L), or a higher concentration of 10 µg/L for 24 hours in 12L tanks. Fish were placed into a flow-through system to gradually reduce oxygen levels to 10% dissolved oxygen until loss of equilibrium (LOE) occurred. LOE is often measured to determine hypoxia tolerance. Behavioural metrics such as distance travelled, velocity, acceleration, and time to LOE were quantified using EthoVisionXT video tracking software. Blood glucose levels were collected to measure energy mobilization. Behavioural metrics were not significant among treatments; however, blood glucose levels were significantly lower in the 1 and 10 µg/L treatments compared to the control. This suggests that high concentrations of venlafaxine act as a potential beta-blocker during severe hypoxia and may impair energy mobilization.

052

SEEDS OF CHANGE: IMPACTS OF PERMAFROST DISTURBANCE ON TUNDRA SHRUB REPRODUCTION

Spenser Morouney*, Jennifer Baltzer

Wilfrid Laurier University, Ontario, Canada N2L 3C5

As permafrost thaw in the Canadian tundra accelerates with rapid climate warming, permafrost disturbances are becoming common on the landscape. Thaw slumps and polygonal terrain have both been shown to play a significant role in facilitating vegetation change, especially in the proliferation of tall shrub populations. This shift towards tall shrub tundra landscapes is happening across global arctic environments. Reproduction is a significant driver of change in these systems as it drives dispersal and establishment. Permafrost disturbances provide favorable conditions for shrub establishment with the exposure of open ground, warm conditions, and thicker active layers. This study focuses on the reproductive traits of two common species, green alder (*Alnus alnobetula*) and dwarf birch (*Betula glandulosa*). Their establishment and reproductive success were evaluated at 7 polygonal terrain and 6 thaw slump sites and compared to adjacent undisturbed tundra near Inuvik, NWT. Through in-field surveys of cone presence and juvenile recruitment along with an in-lab viability study on their seeds, their reproductive traits have been quantified. Shrubs within disturbances were more likely to produce cones and their seed exhibited increased germination rates, indicating a positive impact of disturbance on reproductive output. However, the number of juveniles present in control plots was generally higher than within disturbance, indicating growth in disturbance is not positively influencing establishment. As permafrost disturbances become more prevalent on the landscape, the plant communities established within them will shape future arctic ecosystem feedback to global climate systems and ultimately tundra biodiversity as a whole.

053

WAVELENGTHS OF INFLUENCE: BLUE LIGHT AND ITS ROLE IN MEMORY AND MATE-CHOICE IN FRUIT FLIESMaryem Naimee*¹, Tristan Long²¹Department of Biology, Wilfrid Laurier University, Waterloo, Ontario, Canada, N2L 3C5

The capacity for learning and memory is crucial for success across species, making it important to study factors that influence these abilities. Recent research suggests blue light negatively impacts physiological and neurological functions, potentially affecting learning and memory. To investigate this, we examined whether blue light had neurodegenerative effects using fruit flies (*Drosophila melanogaster*), a well-established model for studying cognition and aging. In two experiments, virgin female fruit flies were exposed to blue, red, or white light on a 12-hour cycle for three weeks. The first experiment tested their ability to associate an unpleasant taste (quinine) with a visual cue (striped or zig-zag pattern). Learning was generally poor across treatments, but flies associated the negative cue more effectively with the zig-zag pattern than with the striped one. The second experiment examined mate-choice copying by measuring how frequently females selected males with a phenotypic marker (green or pink dust), potentially indicating reproductive quality. A trend toward mate-choice copying emerged in white-light-exposed flies, but no learning was observed in blue- or red-exposed groups. White-exposed flies also behaved differently toward males with cues signaling reproductive success. Overall, these findings suggest that blue light may impair learning in some contexts but have no measurable effect in others, highlighting the complexity of its impact on cognition and pointing to intriguing directions for future research.

054

THE ROLE OF CLAUDIN-14 IN MEDIATING THE PROTECTIVE EFFECTS OF WATER CALCIUM HARDNESS IN FISH EXPOSED TO HIGH PH WATER.Najiba Soudi*¹, Patrícia Ferreira², Jonathan.M. Wilson¹.¹Department of biology, Wilfred Laurier University, Waterloo, Ontario, Canada N2L 3C5²Department of biology, University of Ottawa, Ottawa, Ontario, Canada K1N 9A4

Many fish struggle to survive in high-pH water because of ion regulation disturbance, increased ion loss and, impaired ammonia excretion which led to physiological stress. Some study has indicated calcium ions mitigate some of these effects however, the exact molecular mechanism remains unclear. This study aims to investigate the role of Claudin-14 in mediating effects of calcium ions on the metabolic stress induced by alkaline condition in *Astyanax mexicanus*. Both surface and cave morphs have been exposed to alkaline water with normal and elevated calcium concentration levels. Standard and maximum metabolic rates were measured by respirometry followed by analyzing the ion concentration of plasma and muscle tissue. Claudin-14 expression in the gill will be quantified via western blotting. Results indicate that standard metabolic rate in alkaline water increases for both morphs however, surface morph had a greater increase than cave morph. Moreover, elevated calcium levels significantly reduced standard metabolic rate in both morphs. Moreover, in fish exposed to elevated calcium and alkaline water, it decreased significantly. Maximum metabolic rate was lower in cave morphs than in surface morphs, and alkaline water further decreased it in both groups. Additionally, elevated calcium level led to increase in maximum metabolic rate. These findings suggest that alkaline water stress increases metabolic demand while calcium helps mitigate this stress. Further analysis of Claudin-14 expression will clarify its specific role in this protective response.

055

EXPLORING PHOSPHORUS CONCENTRATIONS IN *Tigriopus californicus* SALTWATER HABITATS AND THEIR PROLONGED EFFECTS

Shakiraa Suntharalingam*, Dr. Allison McDonald
Department of Biology, Wilfrid Laurier University
Ontario, Canada N2L 3CS

Tigriopus californicus is a saltwater species primarily found along the Pacific Coast of North America. Various environmental stressors can impact species performance, particularly during reproduction, including temperature, salinity, and pH levels. *T. californicus* is a promising model for understanding the mechanisms of environmental stressors on copepods. In assessing these stressors, it is important to evaluate whether *T. californicus* can withstand high concentrations of NaHPO₄. To examine phosphorus levels in copepod habitats, two treatment groups were established, each with different phosphorus concentrations. One treatment contained 0.2 ppm NaHPO₄, and the other 0.002 ppm, compared to a control with no added phosphorus. Results showed that 0.2 ppm was a high concentration that killed 90% of the population within 30 days, whereas the 0.02 ppm treatment progressed well. By the end of the trial, copepods in the 0.02 ppm habitats matured faster than those in the control. The initial goal was to determine a concentration that supported survival without harm. Unexpectedly, the 0.02 ppm group not only survived and reproduced but also matured significantly faster than copepods in regular habitats during the same period.

056

TESTING THE EFFECTS OF HYPOLIMNETIC AERATION IN A POLLUTED NORTHERN LAKE.

Eryn Wolfe*¹, Madeline Patenall¹, Mike Palmer², Derek Gray¹

¹Department of Biology, Wilfrid Laurier University, Waterloo, Ontario, Canada N2L 3C5

²Aurora Research Institute, Yellowknife, NT, Canada X1A 2R3

Over the last several decades, many freshwater lakes exposed to nutrient pollution have been experiencing periodic low oxygen levels as a result of eutrophication. An example is Frame Lake, located in Yellowknife, Northwest Territories. Frame Lake experiences anoxia (the absence of oxygen) in the winter months, resulting in the absence of fish species and a decrease in rotifers, an important group of zooplankton for fish diets. A rehabilitation project is underway on Frame Lake which implements aeration in the hypolimnetic zone (deepest layer in a stratified lake) to increase dissolved oxygen concentrations. This study aims to characterize the effects of hypolimnetic aeration on Frame Lake and identify alterations in water quality and the rotifer community. I will be using survey data for water quality and rotifer samples collected between 2023 and 2024 to provide information on pre-aerator conditions. Rotifer communities will be evaluated for rarefied richness, diversity and total abundance. I have collected new rotifer and water quality data in winter 2024/2025 to characterize post-aerator conditions. This project is important as it will tell us if hypolimnetic aeration is a feasible rehabilitation strategy for northern lakes that have lost biodiversity due to eutrophication.

057

EDNA & SCDNA AS A TOOL FOR CHARACTERIZING PISCIVORE FEEDING ECOLOGY IN LAKE ST. CLAIRKye Banwell^{*1}, Matthew Yates¹, Michael Thorn², Shelby Mackie¹, Daniel Heath¹¹Great Lakes Institute for Environmental Research, University of Windsor, Windsor, Ontario, Canada N9B 3P4²Ontario Ministry of Natural Resources & Forestry, Wheatley, ON N0P 2P0, Canada

Freshwater ecosystems are under threat due to a myriad of anthropologic effects and invasive species. Within freshwater habitats, predation is arguably the most influential factor in shaping ecosystem function and serves as the basis of trophic web interactions. This study aims to characterize predator-prey dynamics in Lake St. Clair using mitochondrial DNA analysis of stomach content DNA analysis via HT-qPCR on OpenArray® chips alongside environmental DNA metabarcoding. Stomach content DNA (scDNA) refers to DNA extracted from the digestive tracts of predators to identify consumed prey, while environmental DNA (eDNA) consists of genetic material shed by organisms into their surroundings through skin, mucus, feces, or other biological processes. The data sets analyzed include eDNA sampled from various locations within Lake St. Clair, complemented by scDNA of yellow perch (*Perca flavescens*) and walleye (*Sander vitreus*), collected within 24 hours of the eDNA at the same sites. This dual approach enhances the resolution of predator-prey interactions by linking prey consumption to ambient community eDNA. Data analysis is ongoing; however, preliminary eDNA metabarcoding results have detected the presence of the predator species of interest, as well as multiple prey species. Final results will provide critical insights into trophic linkages within the lake, allowing for better understanding of these predator-prey dynamics. This understanding is essential for ecosystem assessments and can serve as a foundation for evidence-based conservation strategies to preserve biodiversity and ecological integrity in freshwater systems.

058

IMPACTS OF HUMAN-MADE NOISE ON THE PRESENCE AND SONG STRUCTURE OF EURASIAN BLACKCAPS (SYLVIA ATRICAPILLA)

Madison Bygrove*, Jaclyn Aubin, Dan Mennill

Department Integrative Biology, University of Windsor, Ontario, Canada N9B 3P4

Human activities have transformed natural environments, introducing noise from traffic, industry, and urbanization. Human-made noise interferes with animal communication, posing a significant challenge for wild animals that rely on vocalizations for territory defense and mate attraction. In some instances, animals are driven out of available habitat by urban noise, while in others, they adapt to urban noise by raising the pitch of their songs to avoid being masked by human-made noise. In this study, our goal was to investigate the impact of urban noise on habitat occupancy and singing behavior of a European songbird, the Eurasian Blackcap (*Sylvia atricapilla*). We used autonomous recorders to collect ambient recordings at 165 sites across urban environments in Paris, France. We evaluated the ambient noise levels within each recording, assessed the presence of Blackcaps, and measured acoustic features of Blackcap songs. We found that Blackcaps were more likely to be present at sites with lower noise levels (49.5 ± 0.9 dB(A)) compared to those with higher noise levels (55.0 ± 0.5 dB(A)), suggesting that Blackcaps preferentially occupy quieter urban areas. We found no correspondence between ambient noise and Blackcap song characteristics, suggesting that Blackcaps do not adjust their song structure in response to high urban noise. We conclude that rather than modifying their songs, Blackcaps adapt to urban noise by avoiding high-noise areas. By understanding how songbirds respond to urban noise, this study can inform urban planning and noise management strategies that support avian populations in increasingly noisy cities.

059

EFFECTS OF ANTHROPOGENIC NOISE IN PARIS ON THE EUROPEAN ROBIN

Callia Collard*, Sarah Dobney, and Dan Mennill

Department of Integrative Biology, University of Windsor, Windsor, Ontario, Canada N9B3P4

Anthropogenic noise levels around the world have been increasing. With this rise in noise levels, we observe changes in animal behavior. The people of Paris, France, have attempted to fight noise pollution in recent years, but are these efforts enough to influence the behaviour of urban birds? In this study, our goal was to investigate European Robins (*Erithacus rubecula*) in an environment with high levels of anthropogenic noise and evaluate whether their presence and song features were influenced by noise levels. We recorded bird song in 166 locations, in parks and urban spaces in downtown Paris. At each location, we determined if robins were present or not. For locations with robins, we isolated one high quality song, measured the number of song syllables, song length and the maximum and minimum song frequency. We observed that European Robins were less likely to be found singing in high levels of anthropogenic noise and our song analyses indicate that there was no correlation between song features and anthropogenic noise. We conclude that European Robins are either not present, or less vocal, in areas with increased anthropogenic noise suggesting a low tolerance to noise. When they are present, they do not show changes in their song structure in relation to noise features. These findings imply that bird species, such as European Robins, are not tolerant of anthropogenic noise and may struggle to communicate in noisy areas or depart from available habitats in an attempt to escape urban noise.

060

WHITE SHARK SCARRING IN AUSTRALIAN WATERS: WOUND CLASSIFICATION, DISTRIBUTION AND ACCUMULATION RATESMichael Anthony Douaihy*¹, Joseph Fotso¹, Charlie Huveneers², Lauren Meyer², Andrew Fox³ and Nigel E Hussey¹¹Department of Integrative Biology, University of Windsor, Windsor, ON, N9B 3P4, Canada²College of Science and Engineering, Flinders University, Bedford Park, South Australia 5042, Australia³Fox Shark Research Foundation, Adelaide, South Australia 5070, Australia

Animal interactions are complex to study underwater due to challenges of the environment and limitations of current direct sampling techniques. Analysis of animal scarring offers an alternative to traditional approaches to assess both intra- and interspecies interactions (i.e. interactions with conspecifics or predators and prey, respectively), while also allowing identification of individual animals, assisting health assessments and monitoring anthropogenic impacts. Here, we quantified injuries observed on white sharks off Southern Australia, identified the origin of these injuries, determined wound acquisition of individual sharks over time and assessed their distribution over 12 distinct body zones on this predator. Assessments were conducted using high quality images of 20 randomly sampled white sharks, 10 females and 10 males, taken during systemic cage diving operations between June 2010 to November 2014. Images were screened for analysis based on pre-defined criteria and provided a time series of wound patterns ranging from weeks to years for each individual. Scarring analysis identified nine distinct injury categories on the body of sampled white sharks: claw marks, tooth rakes, amputation (i.e. part of appendage missing; ex: fin or tail), shark bite, seal puncture wounds, anthropogenic, cookie cutter, invasive science contact and unidentified injuries. These injuries were primarily observed on the dorsal trunk and head regions, with claw marks being the most abundant. Understanding the frequency and extent of white shark predator-prey interactions and anthropogenic threats through non-invasive scarring analysis is necessary to inform on the ecology and impacts to this species for ongoing management and conservation efforts.

061

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SOCIAL CALLS AND FLIGHT BEHAVIOURS IN BIG BROWN BATSRana Elkafarneh*¹, Dr. Hannah ter Hofstede¹.¹Department of Integrative Biology, University of Windsor, Windsor, Ontario, Canada N9B 3P4

The use of echolocation calls for orientation has been well-studied across bat species, but the functions of their social calls have not. Social calls have been documented in many species and appear to have multiple functions, such as food claiming or avoiding collisions. Big brown bats (*Eptesicus fuscus*), which are abundant in North America, have social calls that may be emitted during interactions in flight; however, not all of these social calls have identified functions, or they may have different functions in different contexts. This study documents the interactions between big brown bats to identify the relationship between specific behaviours and specific social calls. Pairs of male bats were released into a large flight enclosure and their calls and behaviour were recorded on microphones and an acoustic camera to determine the relationship between calls and behaviour. The acoustic camera overlays a heatmap of the sound onto video, providing information about which bat produced each call. Preliminary results suggest that one type of call signals avoidance behaviour, but further analysis is required to identify the behaviours pertaining to specific social calls.

062

WHAT'S ALL THE BUZZ ABOUT: HABITAT USE OVERLAP IN BATS AND AERIAL INSECTIVORE BIRDSNatalie Emerick*¹, Hannah ter Hofstede¹

Department of Integrative Biology, University of Windsor, Windsor, Ontario, Canada N9B 3P4

Aerial insectivores are a charismatic group of birds and bats that consume insects during flight. In southern Ontario, aerial insectivore birds have gained attention from the scientific community by being classified as the steepest declining bird population, becoming locally endangered. This is thought to be due to the reduction of insect populations from human disturbances. Essex County has a mix of natural and urbanized areas, which provides an ideal environment for investigating how different habitat types might be used by local species of aerial insectivores. The objective of the current study is to compare the habitat use by aerial insectivores in naturalized and human-modified environments. This study recorded vocal activity of aerial insectivore birds and the echolocation calls of bats across four unique habitat types (forest vs suburban; prairie vs agricultural). The short echolocation buzzes indicative of feeding behaviour were also quantified for bats. Bird and bat vocal activity were analyzed using both automated software and visual inspection of spectrograms. If human habitat modification decreases daytime and nocturnal flying insect abundance, then it is expected that both aerial hawking bird and bat activity will be higher in natural than modified habitats. Results are expected to demonstrate an overlap in aerial hawking bird vocal activity with bat feeding buzzes, particularly in naturalized habitats. Aerial insectivores uniquely benefit ecosystem health by providing natural insect control. Observing the overlap of daytime and nocturnal aerial insectivore habitat use can be used to inform conservation strategies for these species.

063

ASSESSING THE IMPACT OF ENVIRONMENTAL NOISE ON AUDITORY HAIR CELL DENSITY IN BLUEGILL SUNFISH (*LEPOMIS MACROCHIRUS*)

Lama Farah*, and Dennis M. Higgs.

Department of Integrative Biology, University of Windsor, Windsor, Ontario, Canada N9B 3P4

Rising environmental noise in aquatic ecosystems threatens fish auditory structures, potentially impairing key behaviours such as communication, navigation, and predator avoidance. The current study investigates the impact of environmental noise levels on auditory hair cell density in Bluegill (*Lepomis macrochirus*), a freshwater species that relies on auditory cues for survival. Fish were collected from two distinct environments—one characterized by low noise levels and the other by elevated anthropogenic noise. Fish were euthanized in 2 phenoxyethanol and then preserved in 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA) following collection. Ears were dissected from heads and sensory macula and otoliths were removed for analysis. Hair cells visualization was achieved using Oregon Green Phalloidin staining, which binds to actin filaments within the hair cell microvilli. Hair cell density was then quantified and analyzed to assess the effects of noise exposure. Fish from noisier habitats exhibited reduced hair cell density compared to those from quieter environments, indicating structural damage associated with chronic noise exposure. These apparent differences in hair cell density provide evidence that environmental noise negatively impacts auditory system integrity in fish. Understanding these effects may inform conservation efforts by highlighting the need for noise management strategies in freshwater ecosystems. Additionally, this study lays the groundwork for future research on the broader ecological consequences of auditory impairment in fish, including potential impacts on population dynamics, predator-prey interactions, and species resilience in noise-polluted habitats. This research bridges gaps in sensory biology and aquatic conservation by demonstrating how environmental noise affects fish auditory structures.

064

THE EFFECTS OF ANTHROPOGENIC NOISE ON THE SONG STRUCTURE AND HABITAT OCCUPANCY OF THE EURASIAN WREN (*TROGLODYTES TROGLODYTES*)

Kristine Kamensky*, Nelsy Niño, and Daniel Mennill.

Department of Integrative Biology, University of Windsor, Windsor, Ontario, Canada N9B 3P4

Animals living near humans have to deal with high levels of anthropogenic noise, which can disrupt their acoustic communication. Paris, France, is a particularly interesting city for studying anthropogenic noise because the French government has made significant efforts to reduce anthropogenic noise levels. Eurasian Wrens (*Troglodytes troglodytes*), a common species in urban Paris, sing highly variable songs with a broad frequency range, including lower frequencies typically masked by the urban noise of traffic and industry. In this study, our goal was to determine whether levels of anthropogenic noise influence both habitat occupancy and song structure of Eurasian Wrens. From 2023 springtime field recordings, we analyzed field recordings collected in urban areas, green spaces, and parks at 134 sites in Paris. We evaluated whether wrens were present at each site and compared this to the ambient noise levels. For each site where a wren was recorded, we measured minimum frequency, maximum frequency, song length, and number of notes in their song. Our results reveal that wrens are more likely to be present in areas with lower noise levels. Within the sites where wrens are present, our results suggest that as noise levels increase, wrens raise their minimum frequency and shorten their song length. In contrast, we found no evidence of changes in maximum frequency or number of notes. We conclude that wrens modify their song features in response to increasing noise levels, and the likelihood of their presence is influenced by ambient noise levels.

065

BIOTIC AND ABIOTIC INFLUENCES ON FISH DIVERSITY AND DISTRIBUTION IN THE ST. LAWRENCE RIVER USING ENVIRONMENTAL DNAZain Khan*¹, Daniele Heath *², Matthew Yates *³

Department of Integrative Biology, University of Windsor, Windsor, Ontario, Canada N9B 3P4

¹Department of Biological Sciences, University of Windsor, Windsor, Ontario, Canada N9B3P4

Environmental DNA (eDNA) has emerged as a powerful tool for assessing fish biodiversity and informing conservation efforts in aquatic ecosystems. This study examines how biotic (e.g., phytoplankton, bacterial diversity) and abiotic (e.g., temperature, dissolved oxygen, water flow, contaminants) factors correlate with fish diversity and distribution in the St. Lawrence River, with a focus on endangered and invasive species. As part of the 2020 *Lampsilis* survey mission, eDNA samples were collected from multiple river sites and processed to determine fish species presence. Metabarcoding and quantitative PCR (qPCR) will be used to analyze species composition and compare detection efficiencies of these molecular techniques. Statistical analyses, including correlation tests and multivariate approaches, will be applied to explore relationships between environmental factors and fish community composition. By identifying key ecological drivers of species distribution, this research will contribute to improved conservation strategies for at-risk native species and management interventions for invasive species. Additionally, this study highlights the potential of eDNA as a non-invasive, efficient tool for monitoring biodiversity in large freshwater ecosystems.

066

GENE TRANSCRIPTION PROFILE RESPONSE TO HYBRID BREAKDOWN AND TEMPERATURE STRESS IN CHINOOK SALMON FRY (*ONCORHYNCHUS TSHAWYTSCHA*).Renil Kooplicat^{1*}, Patricia Voyer¹, Shelby Mackie³, Kyle Wellband², and Daniel Heath^{1,3}¹Department of Integrative Biology, University of Windsor, Windsor, Ontario, Canada N9B 3P4²Department of Fisheries and Oceans, Canada, West Vancouver Lab, BC, Canada V7V 1H2³Great Lakes Institute for Environmental Research, University of Windsor, Windsor, Ontario, Canada N9B 3P4

Hybridization between genetically distinct populations of Chinook salmon (*Oncorhynchus tshawytscha*) can lead to either genetic rescue, where offspring exhibit increased fitness, or hybrid breakdown, where offspring suffer reduced fitness due to genomic incompatibilities. Determining how among-population hybridization interacts with environmental stressors, such as rising water temperatures due to climate change, is critical for conservation efforts that may involve translocation of salmon among watersheds. This study examines the gene transcription profile response of 56 stress-related genes in Chinook salmon fry derived from pure and hybrid crosses across four populations in British Columbia (Nitinat, Chilliwack, Big Qualicum, and Lower Shuswap). Gametes were collected and crossed in all possible combinations to produce 16 family groups, which were then subjected to control or heat stress conditions. Whole-body RNA was extracted, converted to cDNA, and analyzed using OpenArray qPCR technology to assess gene expression differences. We hypothesize that heat stress will induce gene transcription changes in all fish but that hybrids will exhibit more dysregulated transcriptional patterns compared to purebred individuals, indicative of hybrid breakdown. Gene transcription data will be analyzed to assess differences among cross types and treatment conditions. Preliminary findings will provide insight into whether hybridization disrupts regulated gene expression under environmental stress, as well as if potential maternal/paternal effects play a role. These results are essential for evaluating the potential risks and benefits of mixing populations in salmon enhancement thus informing management strategies in the face of climate change.

067

EXPLORING THE BIASES OF BAITED REMOTE UNDERWATER VIDEOS FOR AQUATIC ECOLOGY

Reese Miller* and Dennis Higgs

Department of Integrative Biology, University of Windsor, Windsor, Ontario, Canada N9B 3P4

Baited Remote Underwater Video (BRUV) is a popular method for both marine and freshwater research, especially for investigations on species abundance and behaviour. Variations in design, including camera position and bait type, have evolved from increased use of BRUVs so questions remain on whether the BRUV itself selects for certain behaviours or interactions between fish. The purpose of the current study is to see if BRUVs are biased by conditions, soundscapes, or presence of bait, all independent of additional sound. The following can then be hypothesized: if different combinations of habitat noise level and bait show different results and behaviours, then the BRUV is biased towards certain conditions. It is predicted that the BRUV will be biased to quiet environments with bait. Trials were conducted at two different locations with different noise levels. At each location, 10 trials were conducted with bait, and 10 without. The effects of the above variables will be analyzed for time of first appearance, residence times, number of fish, and feeding attempts. Early results indicate the highest number of feeding attempts in the noisy environment with bait. BRUV is a very useful tool in marine and freshwater research, but its usefulness could improve with further knowledge of its biases. The current study will improve our knowledge of how to test this method not only locally, but also globally places to test biases more specific to a certain location with certain species.

068

CONTINUOUS OR BIMODAL: INVESTIGATING VARIABILITY IN MOTH EVASIVE RESPONSES TO BAT PREDATOR CUES

Tamjeed Nawaz*, Hadia Nadeem, Hannah ter Hofstede.

Department of Integrative Biology, University of Windsor, Windsor, Ontario, Canada, N9A 0C5

Prey animals often exhibit bimodal responses to predator cues. If they are outside the predator's range or detection distance, they often engage in simple behaviours such as freezing or moving away from the predator. However, once predators are close, prey typically exhibit more complex and unpredictable escape behaviours. Many moth species can hear the echolocation calls of bats and appear to exhibit similarly categorical responses: fly away from a distant bat or perform erratic evasive flight in response to a close bat. Yet there has not been much research into variability in this supposedly rigid behaviour. To test whether moth evasive response is truly bimodal or exhibits a range of variability within each response type. Noctuid and Erebid moths were exposed in flight to the echolocation calls of *Eptesicus fuscus*, a sympatric bat species, and their behavioural responses were recorded with two video cameras. The 3D flight path of the moth was then mapped using the Pro-analyst software, and key values such as their acceleration, velocity, and angular velocity were recorded. The moths were exposed to different amplitude calls depending on their location in flight when they detected the calls. Preliminary analysis showed that moths perform a variety of responses to bat echolocation calls in flight. Further analyses will reveal whether this variation exists as a bimodal response, or a more graded response to sound amplitude at the moth.

069

EFFECT OF QACA/B EFFLUX PUMPS ON POVIDONE-IODINE RESISTANCE IN STAPHYLOCOCCUS EPIDERMIDIS

Nerojini Nehruji*, Bukola R. Aremu, Wence Herrera and John F. Trant.

Department of Chemistry and Biochemistry, University of Windsor, Windsor, Ontario, Canada N9B 3P4
Trant Team, Windsor, Canada N9B 3P4

Hospital-acquired infections pose a significant danger to patients—especially those being fitted with implantable medical devices, where opportunistic bacterial colonization can lead to chronic infection. Treatment-resistant chronic infection arises due to a combination of biofilm formation and antiseptic resistance in aggressive pathogens such as *Staphylococcus epidermidis*. This resistance is partly due to the expression of QacA/B efflux pumps that extrude antiseptics such as povidone-iodine (PVP-I) from the cytoplasm, preventing accumulation and decreasing their bactericidal activity. We investigated the role of efflux pumps in PVP-I resistance and explored the potential of efflux pump inhibitors (EPIs), which stop efflux pump functioning, to enhance antiseptic efficacy synergistically. We tested two strains of *S. epidermidis*: ATCC 35984 (qacA/B positive) and ATCC 12228 (qacA/B negative). PVP-I resistance was evaluated through both minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) and minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) assays. We considered both the antiseptic alone, and its combination with qacA/B EPIs, Reserpine (20 µg/mL), sodium orthovanadate (100 µM), and carbonyl cyanide m-chlorophenyl hydrazone (10 µM). By targeting the efflux pumps directly, we aim to determine the underlying cause of resistance to PVP-I. To further investigate efflux activity, we performed an ethidium bromide accumulation assay in which bacterial cells were incubated with ethidium bromide and the fluorescence intensity measured. Quantitative real-time PCR was performed to determine changes in gene expression in response to the pressure. The findings will provide insight into the role that qacA/B efflux pumps play in mediating PVP-I resistance and could suggest methods to improve antiseptic protocols in clinical settings.

070

EFFECTS OF HANDLING STRESS ON POST-SWIM STRESS PHYSIOLOGY IN JUVENILE LAKE STURGEON (*ACIPENSER FULVESCENS*)

Christopher Sankarlal*, Dane Roberts, Trevor E. Pitcher

Department of Integrative Biology, University of Windsor, Windsor, Ontario, Canada N9B 3P4

Lake sturgeon (*Acipenser fulvescens*) populations have declined due to habitat loss, overfishing, and dam construction, leading to ongoing conservation and restoration efforts for the species. Hatchery-reared juveniles are commonly reintroduced into the wild using management practices that involve brief air exposure and handling prior to release. While necessary, these practices may induce physiological stress, potentially impacting post-release survival. This study examines the effects of handling stress on sturgeon stress physiology by analyzing concentrations of physiological stress indicators, such as blood glucose, lactate, and plasma osmolality. Juvenile sturgeon were exposed to standardized handling stress after a swim trial to assess whether standardized handling stress prior to swimming has any effect on stress physiology compared to control fish. Understanding this management practice is crucial for refining and ensuring that current reintroduction methods support sturgeon survival in the wild. If loading practices significantly impact stress physiology, modifications to handling procedures may be necessary to improve the reintroduction process. These findings contribute to the field of restoration physiology and help determine the best practices for managing juvenile lake sturgeon before their release, overall contributing to conservation efforts to restore wild populations.

071

THE HEARTBEAT OF RIVER ECOSYSTEMS: EXPLORING INDICATORS OF ECOLOGICAL HEALTH IN URBAN WINDSOR-ESSEX RIVERSAmesh H. P. Wickramasinghe*¹¹Department of Integrative Biology, University of Windsor, Windsor, Ontario, Canada, N9B 3P4

The health of headwaters have significant impacts on the broader ecological health of freshwater systems. Anthropogenic inputs from agriculture and urban developments can significantly influence the water quality and ecological health throughout a freshwater system. This study focuses on examining the ecological health of four river systems in largely agricultural or urbanized areas in the Windsor-Essex region (WER) with the focus being on the Little River system. This research aims to answer two primary questions; (1) What suite of metrics best captures the ecological health of rivers in the Windsor-Essex region? (2) What is the ecological health status across Windsor-Essex rivers? Water samples were taken from Little River and three analogous river systems in the WER and were analyzed for water quality, nutrient composition, and carbon characterization. The expected results for the analysis are that areas along the river systems in closer proximity to urbanized or agricultural land will exhibit relatively poor ecological health. Overall, this study aims to create a baseline of measurements for the ecological health of Little River to determine the health status of the river as well as inform future decisions in restoration and management practices in the WER.

075

POTENTIAL REGULATION OF THE RAC EXCHANGE FACTOR PREX1 BY THE TRANSCRIPTION FACTOR KAISOHolly J.A.G. Stibbe*^{1,2}, Robert W. Cowan^{1,2}, Stephanie Ali Fairbairn^{1,2}, Lindyann R. Lessey^{1,2}, and Juliet M. Daniel^{1,2}.¹Department of Biology, McMaster University, Hamilton, Ontario, Canada, L8S 4L8²Centre for Discovery in Cancer Research (CDCR), McMaster University, Hamilton, Ontario, Canada, L8S 4L8

Vertebrate development is the process whereby a fertilized egg transforms into an adult form of the organism. In addition to playing a role in several human cancers, the POZ-ZF transcription factor Kaiso has been implicated in vertebrate development, with its highest expression occurring in the brain. Unpublished data from our lab and others suggest that Kaiso malfunction or loss contributes to human developmental disorders. Individuals with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) are believed to have atypical development, sometimes starting prior to birth. Phosphatidylinositol-3,4,5-trisphosphate-dependent Rac exchange factor 1 (PREX1) is a guanine nucleotide exchange factor associated with normal vertebrate development, but is also implicated in the pathogenesis of ASD and several human cancers. Kaiso binds to Kaiso Binding Sites (KBS) or methylated CpG dinucleotides to regulate gene expression. The *PREX1* promoter contains methylated CpG sites in colon tumours, which may be potential binding sites for Kaiso. A young adult male with developmental delays and behavioural issues was recently found to have point mutations in the Kaiso (*ZBTB33*) and *PREX1* genes. We hypothesize that Kaiso regulates the expression of *PREX1*, and that the *PREX1* mutation affects its function. Kaiso knockout in a human breast cancer cell line resulted in decreased PREX1 expression, as assessed by immunoblot and quantitative reverse transcription polymerase chain reaction (RT-qPCR), but Kaiso knockdown in a human brain cancer cell line had no effect on PREX1 expression. Understanding this molecular mechanism is crucial for identifying biomarkers for developmental disorders.

076

INVESTIGATING THE INVOLVEMENT OF KAISO IN CHEMOTHERAPY DRUG SENSITIVITY OF TRIPLE-NEGATIVE BREAST CANCER CELL LINES USING KNOCKOUT CELLSAkudo C.J. Eze-Onuorah^{*1,2}, Hanad Adan^{2,3}, Robert W. Cowan^{2,3}, Shaiya Robinson¹, and Juliet M. Daniel^{2,3}¹School of Interdisciplinary Science, McMaster University, Hamilton, Ontario, Canada L8S 4L8²Centre for Discovery in Cancer Research (CDCR), McMaster University, Hamilton, Ontario, Canada, L8S 4L8³Department of Biology, McMaster University, Hamilton, Ontario, Canada, L8S 4L8

Triple-negative breast cancer (TNBC) is a very aggressive breast cancer subtype that is characterized by a lack of Estrogen Receptor, Progesterone Receptor, and Human Epidermal Growth Factor Receptor 2 (HER2) expression. TNBC disproportionately affects Women of African Ancestry (WAA), who have been found to have high nuclear expression of the transcription factor Kaiso and which correlates with TNBC's poorer prognosis and survival. Previous research in our lab has implicated Kaiso in tumorigenesis, cancer cell survival, inflammation in many human cancers, and regulating epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT). Through EMT, tumor cells inducing drug resistance, which lends current TNBC treatment strategies ineffective. Recent studies suggest that Kaiso plays a key role in drug resistance in TNBC by promoting EMT. This study investigates how Kaiso influences TNBC cells' response to chemotherapy using two TNBC parental cell lines and their Kaiso knockout (KO) derivatives. Cell viability and apoptosis was evaluated after treatment with the chemotherapeutic drugs Cisplatin and Doxorubicin. Preliminary results revealed that cells Kaiso KO cells were more sensitive to the drugs, suggesting that Kaiso plays a critical role in TNBC drug resistance. Interestingly, EMT markers like SNAI2 are absent from Kaiso KO derivatives after treatment with Doxorubicin, reinforcing the link between Kaiso and EMT. Our findings highlight Kaiso as a possible regulator of TNBC drug resistance and suggest that targeting Kaiso or its downstream pathways may improve therapeutic outcomes in patients.

077

KAISO REGULATES ANDROGEN RECEPTOR TARGET GENES ASSOCIATED WITH INCREASED CELL PROLIFERATION IN TRIPLE-NEGATIVE BREAST CANCER (TNBC)Kyle Kim^{*1,2}, Stephanie Ali Fairbairn^{1,2}, Robert W. Cowan^{1,2}, Lindyann Lessey^{1,2}, and Juliet M. Daniel^{1,2}.¹Department of Biology, McMaster University, Hamilton, Ontario, Canada, L8S 4L8²Centre for Discovery in Cancer Research (CDCR), McMaster University, Hamilton, Ontario, Canada, L8S 4L8

Breast cancer (BCa) is a heterogeneous disease and is the leading cause of female deaths worldwide. Triple-negative breast cancer (TNBC) is an aggressive BCa subtype characterized by the absence of estrogen receptor (ER), progesterone receptor (PR), and human epidermal growth factor receptor 2 (HER2). This results in limited treatment options and poor prognoses, particularly among women of African ancestry (WAA). Quadruple-negative breast cancer (QNBC) is a TNBC subtype that lacks the androgen receptor (AR), is more aggressive and thus has increased mortality rates. Interestingly, the transcription factor Kaiso is highly expressed in TNBC and is implicated in cancer progression due to its key role regulating genes associated with proliferation and metastasis. Recently, AR has emerged as a potential therapeutic target for TNBC. *In silico* analysis identified a strong correlation between Kaiso, AR, and ACSL4, a gene involved in lipid metabolism and tumour growth. Unpublished data from our lab has confirmed that Kaiso knockout increases AR expression, and thus we hypothesized that Kaiso influences AR downstream target genes. Immunoblot analyses revealed decreased ACSL4 expression in Kaiso knockout TNBC cell lines compared to parental cell lines. This suggests that Kaiso is a key transcriptional regulator of AR-mediated gene expression. Ongoing research aims to further elucidate the correlation between Kaiso and AR's downstream target genes in QNBC and TNBC. Understanding these molecular mechanisms is crucial for identifying targetable biomarkers for drug development to improve the prognosis of TNBC and QNBC patients.

078

GASTROINTESTINAL PARASITE INFLUENCE ON GLUCOCORTICOIDS IN WILD DEER MICE (PEROMYSCUS MANICULATUS)

Cameron Lefebvre

Laurentian University

Parasite-host interactions are crucial factors influencing population dynamics of animals. Glucocorticoids (GCs) play a significant role in modulating immune function with corticosterone being one of the primary GCs found in many rodents. Elevated levels of corticosterone increase the likelihood of parasitic infection because of its role in suppression of the immune response. This can lead to a positive feedback loop once infected, with the parasite presence further increasing GC levels. We expect to find helminth parasite eggs within our fecal samples. The primary objectives are to assess the gastrointestinal helminth parasite load and determine fecal corticosterone concentrations in wild populations. We predict that individuals with parasitic infections will exhibit higher fecal corticosterone levels compared to their uninfected counterparts. Additionally, we aim to explore whether parasite intensity and diversity influence corticosterone levels, predicting that different parasite species may exert varying degrees of physiological stress on their hosts. Fecal glucocorticoid analysis allows for analysis of GC levels over a roughly 24-hour period, offering advantages over short-term (30-60 seconds) blood or long-term (several months) hair sample GC analysis. We collected fecal samples from adult Deer Mice (*Peromyscus maniculatus*) populations in Algonquin Park and preserved them in 80% methanol. Parasite presence and load was evaluated using the McMaster egg counting technique, a widely used method for quantifying helminth infections. Fecal corticosterone levels were measured using an enzyme immunoassay. Preliminary results found *Capillaria* sp., *Hymenolepis* sp., and *Strongyloides* sp. in most of the fecal samples.

079

CORRIDOR ECOLOGY: ANIMAL ACTIVITY NEAR SHORELINES IN THE LAKE LAURENTIAN CONSERVATION AREA, SUDBURY, ONTARIO

Hazel Barr*, Jean-francois Robitaille

School of Natural Sciences, Laurentian University, Sudbury, Ontario, Canada, P3E 2C6

Fragmentation creates natural corridors used by animals to reach different habitat patches. Land animals avoid clearings and water, and riparian corridors may be used by semi-aquatic animals. Six trail cameras were deployed in six pre-selected sites in the Lake Laurentian Conservation Area (LLCA) between May and October 2024, with three cameras near water bodies and three in the forest. Each micro-site was photographed, trees were measured to document forest cover and the distance to water was also measured. A tree on the site was marked using a few drops of commercial animal lure, refreshed every 2 weeks. At each visit, the camera was checked, and the SD card was swapped with an empty card. The SD card with data was downloaded on a laptop for further analysis and positive wildlife captures were extracted. The average % herbaceous layer was similar between the two types of sites, but the average % shrub layer was slightly higher in forest sites. The average diameter of trees was higher in Riparian sites. The tree species that were found were Jack pine, White pine, Red pine, Trembling aspen, White birch, Red oak and Red maple. During this study, cameras captured three species of large predators, three small predators, one ungulate, three rodents and four species of birds. The forest sites have more visits than riparian sites, but both types of sites had similar richness and diversity index (H'). Most animals were seen during the day and they left after a short while.

080

FOREST SUCCESSION 2003-2024 AND ANIMAL ACTIVITY IN LAKE LAURENTIAN CONSERVATION AREA IN SUDBURY, ONTARIO, CANADA

Shannon Crockford*

Supervisor: Jean-Francois Robitaille

School of Natural Sciences, Laurentian University, Sudbury, Ontario, Canada P3E 2C6

The Sudbury area underwent catastrophic environmental degradation after the introduction of the mining industry in 1883, which drove the city to take action in 1978, implementing the Sudbury Land Reclamation project. There has been immense recovery since the beginning of the project, and forest succession has been used to track this progress. In 2003, a study was conducted at LLCA to observe where the forest area lies in succession by measuring tree diameters and recording the surroundings. This study is a follow-up of the original study, sampling comparable sites at LLCA. In addition to this, wildlife cameras were monitored to observe wildlife activity in plantation and natural regeneration sites. Forest composition has shifted and it has been found that DBH and CWD has increased over the last 21 years, with herbaceous and shrub coverage decreasing. A wider variety of animal species were observed in plantation sites. Initial data indicates that LLCA has indeed progressed in forest succession, showing success in growth, even after such intense deterioration to the forest community.

081

REACTIVE OXYGEN SPECIES IN CHEMOTHERAPY-DEPENDENT RNA DISRUPTION AND DEATH IN OVARIAN TUMOUR CELLS

Joshua Freimanis*

School of Natural Sciences, Laurentian University, Sudbury, Ontario, Canada P3E 2C6

RNA disruption is a phenomenon characterized by chemotherapy-induced degradation of ribosomal RNA and is currently being assessed in clinical trials as a biomarker of complete tumour destruction in patients. While the cellular mechanisms which drive RNA disruption are poorly understood, many chemotherapeutics strongly induce the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) in cancer cells. In this study, we examined a potential mechanistic link between chemotherapy-dependent ROS generation, RNA disruption, and cell death. To do so, we investigated the ability of the antioxidant N-acetyl cysteine (NAC) to mute ROS production, RNA disruption, and cell death in A2780 ovarian tumour cells treated with the chemotherapeutic doxorubicin (DOX). Preliminary experiments using 2',7'-dichlorodihydrofluorescein diacetate (H2DCFDA) to detect ROS by fluorimetry suggest that while DOX treatments were able to increase cellular ROS levels, NAC appeared unable to significantly mute these increases. Consistent with these results, capillary gel electrophoresis of cellular RNA revealed that NAC did not significantly prevent RNA disruption caused by DOX. DNA content analyses showed that NAC also failed to prevent DOX-induced cell death. While an association between DOX-induced ROS production, RNA disruption, and cell death was established, it is unclear why NAC did not inhibit ROS production by DOX. Overall, this study will provide guidance for future investigations which can benefit from larger sample sizes to further elucidate the role of ROS, if any, in the ability of chemotherapy agents to promote RNA disruption and cell death.

082

MORE ON BITE FORCE AND ENCEPHALIZATION IN THE FAMILY CANIDAE AND IN WOLVERINES (*GULO GULO*).

Matteo Vocaturo*, Jean-Francois Robitaille

School of Natural Sciences, Laurentian University, Sudbury, Ontario, Canada, P3E 2C6

Cranial morphology can explain many aspects of an animal's life. Features such as bite force and brain volume can inform us about ecological niches and evolutionary adaptations. Bite force is influenced by factors like prey type, and brain volume may be influenced by an animal's cognitive abilities. This study aims to review different estimators for bite force and brain volume, and to compare these traits between two groups of animals, social canids including eastern wolves (*Canis lupus lycaon*) and coyotes (*Canis latrans*) and solitary mustelids, specifically wolverines (*Gulo gulo*). We will contrast ecological roles and behaviors with relative bite force and brain volume. Twenty-four skulls were analyzed including twelve canids and twelve wolverines. Each fresh head underwent a defleshing process which involved manual removal of soft tissue and boiling. Using ImageJ software, measurements were taken including length, width, height to estimate cross sectional areas of the masseter and temporal muscles and thereby, bite force based on existing models. Brain volume was estimated by filling the endocranium with copper pellets with a diameter of 4.5mm through the foramen magnum, thus assessing cranial capacity. I further calculated bite force and brain volume quotients (BFQ and BVQ) to compare observed values with those expected from calculations using skull length as an index for body size. Differences in bite forces, brain volumes, BFQ and BVQ between canids and wolverines will be discussed in relation to their respective behavioral ecologies.

083

PATTERNS OF PARASITISM IN URBAN RODENTS AND EFFECTS OF ECTOPARASITE DIVERSITY ON BODY CONDITION.

Sabrina Lepage*, Luigi Richardson, Albrecht Schulte-Hostedde

School of Natural Sciences, Laurentian University, Sudbury, Ontario, Canada, P3E 2C6

Parasites impose an energetic cost on their hosts due to allocation of energy to the immune system, thus reducing the energy available for other functions such as growth and reproduction. We examined ectoparasites on urban deer mice (*Peromyscus spp.*) and assessed patterns of parasite diversity related to age, sex, capture location, seasonality and body condition. We predicted that male mice would have a higher parasite index compared to females. We also predicted that adult mice would have higher parasite diversity than immatures. As part of a larger project, we trapped mice within multiple "wildland" sites adjacent to buildings in the Greater Toronto Area. Parasites were collected and identified, and the number and taxa found in each sample (tick, mite, lice, fleas, and botflies) was used to calculate Simpson's Diversity index. A total of 132 individuals (57%) were infested with ectoparasites. Adults had significantly higher mean diversity compared to immatures. A general linear model also showed significant effects of session, sex, and age on increased parasite diversity, but not location or body weight residual (BWR), despite the decrease in parasite diversity concordant with increased BWR. We concluded that adult deer mice, males and those caught later in the summer (i.e. August vs July) were more likely to have an increased diversity of ectoparasites, but that this diversity had no significant effect on body condition, nor did diversity vary between sites. These findings help better our understanding of ectoparasite patterns of infestation and emergence and can help inform studies of diseases ecology.

084

EXAMINING THE IMPACT OF COLITIS ON INTESTINAL INFLAMMATION AND L-CELL PHYSIOLOGY IN MICE

Josée McDavid* and Jeffrey Gagnon

School of Natural Sciences, Laurentian University, Sudbury, Ontario, Canada P3E 2C6

Ulcerative colitis (UC) is a type of inflammatory bowel disease that is characterized as a chronic inflammation of the large intestine. With the unknown pathogenesis and increasing prevalence rates worldwide, it is becoming more apparent the need to understand the pathogenesis of this disease to improve treatment options for patients suffering with UC. Within the colon, the enteroendocrine L-cells secrete important peptide hormones such as glucagon-like peptide 1 (GLP-1). GLP-1 has various physiological roles with most recent findings showing an interplay between GLP-1 and inflammation. This study thus aimed to evaluate changes in L-cell physiology and characterize inflammation during colitis. An *in-vivo* model using dextran sulfate sodium (DSS) to induce colitis in mice along with a control group was completed to perform this analysis. Immunoassays on GLP-1 and cluster of differentiation 3 (CD3) (a T-lymphocyte marker), from colonic tissue lysate were completed along with histological staining for goblet cells within the colonic epithelium. Preliminary data indicates L-cell physiology impairments occurring in DSS treated mice with decrease in colonic tissue GLP-1 levels and lower levels of CD3 in the DSS treated group compared to that of the control group. These findings suggest an impairment of immune function in the colitis intestine and an altered L-cell physiology. Further research is required in order to fully understand the involvement of L-cells and GLP-1 in colitis and whether GLP-1 based therapies will have a role to play in colitis.

085

RECOVERY TRAJECTORIES OF BOREAL LAKE ZOOPLANKTON COMMUNITIES IN THE FACE OF MULTIPLE STRESSORSKate Pappin¹ and Brie Edwards²¹ School of Natural Sciences, Laurentian University, Sudbury, Ontario, Canada P3E2C6² Ministry of Environment, Conservation and Parks, Sudbury, Ontario, Canada P3E2C6

The Ontario Ministry of Environment, Conservation and Parks (MECP) has been monitoring Sudbury area lakes for over 40 years. As part of these surveys, zooplankton and chemistry have been recorded to track recovery from acidification, and more recently, effects of emerging stressors. My thesis assessed these parameters to highlight changes in diversity and abundance of zooplankton in the study lakes, their shifting water chemistry, and the complex interactions affecting zooplankton species in Boreal shield lakes, in an attempt to find why some zooplankton are recovering slower than others. Preliminary results show great recovery in many chemical parameters related to acidification. Additionally, many of the lakes showed increases in Simpsons diversity index. Contrastingly, the lakes also showed clear signs of emerging concerns, such as declining calcium levels in 10 of the 11 lakes, or high chloride levels in the more urban lakes. A constrained correspondence analysis (CCA) showed strong impacts of legacy-related stressors (pH, calcium, and nickel concentrations) on relative abundance of zooplankton. The CCA also showed strong relationships between certain zooplankton species and the parameters listed, allowing for the exploration of potential indicator zooplankton that could be used in other lakes to identify health of a lake— both past and present. This exploratory study paves the way for other studies focusing on other influences on zooplankton; either physical, chemical, or biological, and eventually determine the driving forces behind zooplankton recovery and proliferation.

086

CHLORIDE POLLUTION IMPACTS IN BOREAL LAKES: AN INVESTIGATION OF PHYSICOCHEMICAL INTERACTIONS AND BIOLOGICAL RESPONSES USING ZOOPLANKTON COMMUNITIES AS BIOINDICATORSEllis Albrecht*¹, Jocelyne Heneberry², Brie Edwards²¹ Cooperative Freshwater Ecology Unit, Vale Living with Lakes Centre, School of Natural Sciences, Laurentian University, Sudbury, ON P3E 2C6, Canada² Ontario Ministry of the Environment Conservation and Parks, Cooperative Freshwater Ecology Unit, Vale Living with Lakes Centre, Laurentian University, Sudbury, ON P3E 2C6, Canada

The use of road salts is driving freshwater chloride (Cl⁻) pollution across the Northern Hemisphere. Cl⁻ interacts with physicochemical lake processes, altering stratification, mixing regimes, and releasing ions from surrounding soils and sediments. In turn, these environmental changes shift the composition of aquatic communities. The oligotrophic, softwater lakes of Greater Sudbury, Ontario have been particularly sensitive to anthropogenic stressors in the past, namely acidification and metal deposition from mining activities. With this study, we aimed to characterise the interactive effects of freshwater Cl⁻ pollution in Greater Sudbury and identify candidate indicator zooplankton taxa for future studies of Cl⁻ polluted lakes across the Boreal Shield. We selected a mix of 18 urban and remote lakes along a gradient of chloride pollution and surveyed their physical characteristics, water chemistry in the surface (epilimnion) and bottom (hypolimnion) water layers, sediment chemistry, and zooplankton communities. Analysis revealed that Cl⁻ is concentrated in the hypolimnion of the two most polluted lakes and is potentially interacting with the underlying sediments to release sequestered metals (nickel, copper, and zinc) back into the water column. Further, we found that zooplankton communities differed between urban and remote lakes. Urban lakes exhibited significantly lower species richness which may highlight the absence of certain indicator taxa with low Cl⁻ thresholds. With this study, we began to explore how Cl⁻ pollution impacts Boreal waterbodies that have a complex history of anthropogenic stressors. Future research should expand on interactive Cl⁻ effects to establish a comprehensive understanding of how basal taxa will be affected.

087

MESO-CARNIVORES: INVESTIGATING THE DIETS OF THE BOBCAT (FELIS RUFUS) AND EASTERN WOLF (CANIS LUPUS LYCAON)

Naomi Naokwegijig

Laurentian University

The bobcat (*Felis rufus*) and eastern wolf (*Canis lupus lycaon*) are two meso-carnivores that share patterns of wide geographic ranges, setting the stage for adaptability when it comes to their diets. The goal of this study is to investigate the diets of eastern wolves from Northern Ontario (collected 2023-2024) and bobcats from Wisconsin (collected 2022-2023). Using fresh stomachs donated from carcasses to the laboratory, the contents were manually sorted, identified and quantified into prey frequencies and volumes comparatively between two species. It was found that bobcats ($H' = 1.12$) consumed more food than the more diverse eastern wolves ($H' = 1.31$). Frequency has shown that sciurids and ungulates were the dominant prey item for bobcats, and ungulates were the dominant prey item for eastern wolves. Volume shows that 66.1% and 61.04% of total volume in bobcats and eastern wolves respectively, can be attributed to ungulates. Results show that bobcats had a less rich and less diverse diet while consuming sciurids and ungulates more out of the 4 prey categories. It also shows that wolves consumed ungulates more out of the 6 prey categories. The chi-square tests show significant differences in sciurid, small mammal, and plant frequencies and significant differences in sciurid and other mammal volumes. This study provides new data for diet studies and together, quantifying volumes and frequencies will help determine the level of similarities between the two species and their feeding niches in terms of richness, diversity and overlap.

088

THE EFFECTS OF URBANIZATION ON THE MORPHOLOGY OF AMERICAN TOADS (*ANAXYRUS AMERICANUS*).

Miah Wildschut*, David Lesbarrères, and Albrecht Schulte-Hostedde.

Department of Natural Sciences, Laurentian University, Sudbury, Ontario, Canada, P3E 2C6.

Urbanization exerts profound impacts on wildlife, often leading to adaptations in morphology. However, the species-specific effects of urbanization on amphibian populations and their responses to urbanization continue to be explored. American toads (*Anaxyrus americanus*) are the most widely distributed toad species in Ontario, and like many amphibian species, they are known as good indicators of environmental health due to the permeability of their skin and dual life strategy, making them vulnerable to environmental changes. Urban American toad populations were predicted to undergo morphological changes such as decreased parotoid gland size, increased limb size, increased tympanum diameter, reduced melanistic patterning, and increased body condition, due to selective pressures imposed by urbanization, driving natural selection. Adult toads were sampled in Lambton County, Ontario, from seven sites categorized into urban and rural areas using the proportion of impervious surface area. Mass, snout-vent length, limb size, tympanum diameter, parotoid area, melanistic patterning, and body condition were measured for each toad. These features were then analyzed in relation to continuous measures of impervious area in linear mixed effects model analyses. Male toads in urbanized sites were found to be in better body condition than those in less urbanized areas. Furthermore, dorsal melanism was found to decrease as urbanization increased; however, females were more affected than males. The results demonstrate that urbanization may drive morphological differences between urban and rural American toad populations, emphasizing the need for further research on the evolutionary and ecological consequences of urban environments on amphibian morphology.

089

MATERNAL GENETIC BACKGROUND INFLUENCE ON PHENOTYPIC VARIATION IN *DROSOPHILA MELANOGASTER*

Owen Allard*, Thomas J.S. Merritt.

Department of Chemistry and Biochemistry, Laurentian University, Sudbury, Ontario, Canada, P3E 2C6

Phenotypic variation is the observable differences in traits within a population, which are influenced by a combination of environmental and genetic factors. Environmental factors can be controlled for, so it is of interest to focus on the role of genetic background in shaping phenotypic expression. Commonly, genetic backgrounds are often accounted for by using isogenic, genetically identical, lines. While isogenic lines are valuable for investigating phenotypic variation, they do not reflect the complex biology of a typical population that more genetically diverse models can offer. Crossing isogenic lines to create heterozygous crosses introduces a controlled degree of genetic diversity, enhancing biological relevance. However, in doing so, confounding maternal genetic background effects may be introduced. The role that the maternal genetic background plays in the phenotypic variation seen in heterozygous crosses is not well characterized. We used reciprocal heterozygous crosses of *Drosophila melanogaster* to investigate the impact of maternal genetic background on offspring traits, particularly under metabolic stress induced by nickel exposure. We examined how different maternal genetic backgrounds influence five phenotypic traits, including the activity of three cytosolic enzymes (malic enzyme, isocitrate dehydrogenase, glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase), as well as whole body lipid and dietary triglyceride quantification. Using a broad suite of phenotypic traits provides an in-depth organism-wide analysis of the influence of maternal genetic background. Exploring the influence of maternal genetic background provides insight into considerations in future research using heterozygous crosses and deepens our understanding of how maternal genetics shape the diversity within their offspring.

090

RHIZOSPHERE EFFECTS ON ENZYME ACTIVITIES IN RED PINE (*PINUS RESINOSA*) STANDS

Kabwe Nkongolo, Sirui Tong*

School of Natural Sciences , Laurentian University, Ontario, Canada, P3E 2C6

The rhizosphere is a vital component of plant life directly under the plant roots. It is a complex community of microbes, minerals, and enzymatic activity. These components allow for nutrient cycling within the soil and plant roots, making it necessary for plant survival. Several studies have focused on the biogeochemical cycling of elements in this microenvironment. This study aims to better understand the rhizosphere effect on the microbial activity in the soil. Soil samples were collected from three different sites at Laurentian University site. At each site, soil samples were collected from the rhizospheres of the tree red pine (*Pinus resinosa*) trees. Surrounding non-rhizospheric soils were used as controls in three separate areas. Nine different enzymes were analyzed due to their importance in their roles in the ecological processes. They included β -glucosidase (BG), cellobiohydrolase (CBH), β -N-acetylglucosaminidase (Nagasee), aryl sulfatase (AS), acid phosphatase (AP), alkaline phosphatase (ALP), glycine aminopeptidase (GAP), leucine aminopeptidase (LAP), and peroxidase (PER). Preliminary results indicate there is a notable increase in certain enzyme activities, within soils collected from rhizospheres compared to control samples. Detailed analyses will provide insights and information on differences between rhizosphere and non – rhizosphere areas at microbial function levels.

091

INVESTIGATING THE ROLE OF *CHRFAM7A* IN THE IMMUNE RESPONSE OF HUMAN MACROPHAGESOlivia Norman¹, Alain Simard¹, Sujeenthatharmalingam²¹Department of Natural Sciences, Laurentian University, Sudbury, Ontario, Canada, P3E 2C6²Department of Molecular Biology, NOSM University, Sudbury, Ontario, Canada, P3E 2C6

Macrophages play a key role in initiating the inflammatory response through cytokine production, thus acting on the immune system's first line of defense. THP-1 is a human monocytic cell line that can be used to study monocytes and macrophages in vitro. THP-1 macrophages express the human-specific gene *CHRFAM7A* that encodes a truncated form of a nicotinic acetylcholine receptor (nAChR) with unknown function. To elucidate the role of *CHRFAM7A* in the immune system, CRISPR-dCas9-mediated *CHRFAM7A* overexpression (*CHRFAM7A*⁺) cell lines were created in human THP-1 macrophages using a lentiviral delivery system. Transcriptional overexpression of *CHRFAM7A* mRNA was validated with RT-qPCR. Following verification, *CHRFAM7A*⁺ THP-1 monocytic cells were differentiated into naive M0 macrophages using Phorbol-12-Myristate-13-Acetate (PMA). The differentiated M0 macrophages were exposed to the immunogen lipopolysaccharide (LPS) with and without the nAChR agonist nicotine. The nature of the resulting immune response was characterized by ELISA assays to detect and quantify the secreted cytokines Tumor Necrosis Factor alpha (TNF- α), Interleukin-6 (IL-6), and Interleukin-10 (IL-10). In this way, the impact of the gene *CHRFAM7A* on the immune response in THP-1 macrophages was measured. This study hopes to contribute to an understanding of the implications of *CHRFAM7A* expression in the immune system and generate unique immortal cell lines for future research.

092

INFLAMMATION AS A DRIVER OF AGE-RELATED DNA METHYLATIONClaire McInroy*¹ and Dr. Chris Verschoor².¹Laurentian University School of Natural Sciences, Sudbury, ON, Canada P3E 2C6²Health Sciences North Research Institute, Sudbury, ON, Canada P3E 2H2

DNA methylation is an important epigenetic regulatory mechanism that is known to influence biological processes such as gene expression. Studies have shown that DNA methylation exhibits systematic changes with age, subsequently impacting gene expression by inhibiting the binding of transcription factors, causing gene repression. However, *how* aging drives changes in DNA methylation is unclear. We hypothesize that chronic inflammation, which also changes with age, reduces DNA methylation. To evaluate this, we have created a laboratory protocol to estimate site-specific DNA methylation status using a sodium bisulfite treatment to convert unmethylated cytosine to thymine, routine PCR using specific primer sets to distinguish between converted and unconverted DNA, and agarose gel electrophoresis for visualization. From there we can determine the influence of chronic inflammation on DNA methylation using our protocol on DNA extracted from monocytes after application of various amounts of pro-inflammatory cytokines, TNF- α and IL-6. Preliminary data has been valuable in the creation of the protocol by showing important trends in DNA concentration, where low DNA yields are occurring throughout the experiment. This indicates that there is likely damage caused to the DNA by the bisulfite treatment, as well as some loss occurring post DNA precipitation. This data and experimentation has been crucial in determining how we assess DNA methylation status and how/why it changes. Understanding the influence of chronic inflammation on DNA methylation in monocytes will allow scientists to better estimate other age-related outcomes such as frailty, mortality, and how inflammation affects immune cell function as we age.

093

TARDIGRADE DIVERSITY AND COMMUNITY COMPOSITION OF AN ONTARIAN FOREST

Decklyn Brodersen*

Department of Natural Sciences, Laurentian University, Sudbury, Ontario, Canada P3E 2C6

Tardigrades are some of the smallest animals on Earth. They can be found in various environments such as ocean bottoms, mountain tops, and Antarctic glaciers, although they are mainly associated with lichens and mosses. The microenvironmental factors that determine their communities show no consistent patterns across the literature. Tardigrade species and community composition were analyzed in moss and lichen samples within the Macnamara Nature Trail in Arnprior, Ontario, and were analyzed to determine what microenvironmental factors predict tardigrade communities. Morphological features were used to identify the tardigrade species. Tardigrade species richness was found to be negatively associated with the horizontal growth of the substrate. Tardigrade individual abundance was found to be significantly greater on lichens than mosses, with significantly higher individual abundance found on foliose lichens than on crustose and fruticose lichens. This study documents the first recorded observations of *Crenubiotus crenulatus*; *Isohypsibius prosostomus*; *Guidettion prorsirostre*; *Paramacrobotus richtersi*; and *Paramacrobotus tonollii*; within Ontario, the first recorded observations of *Echiniscus arctomys* and *Echiniscus virginicus* in Canada, and the first recorded observations of *Diphyscon greveni* and *Macrobotus ariekammensis* in North America. This study enhances the understanding of tardigrade biodiversity in Ontario, contributing insight into how ecological variables influence species distribution and community composition.

094

INVESTIGATING THE ROLE OF PROSTAGLANDINS AND ISOPROSTANES MEDIATED BY DYSREGULATION OF INFLAMMATORY ENZYME PTGS2 IN RADIATION RESISTANCE OF TRIPLE NEGATIVE BREAST CANCER CELLS

Emma Mageau*¹, Alyssa Murray¹, Noah Dickinson¹, Megan Davis¹, Kaitlyn Marshall-Bergeron¹, Jessica Dougherty², Wuroud Al-Khayyat¹, Ramya Narendrula^{1,2}, Maggie Lavoie¹, Ronan Derbowka¹, Tom Kovala^{1,2,3}, Douglas R. Boreham^{1,2}, Natalie Lefort^{1,2}, Tze Chun Tai^{1,2,3}, Christopher Thome^{1,2,3}, and Sujeenthara Tharmalingam^{1,2,3}

¹School of Natural Sciences, Laurentian University, Sudbury, ON P3E 2C6, Canada

²Medical Sciences Division, NOSM University, 935 Ramsey Lake Rd., Sudbury, ON P3E 2C6, Canada

³Health Sciences North Research Institute, Sudbury, ON P3E 2H2, Canada

Radiation resistance (RR) significantly challenges the treatment of triple negative breast cancer (TNBC). Prostaglandins, a group of bioactive lipid compounds, are involved in various physiological processes. Their dysregulation has been linked to breast cancer progression. Isoprostanes are structurally like prostaglandins, and form through lipid oxidation by reactive oxygen species (ROS). Prostaglandins and isoprostanes may play critical roles in cancer biology, but their involvement in RR is not well understood. Our previous whole-transcriptome analysis revealed significant upregulation of Prostaglandin Synthase 2 (PTGS2) in a RR variant of the MDA-MB-231 TNBC cell line. We hypothesize that PTGS2-mediated dysregulation of prostaglandins and isoprostanes contributes to RR in TNBC cells. We performed RT-qPCR to investigate the relationship between PTGS2 expression and genes involved in cell survival and DNA damage repair. Additionally, since radiation therapy generates ROS, we hypothesize that radiation may increase the production of isoprostanes typically associated with cancer progression. Isoprostane and prostaglandin profiling was done using liquid chromatography tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) on PTGS2 overexpressing MDA-MB-231 cells. Results are currently under analysis. Preliminary data indicates that PTGS2 may play a role in RR, specifically at the 6Gy dose. This study will provide insights into the role of prostaglandins and isoprostanes in RR, potentially identifying novel therapeutic targets to enhance sensitivity of TNBC cells to radiation therapy.

095

INFLUENCE OF NUTRIENT AVAILABILITY ON SENESCENCE IN WETLAND MONOCOT SPECIES WITH DIFFERING NUTRIENT ECONOMIES.

Kayla Twilley

School of Natural Sciences, Laurentian University, Sudbury, Ontario, Canada, P3E 2C6.

A proper timing of senescence is essential to optimize plant production. A delay of the process to elongate growing season must balance the need to senesce in time for nutrient conservation and redistribution before frost. The timing of senescence is influenced both by abiotic and biotic factors, with abiotic factors such as drought, nutrient limitation, and extreme temperatures being the most prominent. This study aimed to investigate the role of nutrient availability in senescence among plants with differing nutrient economies. *Juncus nodosus* is known to acquire and use nutrients rapidly, whereas *Juncus filiformis*, which acquires nutrients at a slower rate, utilizes them more conservatively. To investigate this, all plants were placed in low-nutrient peat moss and divided into two groups: one received ongoing nutrient treatment, while the other had the nutrient treatment terminated at the onset of autumn. A senescence index was calculated. The ANOVA on the index values revealed that neither nutrient treatment, nor the species had a significant effect on the average index values. This is potentially due to inadequate nutrient limitation in the treatment with the terminated nutrient addition. Further research is needed to clarify the impact of nutrient availability on senescence.

096

ELEMENTAL COMPOSITION OF OSTRICH FERN (*MATTEUCCIA STRUTHIOPTERIS*) FIDDLEHEADS IN SUDBURY-MANITOULIN DISTRICTS, ONTARIOMackenzie Hobbs¹, Max Lakanen^{1,2}, Julia Anderson^{1,3}, Mark Charbonneau³, Peter Beckett¹ & Graeme Spiers^{1,4}¹Laurentian University, 935 Ramsey Lake Rd., Sudbury, Ontario, Canada, P3E 2C6²Queens University, 99 University Ave, Kingston, Ontario, Canada, K7L 3N6³Testmark Laboratories, 7 Margaret St N, Garson, Ontario, Canada, P3L 1E1⁴Universidad Nacional Jorge Basadre Grohmann, Tacna, Peru

Foraging, driven by the perceived nutritional benefits of wild foods, ever increasing grocery prices, and tradition, is a common practice among locals in Northern Ontario. One of the most commonly foraged foods are ostrich fern fiddleheads (*Matteuccia struthiopteris*), harvested in spring prior to unfurling into fern fronds. A series of 14 sites across the Sudbury-Manitoulin Districts were selected for the collection of soil and ostrich fern fiddleheads, for detailed characterization, and analysis. The soil samples were analyzed for pH, electrical conductivity, and bulk density, with both total and bioavailable estimates for key nutrient elements in the soils being obtained by ICP-MS analysis of strong acid digests and 0.01 M lithium nitrate (LiNO₃) extraction solutions. The fiddlehead samples were dried, ground, and digested using strong acids in a programmable digestion block, with the analysis of digest solutions being performed using ICP-MS. The key nutrients found in fiddleheads were calcium (397 ± 84 mg/kg), chromium (0.2 ± 0.03 mg/kg), copper (3.5 ± 0.7 mg/kg), iron (10.8 ± 4.6 mg/kg), magnesium (376 ± 48 mg/kg), manganese (3.9 ± 1.1 mg/kg), phosphorus (961 ± 128 mg/kg), potassium (3707 ± 353 mg/kg), selenium (0.1 ± 0.01 mg/kg), and zinc (8.8 ± 1.5 mg/kg). Commercial and wild sourced fiddleheads showed highly variable concentrations of potentially toxic elements (PTEs), such as lead (0.04 – 0.39 mg/kg) and cadmium (0.02 – 0.56 mg/kg). This study will allow local foragers to review the risks and benefits of fiddlehead consumption from the study area.

097

INVESTIGATING GENE DYSREGULATIONS ASSOCIATED WITH ANTIFUNGAL RESISTANCE IN *C. ALBICANS* STRAINS FROM NORTHERN ONTARIOYamamah A. Al-Jumaili*¹, Karolina Czajka², Anu Nair¹, Michael Reich¹, Jessica Dougherty¹, Krishnan Venkataraman¹, Danielle Brabant-Kirwan³, Stacey A Santi⁴, Chris Verschoor^{2,4}, Vasu D Appanna¹, Ravi Singh³, Deborah P Saunders^{2,4}, Sujeenthara Tharmalingam²¹Laurentian University, Sudbury, Ontario, Canada²Northern Ontario School of Medicine University, Sudbury, Ontario, Canada³Health Sciences North, Sudbury, Ontario, Canada⁴Health Sciences North Research Institute, Sudbury, Ontario, Canada

Oral candidiasis is one of the most common fungal infections in the oral cavity of humans. It is caused by the overgrowth of naturally occurring *Candida* fungal species in the oropharynx and debilitates a wide range of the population, most commonly the immunocompromised and elderly. A recurring issue in treating these infections is that many species of interest have varying levels of resistance to antifungal treatments. We hypothesize that genes related to the ergosterol biosynthesis pathway, a target for the antifungals, are upregulated in resistant *Candida* strains. Therefore, the objective of this study is to identify gene dysregulations associated with antifungal resistance in *C. albicans* strains from Northern Ontario. Cultures obtained from oral samples of patients were grown in lab with and without common antifungals such as fluconazole and clotrimazole. Samples were collected at mid-log growth phase. RNA extraction was performed, followed by cDNA synthesis and RT-qPCR (real-time polymerase chain reaction) in order to determine expression levels of genes involved in the ergosterol biosynthesis pathway. This approach will allow measurements of gene expression changes related to antifungal resistance. Preliminary data show that common strains isolated from candidiasis patients in Northern Ontario are resistant to azole treatment. This study will strengthen our understanding of the molecular mechanisms underlying antifungal resistance.

098

FORENSICALLY IMPORTANT INSECTS IN FORESTS OF GREATER SUDBURY: INVESTIGATING IMPLICATIONS FOR FORENSIC ENTOMOLOGYBroglia Lorrana
Algoma University

Forensic Pathology, the analysis and investigation of a non-natural or suspicious death, requires the identification of the PMI (Post-Mortem Interval) of a deceased person. The PMI determines the amount of time that has passed since an individual's death. Forensic Entomology has been a leading method of analysis in determining PMI, via studying the development and success of entomological activity upon the deceased. In Greater Sudbury, the regreening program aims to restore biodiversity to lands degraded by historical mining and smelting activities. This research seeks to assess the prevalence and success of forensically relevant insect species in various forest fragments across Greater Sudbury, exploring how mining activities and regreening efforts have influenced entomological biodiversity in these areas. Insects have been collected using homemade traps baited with liver to attract forensically relevant species. These traps were placed near three mining areas: Coniston Hydro Road (near the previous site of the Mond Nickel Company), Falconbridge (near Glencore Canada), and Ruisseau Nolin Creek (near the Vale Copper Cliff Complex), as well as a site far from mining, near Laurentian University. The traps have remained in the field for three weeks, with samples collected every four days. Collected insects have then been sorted, pinned, and identified to the familial level. Data on species diversity and abundance have been compiled into tables, and diversity indices sourced from such have been calculated. Statistical analyses will explore patterns across the sampling sites. Such will display the variations in communities among the sampled areas, providing insights into the impact of mining and regreening efforts on forensically important insects.

099

ISOLATION AND QUANTIFICATION OF LIPID POLYESTERS IN THE WET STIGMAS OF NICOTIANA TABACUMDiya Prajapati*¹, Richard Bourgault, and Isabel Molina.

Department of Biology, Algoma University, Sault Ste. Marie, Ontario, Canada P6A 2G4

The wet stigma possesses a sticky secretion, known as stigmatic exudate, on its outermost surface that traps pollen. These exudates act as a water reservoir and may contain essential macromolecules including lipids. Previous studies have shown that the exudate of *Nicotiana tabacum* stigma contains 7.4% lipids, which aids in pollen tube development. Tobacco exudate contains lipid estolides (polyesters) that are end-capped with unsubstituted fatty acids (nFA); the estolide bond is an ester between a fatty acid and the hydroxyl group (ω -HFA) of another fatty acid (nFA). These estolides are esterified to glycerol forming triacylglycerides (TAG_n) and diacylglycerides (DAG_n); free fatty acid estolides (FFA_n) and membrane polar lipids (PL_n) are also present (n=number of estolide bonds). This thesis focused on quantifying total lipid polyesters and isolating their four components: TAG_n, DAG_n, FFA_n, and PL_n and further quantifying these components across the seven tobacco flower developmental stages. After lipid extraction from stigmas, thin layer chromatography was performed to isolate the components; depolymerization and transmethylation was then performed to quantify lipids through gas chromatography. The results were consistent with the previous studies that showed that total lipid polyesters quantity increased across the developmental stages, and the ω -HFA increased across the stages indicating an increase in the length of lipid polyesters as stigma develops. The quantification of the four lipid components is underway. This thesis provides an accurate quantification of lipid polyesters in developing tobacco stigmas, a foundational knowledge required to interpret radioisotope labeling experiments that are being conducted in our laboratory.

100

HOW DOES WHITE-THROATED SPARROW SONG LENGTH VARY ACROSS SINGING CONTEXTS

Ruth Ogiri* and Jennifer Foote.

Department of Biology, Algoma University, Sault Ste. Marie, Ontario, Canada P6A 2G4

Song length is one feature of bird song that may vary and may contain important information about individual quality. Birds may also vary their song length depending on the intended receiver or social context. For example, longer songs may be used in long-range advertisement but shorter songs in close territorial contests. In this study, we examined the daily and seasonal song length patterns of the White-Throated Sparrow (*Zonotrochia albicollis*) in Ontario, Canada over two breeding seasons. We used autonomous recorders to record from dusk through 4h after sunrise a day from May to June. We visualized songs in Raven Pro and selected clear songs without overlap and measured song length. Song length peaked earlier in the breeding season and declined with increasing calendar day, suggesting that longer songs may function in mate attraction. Song lengths were significantly shorter at dawn and in the morning than at dusk and night while songs at night were significantly longer than at dusk. Longer songs later in the day may be shaped by predation pressure if it is safer to sing longer at dusk/night when predators are not active. Alternatively, there may be improved sound transmission at dusk and night when fewer species are singing. Overall, this study provides the first quantitative description of the effects of time of day, time of year, and social context on song length in this species.

101

DOES SPRING LEAF OUT TIMING AND VINCA MINOR INVASION REDUCE ARBUSCULAR MYCORRHIZAL FUNGAL ABUNDANCE?

Amna Arif* and Pedro M. Antunes

Department of Biology, Algoma University, Sault Ste. Marie, Ontario, Canada, P6A 2G4

Vinca minor is an invasive plant species introduced to Canada as an ornamental, now threatening biodiversity by forming dense ground cover in forest understories. This species establishes mutualistic relationships with arbuscular mycorrhizal (AM) fungi, which are essential for soil nutrient cycling and plant health. Climate change has altered the timing of spring leaf-out in deciduous forests, potentially influencing competitive interactions among plants by modifying light availability. However, its impact on AM fungal associations in understory plant communities remains poorly understood. We investigated the effects of altered leaf-out timing and *V. minor* invasion on AM fungal abundance in an understory deciduous plant community using a controlled mesocosm experiment. Specifically, AM fungal abundance was assessed by measuring extra-radical soil hyphal length, an indicator of fungal colonization and nutrient exchange potential. The results showed no significant effect of either shade timing or *V. minor* presence on fungal abundance. These findings suggest that AM fungal associations are tolerant to shifts in canopy phenology and invasive plant encroachment, at least in the short-term and under controlled conditions. However, further research is needed to explore potential long-term ecosystem impacts, including on belowground microbial communities, nutrient cycling, and forest regeneration processes.

102

LIPID POLYESTER PROFILING IN STIGMAS OF TOBACCO (*NICOTIANA TABACUM*) MUTANTS

Kumar Pokharel*, Richard Bourgault, Deborah Buhlers, and Isabel Molina

Department of Biology, Algoma University, Sault Ste. Marie, Ontario, Canada, P6A 2G4

Plants produce extracellular lipid polyesters that modify cell walls and contribute to structural integrity and protection. While cutin, the lipid polyester of the plant cuticle, is an insoluble polymer of glycerol and hydroxy fatty acids, *Nicotiana tabacum* stigmas secrete an exudate rich in soluble lipid polyesters that are structurally similar to cutin. Although cutin biosynthesis has been extensively studied, stigma lipid polyester synthesis remains poorly understood. Our lab has analyzed the transcriptomes of developing tobacco stigmas and identified candidate genes for the biosynthesis of these lipids; many of these are genes known to be important for cutin biosynthesis. Here, we investigate the role of candidate genes of stigma lipid biosynthesis using a mutant approach in tobacco. Transgenic tobacco plants carrying constructs to produce either down- or up-regulation of specific genes were genotyped by PCR, and stigma lipid composition was analyzed by gas chromatography-flame ionization detection (GC-FID) after chemical depolymerization of stigmas. This study aims to elucidate the biosynthetic pathways of stigma polyesters, which has potential applications in biomaterial development, and may provide insights into still unknown steps of cutin biosynthesis.

103

INDIVIDUAL DISTINCTION AND MICROGEOGRAPHIC VARIATION OF BLACK-THROATED GREEN WARBLER (*SETOPHAGA VIRENS*) SONG

Kristian Gapp* and Jennifer Foote

Department of Biology, Algoma University, Sault Ste. Marie, Ontario, Canada, P6A 2G4

Bird song may exhibit microgeographic patterns of variation where songs may be more similar or dissimilar among neighbours than more distant birds. In addition, songs of most birds have been shown to be individually distinctive, even when similar to others. Wood warblers belonging to the *Setophaga* genus have a song system in which songs can be placed into two categories. Type A song is associated with intrasexual functions, being used to signal between males for functions like territory defense. Type B songs in contrast are used for intersexual functions, such as mate attraction from a male. The black-throated green warbler (*S. virens*) is a wood warbler with a repertoire size of two, with one of each type A and B categories. To examine individual distinction and microgeographic patterns of type B song automated recording units were placed in a grid in Sault Ste Marie, Ontario to record black-throated green warbler songs. Recordings were analyzed using Raven Pro to ID individual type B songs and clip the best ten from each individual bird (n=61) to use for measurements. Spectrogram cross correlation was used to examine variation within individuals and between neighbour and non-neighbour groups. Cross correlation scores were significantly different between self, neighbour and non-neighbour groups, with neighbours having slightly but significantly higher cross correlation scores than non-neighbours. This indicates that there may be some sharing of type B song among neighbours in black-throated green warblers at levels greater than chance, in contrast with studies on other wood warbler species that find no microgeographic pattern in type B song.

104

IS PLANT SPECIES DIVERSITY INFLUENCED BY MYCORRHIZAL TYPE AND CLIMATE WARMING IN POST-BURN UNDERSTORIES IN THE ONTARIO BOREAL?Joel Lucenay^{1*}, Stephen Mayor², and Pedro M. Antunes¹¹Department of Biology, Algoma University, Sault Ste. Marie, Ontario, Canada, P6A 2G4²Ontario Forest Research Institute, Sault Ste. Marie, Ontario, Canada, P6A 2E5

In the Canadian Boreal Forest, understory plant communities contribute significantly to overall biodiversity. However, increasing wildfire frequency and rising temperatures are expected to impact these ecosystems. The dominant tree species in a stand can shape understory composition, influencing plant-mycorrhizal associations, which are essential for nutrient exchange between plants and soil. Despite this, the effects of anthropogenic disturbances on these relationships remain poorly understood. This study examined how dominant tree species and temperature changes influence plant community composition and mycorrhizal associations after wildfire. We hypothesized that both factors would drive community structure and fungal associations. Using percent cover data, we assessed understory vegetation in recently burned areas and again one year later. Eight sites were selected within jack pine (*Pinus banksiana*)- and white birch (*Betula papyrifera*)-dominated stands, where plots were subjected to contrasting temperature treatments. Our results showed that plant communities varied by dominant stand type, with white birch forests supporting greater diversity than jack pine stands. In addition, an overwhelming presence of arbuscular mycorrhizae-associating plants were in nearly every plot. However, temperature treatments had no significant effect on plant composition. These findings provide insight into the role of mycorrhizal fungi and climate in post-disturbance forest recovery, offering valuable guidance for forest management in the face of climate change.

105

DO NEIGHBOUR TRAITS PREDICT FLOWERING TIME SHIFTS FOR FOCAL PLANTS WHEN COMPETITORS ARE REMOVED?

Austin McGonegal* and Brandon Schamp

Department of Biology, Algoma University, Sault Ste. Marie, Ontario, Canada, P6A 2G4

Fertilizing plants generally leads to them flowering later, and recent research indicates that neighbour removal has a similar effect. This body of research strongly suggests that competition among plants has the potential to significantly alter a plant's flowering time. In other recent research, we identified that competition intensity was not related to abiotic nutrient availability, suggesting a role for the relative traits of competitors. Here, we identified pairs of target plants of the same species growing close together, for seven target species (15 replicate pairs species). We identified all neighbours for the control target plants, and removed the neighbours of the other nearby target plant by regular clipping. We then recorded flowering time for all target plants throughout the growing season. We also determined species-level functional traits for all plant species (mean of 25 measures per species for maximum height, specific leaf areas). We tested whether the mean difference between the traits of neighbours and those of the target plant predicted the degree to which a target plant shifted in flowering time for neighbour-removal target plants. Plants whose neighbours were removed varied in the degree to which their flowering time shifted; however, shifts were not as pronounced as observed in previous growing seasons. Importantly, the degree to which target plants differed from neighbours in maximum species height and SLA did not predict observed shifts in flowering time.

106

THE EFFECTS OF TREE COMMUNITY AND WATER LEGACY ON SOIL MACROFUNGI FRUITING

David Storms* and Pedro M. Antunes

Department of Biology, Algoma University, Sault Ste. Marie, Ontario, Canada, P6A 2G4

Macrofungi play important and contrasting roles in forest ecosystems depending on their strategy. Ectomycorrhizal (ECM) fungi associate with trees, providing soil nutrients in exchange for photosynthetic sugars, while saprobic fungi act as decomposers. These strategies have contrasting implications for soil carbon sequestration in temperate forests: ECM fungi can contribute to increased soil carbon storage by slowing decomposition, whereas saprotrophic fungi accelerate carbon cycling by decomposing organic matter. These guilds compete for soil resources; however, their reproductive responses to factors such as tree functional diversity and water availability are poorly understood. In this study, we sampled sporocarps weekly during a growing season at an International Diversity Experiment Network with Trees (IDENT) site, which contains plots representing a gradient of tree functional diversity, either subjected to a drought treatment or not. Sporocarps were identified morphologically, dried, and weighed. We found that tree species assemblage and water legacy both had significant effects on sporocarp biomass. In addition, ECM and saprobic fungi produced relatively more biomass in plots that were subjected to long-term drought in previous years. These findings indicate that exposure to drought affects fungal fruiting, possibly leading to community shifts consistent with increased stress tolerance.

107

COMPUTATIONAL ASSESSMENT COMPARING THE STANDARD GENETIC CODE'S ABILITY TO MINIMIZE ERROR ACROSS 54 AMINO ACID PROPERTIES WITH AN OPTIMIZED GENETIC CODE

Taha Cheema, Jaskarn Bola

Department of Biology, McMaster University, Hamilton, Ontario, Canada, L8S 4L8

Various theories have emerged regarding the evolution of the standard genetic code (SGC). The adaptive theory states that the code evolved to minimize the effect of error. This idea is supported by the observation that codons differing by just one nucleotide often encode amino acids with similar biochemical properties—or, in some cases, the same amino acid (Koonin & Novozhilov, 2008). Freeland and Hurst (1998) built on these principles when testing the efficiency of the SGC in minimizing error, using polar requirement as the amino acid property. When comparing with 999999 alternative genetic codes, only one performed better, leading to their famous conclusion that the SGC is “one in a million”. Expanding the scope of their study, here a similar analysis was performed on 54 amino acid properties. Wolfram Mathematica was used as the integrated development environment (IDE) to simulate 9999 alternative genetic codes 10 times for each of the 54 properties, to determine an average ranking of the SGC in comparison to all alternative codes. The SGC ranked the highest among the polar requirement, long-range non-bonding energy (E_l), and unfolding entropy change of chain ($-T\Delta S_c$) amino acid properties. The genetic code that performed most optimally in the original 1998 study was then tested against the 10 properties where the SGC ranked the highest, aiming to explore potential relationships among the most conserved properties.

108

NEUROMUSCULAR JUNCTION MORPHOLOGY IS MODESTLY INFLUENCED THROUGH AMPK ACTIVATION IN AGED MICE

Ricky K Hong*, Andrew I Mikhail, Sean Y Ng, Stephanie R Mattina, Magda Lesinski, Vladimir Ljubcic
Department of Kinesiology, McMaster University, Ontario, Canada L8S 4L8

Introduction: The neuromuscular junction (NMJ) facilitates the electrochemical communication between an α -motor neuron and myofiber that is crucial for the induction of a muscle contraction. Accompanying the age-related loss of muscle mass, i.e., sarcopenia, are deleterious alterations to NMJ morphology. Interventions such as exercise and caloric restriction can ameliorate age-associated deficits at the NMJ due, in part, to the stimulation of upstream proteins that are directly or indirectly regulated by AMP-activated Protein Kinase (AMPK). Hence, the purpose of this study is to investigate the effects of chronic AMPK activation on NMJ morphology and health within aged mice. **Methods:** Old C57BL/6 mice (n = 16) were randomized at 18-months of age to receive either a vehicle (Old-Veh) or 10 mg/kg of body weight of a small molecule AMPK agonist MK8722 (old-MK) every other day for a total of 6-months. The epitrochleoanconus muscle was collected, stained and further analyzed. Young 3-month-old mice served as a healthy control. **Results:** Our preliminary data (n=2-4 per group) demonstrate a significantly greater nerve terminal perimeter ($p < 0.05$) in Old-Veh relative to young mice, which tended to decrease ($p = 0.09$) with MK treatment. Furthermore, we observed a greater number of polyinnervated NMJs, and pre-synaptic branch length in Old-Veh mice only. Age also exacerbated post-synaptic fragmentation ($p < 0.05$) which was partially decreased in old-MK mice. **Conclusion:** This study provides evidence implicating AMPK's role as an influential molecular regulator at the level of the NMJ. Further work is aimed to achieve a full data set to grasp the extent of this relationship.

109

EFFECTS OF PIKFYVE LIPID KINASE INHIBITION ON ENDOPLASMIC RETICULUM IN THE CONTEXT OF ER-REMODELING

Lomiyev, Sharifa*, Jenkins, Nicala, Adamji, Zainab, Almasri, Nourhan, Botelho, Roberto J.
Department of Chemistry and Biology, Toronto Metropolitan University, Toronto, Ontario, Canada M5B 2K3

Lysosomes are important for molecular degradation and regulation of other organelles through membrane contact sites (MCS), including the endoplasmic reticulum (ER), the largest organelle in the cells responsible for protein and lipid synthesis, and calcium signaling. The ER is highly dynamic, constantly changing shape, partly through ER-hitchhiking, a process of ER-remodeling driven by ER-anchoring to motile lysosomes. A key effector of lysosomal dynamics is the kinase PIKfyve, responsible for synthesizing phosphatidylinositol 3,5-bisphosphate. Inhibition of PIKfyve disrupts lysosome shape and dynamics by lysosomal coalescence, reduced motility, and diminished endocytic trafficking and autophagic flux. However, the specific effects of PIKfyve inhibition on lysosomal cross-talk with the ER are unclear. We discovered that PIKfyve inhibition causes a collapsed ER morphology with reduced dynamics and reduced ER hitchhiking. My work aimed to understand these observations by asking if PIKfyve inhibition altered microtubules and contact sites between ER-lysosomes, both needed for ER hitchhiking.

Utilizing high-resolution microscopy of EB1 (a microtubule plus-end marker) and α -tubulin (a standard microtubule marker), we noted that upon PIKfyve inhibition, there are no significant differences in microtubule morphology or dynamics. This suggests that alteration of ER-remodeling via ER-hitchhiking is not influenced by microtubule instability upon PIKfyve inhibition. Given what we discovered, we are utilizing high-resolution microscopy using GCEP1A-ER (an ER-calcium biosensor) to explore the functional consequences of PIKfyve-inhibition on ER-lysosome MCS. Investigating this aims to link lysosomal dysfunction to altered organelle cross-talk and impaired ER functions, offering potential insights for therapeutic intervention in diseases driven by organelle disruption.

Poster Presentation Abstracts

001

USING NOVEL PHYSIOLOGICAL INDICATORS TO DETECT INVESTMENT IN AND TIMING OF BREEDING IN AN ARCTIC-BREEDING SEADUCK.

Emily A. Archambeault*¹, Holly L. Hennin^{1,2}, Chris M. Harris¹, Christina A.D. Semeniuk¹, H. Grant Gilchrist², Oliver P. Love¹

¹University of Windsor, Windsor, ON, Canada, N9B 3P4

²Environment and Climate Change Canada, Ottawa, ON, Canada, K1H 1E1

Life-history investment theory predicts that some individuals may be better at using physiological and behavioural mechanisms to meet the energetic demands from environmental challenges to maximize breeding success. However, field-testing these predictions is complicated by the challenge of quantifying environmentally induced flexibility in mechanisms before breeding investment. Nonetheless, these questions are vital to answer in places such as the Arctic, which is experiencing climate change 3-4 times the global average. Here we use a 16-year dataset from Canada's largest colony of Arctic-breeding common eiders (*Somateria mollissima*), located at East Bay Island, Nunavut, to field-test these investment predictions. Specifically, from 2006-2023, we captured and blood-sampled almost 3000 pre-laying females following arrival on the breeding grounds as birds began fattening and investing in follicle (yolk) recruitment. We then followed individuals to assess two reproductive decisions that impact breeding success: whether birds bred, and if so, when they initiated laying. To answer these questions, I am quantifying levels of vitellogenin (VTG) and plasma estradiol (E2) prior to laying as biomarkers of breeding investment. To quantify the length and timing of this investment period I will explore patterns of VTG, E2, plasma triglycerides, and body mass in relation to lay date. These results will also shed light on whether temporal overlap between fattening and follicle recruitment is possible in this species. Filling in these challenging life history gaps is vital for predicting whether individuals and the populations they make up can persist and succeed in the face of rapidly increasing change in the north.

002

SILK NANOPARTICLE DRUG DELIVERY OF DOUBLE-STRANDED RNA AS AN EPITHELIAL OVARIAN CANCER TREATMENT

Hanna Kusznirewicz*, Samuel Peters, Nirosha Murugan

Department of Health Science Wilfrid Laurier University, Waterloo, Ontario, Canada N2L 3C5

In epithelial ovarian cancer, late detection and limited treatment options contribute to high mortality rates. Common applications of platinum-based chemotherapy are ineffective due to chemo-resistance and cumulative toxic effects from the platinum. This research project investigates the use of silk nanoparticles (sNPs) as a potentially safer drug delivery system for double-stranded RNA (dsRNA) in ovarian cancer cells in order to observe the treatment's potential cytotoxic effects. dsRNA has shown promise in triggering a caspase-dependent apoptotic response, while sNPs are noted for their biocompatibility and low toxicity. Given that sNPs naturally exhibit a negative charge, they will be modified to carry a positive charge to facilitate binding with dsRNA. The methodology of this project entails that the liquid silk, derived from *Bombyx mori* silk cocoons, is processed via nanoprecipitation. The size and size distribution of the sNPs is analyzed using a dynamic light scattering technique. Cytotoxicity will be assessed by comparing cell viability following treatments with free dsRNA, unloaded sNPs (negative control), modified sNPs (control), and dsRNA-coated sNPs, using an Alamar Blue assay. This project is expected to provide further insight into dsRNA-based therapies and understanding the efficacy of silk nanoparticles as a drug delivery system. These findings could inform future cancer-related clinical strategies, offering a novel approach to ovarian cancer treatments and potentially other cancer types as well.

003

MELANIN'S IMPACT ON CHEMOTHERAPY EFFICACY IN LUMINAL A BREAST CANCER

Vanessa Vashishth*¹, and Nirosha J. Murugan¹

¹Wilfrid Laurier University, Waterloo, Ontario, Canada, N2L 3C5

Luminal A breast cancer is the most common subtype of breast cancer, known for its favorable prognosis due to its lower expression of genes associated with cell proliferation. However, its resistance to chemotherapy, particularly doxorubicin, poses a challenge in treatment. This study investigates the potential of melanin, specifically synthetic eumelanin, to enhance the efficacy of doxorubicin in treating Luminal A breast cancer. Melanin is known for its antioxidant properties and ability to protect against oxidative stress, and recent advancements have shown promise in using melanin in drug delivery and cancer therapy. This study examines whether combining doxorubicin with melanin can reduce the necessary chemotherapy dosage while improving cancer cell death and minimizing side effects brought upon by treatment. The study will utilize MCF7 cells, a well-established Luminal A breast cancer cell line, and assess the effects of a combination treatment on cell proliferation and viability. The hypothesis driving this research is that melanin will enhance doxorubicin's ability to induce cancer cell death while reducing proliferation rates, compared to chemotherapy alone. This study aims to provide insight into whether melanin could serve as an adjunct to conventional chemotherapy, potentially improving treatment outcomes and offering a strategy to overcome chemotherapy resistance in Luminal A breast cancer. By investigating melanin's interaction with chemotherapy, this research has the potential to lead to more effective, targeted therapies, improving survival rates, reducing relapse, and enhancing the quality of life, thus contributing to the advancement of precision medicine in oncology.

004

SPATIAL GENE EXPRESSION PATTERNS OF DIGESTIVE CYSTEINE PROTEASES IN *TETRANYCHUS URTICAE*

Eric Deaconu*¹, Zoran Culo¹, Vinayak Singh¹, Vojislava Grbic¹

¹Department of Biology, University of Western Ontario, 1151 Richmond St., London, Ontario, Canada N6A 3K7

The two-spotted spider mite, *Tetranychus urticae*, is a highly polyphagous agricultural pest capable of feeding on over 1,100 plant species. Central to its adaptability and extreme generalism is a robust digestive system, in which cysteine proteases are proposed to facilitate intracellular digestion. This study investigates the spatial gene expression patterns of selected cathepsin L and B family digestive cysteine proteases in the *T. urticae* midgut, focusing on their role in the proposed intracellular digestive processes taking place within free-floating digestive cells, and their potential preloading in midgut generative epithelial cells, in advance of digestive cell budding. Using *in situ* hybridization, we mapped the localization of the selected cathepsin L, *TuPap-41*, and selected cathepsin B, *TuPap-9*, across the *T. urticae* midgut cells. Our findings reveal that the selected cathepsin L is expressed in generative cells with an apparent patterning in expression over the midgut generative epithelia, perhaps indicative of preloading in advance of digestive cell budding, supporting the hypothesis that digestive cells are preloaded with digestive enzymes before entering the gut lumen. In contrast, the selected cathepsin B appears to be predominantly expressed in generative cells, though without the distinct organization observed with the selected cathepsin L. Additionally, we observed potential expression of the selected cathepsin B within other midgut cell types, suggesting further non-digestive roles. These findings demonstrate functional differentiation among digestive cysteine proteases in *T. urticae*, and improve the understanding of the proposed *T. urticae* intracellular digestive mechanism.

005

EVALUATING DIMETHOATE RESISTANCE OF SPIDER MITE POPULATIONS FROM SOUTHWESTERN ONTARIO SOYBEAN CROPS.

Alexandria Ojha^{*1}, Joseane Moreira do Nascimento¹, Reagan Michiels¹, Mikaelison da Silva Lima¹, Kristie Adriana Bruinsma¹, Tracey Baute³, Ian Scott², Vojislava Grbic¹

¹Department of Biology, University of Western Ontario, 1151 Richmond St, London, Ontario, Canada N6A 3K7

²London Research and Development Centre, Agriculture and Agri-Food Canada (AAFC), 1391 Sandford St, London, Ontario, Canada N5V 4T3

³Ontario Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Rural Affairs (OMAFRA), 120 Main Street East, Ridgeway, Ontario, Canada N0P 2C0

Tetranychus urticae (Koch) (Acari: Tetranychidae) is an extreme generalist spider mite that is highly resistant to acaricides and severely threatens economically important crops. Due to its ability to rapidly adapt to chemical controls, it is crucial to evaluate the effectiveness of currently available products, such as dimethoate—the only registered acaricide for spider mite control in Ontario soybean fields. Dimethoate is an organophosphate (OP) which is an acetylcholinesterase (AChE) inhibitor that functions by preventing the hydrolysis of acetylcholine. This leads to its accumulation in the synaptic cleft, disrupting neural transmission, and ultimately causing paralysis and death in mites. This project aims to evaluate dimethoate resistance in eight spider mite populations from Southwestern Ontario soybean fields and to develop a streamlined molecular approach for resistance detection in comparison to conducting laborious toxicity bioassays. The molecular analysis focused on the AChE gene. All populations were screened for known target-site mutations (G119S, A201S, T280A, G328A and F331W/C/Y) using Sanger sequencing, AChE expression levels were quantified using RT-qPCR, and copy number variation was assessed using q-PCR. For the toxicity bioassays, mites were placed on leaf discs treated with dimethoate (50 ppm) or water (control), to assess adult mortality. The data from the bioassays demonstrated that four of the eight populations are resistant to dimethoate, and the molecular analysis is still in progress. These results highlight the importance of assessing dimethoate's effectiveness against spider mite populations and developing efficient, reliable methods to detect resistance.

006

INVESTIGATING THE ROLE OF UGD IN *SHIGELLA FLEXNERI* POLYMYXIN B RESISTANCE THROUGH PMRAB-DEPENDENT REGULATORY SYSTEM

Daniel Bekele^{*1}, Joseph McPhee¹

Department of Chemistry and Biology, Toronto Metropolitan University, Toronto, Ontario, Canada M5B 2K3

Shigella flexneri has undergone genetic inactivation of key regulatory genes, including PmrD and PmrAB, which are responsible for lipopolysaccharide (LPS) modifications crucial for resistance to cationic antimicrobial peptides. In *Escherichia coli*, PmrD links the PhoPQ and pmrAB systems and mediates LPS modifications in response to magnesium and iron levels. In *S. flexneri*, under conditions of high magnesium, which inactivates PhoPQ, and high iron, activating PmrAB, we have observed partial resistance to polymyxin B, suggesting residual PmrAB activity still mediates some protective modifications. However, the loss of *ugd*, a downstream gene regulated by PmrAB that is required to make the 4-aminoarabinose modification, may limit the extent of resistance. We plan to investigate this by restoring *ugd* function in *S. flexneri* and assessing its role in PmrAB-dependent polymyxin B resistance. This will be explored using minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) assays to quantify resistance levels and killing assays to evaluate bacteria survival under antimicrobial stress. These findings will further elucidate the genetic determinants of antibiotic resistance in *Shigella* and their broader implications for bacterial pathogenesis.

007

BIOMECHANICAL ANALYSIS OF FORCE PRODUCTION AND SKATING EFFICIENCY IN FEMALE VARSITY HOCKEY PLAYERS

Veronica Langdon¹, Nick Westcott², Jeff Dawson¹, Iain McKinnell¹

¹Department of Biology, Carleton University, Ottawa, Ontario, Canada K1S 5B6

²Recreation and Athletics, Carleton University, Ottawa, Ontario, Canada K1S 5B6

In high-demand sports like ice hockey, optimizing biomechanics and physical performance is crucial for on-ice success. Female athletes have unique anatomical, biomechanical, and physiological differences compared to males, however, the majority of research in this field has focused on male athletes, leaving a gap in understanding the specific needs of female hockey players. This study investigates the relationship between anthropometric factors, force production capabilities, and skating performance in female varsity hockey players. Using countermovement jump (CMJ) performance as a key indicator of lower-body power, we examine its relationship with on-ice speed and efficiency. Given the structural and neuromuscular differences between male and female athletes, this research aims to provide gender-specific insights for improving training strategies. By integrating biomechanical assessments with anthropometric data, our findings will contribute to developing tailored conditioning programs that enhance performance for female hockey players.

008

THE EFFECT OF TNF ON DENSITY AND MORPHOLOGY OF MICROGLIA IN THE CA1 REGION OF THE BRAIN.

Alizée Fieffé-Bédard^{*,1,2}, Braeden Cowbrough^{1,2}, Sofya Ermolina^{1,2}, Erica DeJong^{1,2}, Dr. Dawn Bowdish^{1,2}

¹McMaster Immunology Research Center, Hamilton, Ontario, Canada, L8N 3Z5. ²Firestone Institute of Respiratory Health, St. Joseph's Healthcare, Hamilton, Ontario, Canada, L8N 1Y2.

Microglia play an active role in the central nervous system, they are involved in synaptic pruning, neurogenesis, crosstalk with other glial and modulating the immune response. With age, microglia show both an altered morphology and inflammatory profile leading to an overactive microglia population that has been linked with cognitive decline. Within the CA1 region of the brain, linked to memory consolidation and spatial reasoning, microglia are known to increase in density with age. One pro-inflammatory cytokine shown to activate microglia is TNF which serves as a major regulator of many immune processes. TNF stimulation increases microglia proliferation, induces increased phagocytosis and increases neuron pruning. We hypothesize that microglia from TNF-deficient mice (TNFKO) will have lower microglia density as well as reduced somas and larger arborization compared to wild-type (WT) mice. We compared images taken from the CA1 region of TNF KO and WT mice brains that were stained with Iba1 and TMEM119 to examine the difference in microglia morphology and density. We found that TNF KO mice had a lower microglia density but no significant differences in morphology. The next steps of the project will be to isolate microglia from whole brains using a mojosort kit. The success of the Mojosort kit was measured by Flow Cytometry. The microglia will be stimulated with TNF and cytokine levels (IL-6, IL-1 β and IL-10) will be measured with ELISA assays. We hope that these results will help elucidate the long term effects of exposure to TNF on microglia.

009

THE ROLE OF A FLUORESCENT WBOX2 PEPTIDE IN CLATHRIN MEDIATED ENDOCYTOSIS: ASSESING SPECIFICITY WITH

Ornella M. Shaikovsky, BSc Student ¹, Natalie Uzynski, MSc Student¹, Costin Antonescu, PhD¹, Eden Fussner-Dupas PhD²

¹Department of Chemistry and Biology, Toronto Metropolitan University, Toronto, Ontario, M5B 2K3

²Department of Biochemistry and Molecular Biology, University of British Columbia, Vancouver, British Columbia, V6T 1Z3

Clathrin-mediated endocytosis (CME) is a critical pathway for cellular uptake, enabling the internalization of surface proteins through clathrin-coated pits (CCPs). This study explores the specificity of Ikarugamycin (IKA) as an inhibitor of CME by evaluating its potential to displace the Wbox2 peptide, a clathrin-binding marker that facilitates the study of clathrin recruitment dynamics, from CCPs. The Wbox2 peptide was engineered with a TAT sequence to facilitate cellular entry and an HA detection tag for visualization, allowing for precise tracking within ARPE-19 cells. The methodology involves incubating cells with the TAT-Wbox2 peptide, confirming recruitment to CCPs using Total Internal Reflection Fluorescence (TIRF) microscopy. Following localization verification, IKA is introduced to determine its ability to displace the peptide from CCPs. Quantification of fluorescence signals will provide a measure of peptide displacement, enabling an assessment of IKA's specificity as a CME inhibitor. It is anticipated that IKA significantly reduces peptide localization within CCPs, indicating that it effectively disrupts clathrin recruitment. This would support IKA's potential as a selective inhibitor of clathrin-mediated endocytosis, offering valuable insights into its feasibility for therapeutic applications targeting endocytic pathways.

010

DOES MICROBIAL FUNCTION VARY WITH STREAM HEALTH? COMPARISON OF DON RIVER AND EAST HUMBER TRIBUTARIES WITH POOR TO GOOD QUALITY CONDITIONS.

Amasha Malawiya Arachchige*

Department of Chemistry and Biology, Toronto Metropolitan University, Toronto, Ontario, Canada M5B 2K3

The Don River, located in Toronto, Ontario, is situated in a highly urbanized area, contributing to its 96% urbanization. Combined sewer overflows (CSOs) and effluent from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) contribute to approximately 51% of the Don River's flow, significantly impacting its pollution levels. Biofilm serves as an important bioindicator of pollution in aquatic ecosystems; its community structure adapts to increased pollution by favoring more tolerant species, thereby altering its metabolic functional diversity. This study aimed to assess the water quality of various Don River tributaries, including the heavily polluted Taylor-Massey Creek and the relatively healthy East Humber River. Two of the sampling sites were located upstream and downstream of the North Toronto Treatment Plant (NTTP), an area known for frequent CSO events. These sites were evaluated to determine whether pollution from CSOs or improperly treated effluent is affecting water quality. A microbial metabolic fingerprint of each site was generated using Biolog EcoPlates™, providing insight into the metabolic rate and community structure of the biofilm. Additional water quality parameters, such as nitrate and chloride concentrations, were also measured to further assess stream health. Initial results suggest that the metabolic rates across most sites are similar, potentially indicating consistent pollution levels and metabolic functional diversity among the tributaries. Furthermore, the sites upstream and downstream of the NTTP exhibited comparable metabolic functional diversity, which may suggest that CSOs or WWTP effluent are not contributing significant additional pollution to these areas.

011

REGULATION OF GSK3 β IN NUTRIENT STARVATION AND CELLULAR DIFFERENTIATION VIA CLATHRIN-MEDIATED LYSOSOMAL PATHWAYS

Sophia Anazia*¹, Rebecca Cabral-Dias^{1,2}, Laura A Orofiamma^{1,2}, Ayshin Mehrabi¹, Diana S Forkel^{1,2}, Costin N Antonescu^{1,2,3}

¹Department of Chemistry and Biology, ²Graduate Program in Molecular Science, Toronto Metropolitan University, Toronto Ontario, Canada, M5B 2K3, ³Keenan Research Centre for Biomedical Science of St. Michael's Hospital, Toronto, Ontario, Canada, M5B 1W8

Cells continuously adapt to nutrient availability, relying on tightly regulated signalling pathways to control survival and differentiation. Glycogen Synthase Kinase 3 β (GSK3 β) plays a key role in these processes, with its nuclear-cytoplasmic localization influencing transcriptional regulation. However, the mechanisms governing its trafficking remain unclear. This study investigates how clathrin-mediated endocytosis (CME) regulates lysosomal function and, in turn, GSK3 β localization. Lysosomes are critical for controlling GSK3 β 's nuclear export, and clathrin is essential for maintaining lysosomal integrity. Disrupting clathrin function alters lysosomal morphology, leading to enlarged lysosomes fragmenting into smaller vesicles, ultimately affecting GSK3 β localization. Using Ikarugamycin, a clathrin inhibitor, we examine its impact on lysosome dynamics and the subsequent mislocalization of GSK3 β . Methanol fixation enables precise imaging of these interactions under nutrient-rich and nutrient-deprived (EBSS media) conditions. By comparing GSK3 β localization across different nutrient environments and clathrin inhibition conditions, this study aims to clarify how lysosomes regulate nuclear-cytoplasmic shuttling. These findings will provide insights into the role of clathrin in lysosomal homeostasis and its broader implications for nutrient sensing and cellular differentiation.

012

TIME-OF-DAY DIFFERENCES IN CELL COMPOSITION IN CHRONIC PAIN

Christina Meier*¹, Amanda Zacharias², Courtney A. Bannerman², Jaqueline Raymondi Silva², Robert Colautti¹, Qingling Duan^{2,3}, and Nader Ghasemlou^{2,4}.

¹Department of Biology, ²Department of Biomedical and Molecular Sciences, ³Queens School of Computing, ⁴Department of Anesthesiology, Queen's University, Kingston, Ontario, Canada

Chronic pain is caused by damage to the nervous system. Although highly prevalent, it lacks effective treatment options. Circadian rhythms are roughly 24-hour cycles in biological processes that have been observed in the pain sensitivity of both mice and humans. Understanding why pain follows these rhythms could provide new insights into the development and persistence of chronic pain. The dorsal root ganglia (DRG) and spinal cord (SC) are key structures in the nervous system that contribute to the initiation and maintenance of this pain. Throughout the pain signaling pathway, neurons constantly communicate with immune cells, including microglia, macrophages, and astrocytes, to mediate pain sensitivity. A computational approach called cell deconvolution was used to estimate the proportions of different cell types in heterogeneous samples of DRG and SC tissue in a model of chronic pain (spared nerve injury (SNI)). This study aims to 1) compare cell type compositions in naive and SNI conditions in the DRG and SC, and 2) explore how cell type compositions in the DRG and SC vary across the day-night cycle. Cell type compositions in the DRG and SC differed significantly between naive and SNI conditions ($p < 0.05$). Notable differences were also observed in LDA axes between day and night sample groups. These findings show that further characterization of rhythmicity in the DRG and SC is needed, which may lead to novel therapeutic options for treating chronic pain.

013

IDENTIFYING AND EXPRESSING PIP-BOXES AND HRP-BOXES UPSTREAM OF T3SEs IN XANTHOMONAS AND PSEUDOMONAS GENOMES

Brianna Tapia*², Viplav Agarwal², and Marcus M. Dillon^{1,2}

¹Department of Ecology and Evolutionary Biology, University of Toronto, Toronto, Ontario, Canada M5S 3B2

²Department of Biology, University of Toronto Mississauga, Mississauga, Ontario, Canada L5L 1C6

Bacterial plant pathogens such as *Xanthomonas* and *Pseudomonas* utilize the Type III Secretion System (T3SS) to inject effector proteins (T3SEs) into host cells, manipulating plant immunity and promoting infection. The expression of these effectors is regulated by conserved promoter elements, including Pip-Boxes in *Xanthomonas* and Hrp-Boxes in *Pseudomonas*. However, the ability of these regulatory elements to control horizontally transferred effectors across genera remains poorly understood. This study aims to determine whether *Pseudomonas* T3SEs can be expressed in *Xanthomonas* and vice versa, and whether these effectors retain the ability to trigger Effector-Triggered Immunity (ETI) in host plants. To address these questions, bioinformatics analysis using R was performed to identify Pip-Boxes and Hrp-Boxes upstream of T3SE genes across multiple *Xanthomonas* and *Pseudomonas* genomes. Motif searches and Position Weight Matrices (PWMs) were used to detect conserved sequences, followed by sequence alignment and phylogenetic analysis to evaluate evolutionary conservation. Cloning experiments involved inserting effector genes into the broad-host-range plasmid pBBR1-MCS-2, which was subsequently introduced into recipient strains via triparental mating (TPM). Successful transconjugants were selected using antibiotic resistance markers.

Effector expression will be confirmed in future experiments through spray assays conducted on *Arabidopsis thaliana* and followed up with Western blot analysis. This study enhances our understanding of regulatory mechanisms governing T3SE expression and their potential for functional conservation across bacterial genera, contributing insights into pathogen evolution and plant disease management.

014

IMPACT OF SERT KNOCKOUT ON SURFACING BEHAVIOUR IN *DANIO RERIO*

Ben Harrison*, Michael Tea and Kathleen Gilmour

University of Ottawa, 75 Laurier Ave E, Ottawa, ON K1N 6N5

Serotonin transporters (*sert*) reuptake serotonin from the synapse within the brain. Zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) express two *sert* paralogues (*serta* and *sertb*) which are not co-expressed in the brain. Zebrafish lacking functional expression of *serta*, *sertb*, and both paralogues were generated using CRISPR-Cas9 technology. The *sertb*-knockout (KO) zebrafish exhibited surfacing behaviour in which they remain near the surface of the water without any environmental stimulus. The pathways underlying surfacing behaviour are unknown. Previous studies have linked higher tank region preference to an anxiolytic phenotype. Similarly, we show through the novel tank dive test that larval *sertb*-KOs and *sert*-KOs exhibited increased surface preference relative to wild-types. We asked whether surfacing behaviour is a result of visual differences because serotonin accumulation is known to lead to changes in the visual system and the zebrafish retina expresses only *Sertb*. To assess both responses to light, as well as anxiety, locomotion was measured in an open field test under light and dark conditions, and a scototaxis test was performed to determine whether time spent under light versus dark conditions differed across genotypes. Differences in activity between genotypes may provide insight into the role of serotonin signalling in surfacing behaviour.

015

INVESTIGATING THE IMPACTS OF REPLICATION STRESS UPON WILD-TYPE AND GSK3 β MDA-MB-231 CELLS IN PRESENCE AND ABSENCE OF PYRUVATE

Shruti Manna*, Cindy Ong and Sarah A. Sabatinos

Department of Chemistry and Biology, Toronto Metropolitan University, Toronto, Ontario, Canada, M5B 2K3

Breast cancer is the most diagnosed cancer among women. Glycogen synthase kinase 3 (GSK3) is a serine/threonine kinase that regulates cell metabolism and growth. GSK3 β plays a role in breast cancer development and is studied for its role in the β -catenin/Wnt signalling pathway. Our lab's recent work found that GSK3 loss in TNBC cells may alter drug sensitivity and that these values are sensitive to the pyruvate present in the medium. Pyruvate is produced via glycolysis and feeds into the Krebs Cycle for energy production. This study examines how DNA replication instability drugs impact GSK3 β + and GSK3 β -knockout TNBC cells in the presence and absence of pyruvate. We tested chemotherapeutic drug doses required to inhibit TNBC cell line MDA-MB-231 growth. This includes the drug gemcitabine, which causes an S phase arrest in cells by acting as a nucleoside analogue to halt DNA replication. We used the cell counting kit reagent CCK8 to monitor proliferation in GSK3 β + or knockout cells in the presence/absence of pyruvate and under DNA replication stress drugs. The half-maximal inhibitory concentrations (IC50) for replication stress drugs differed in the absence of pyruvate. Further, the nuclear area of MDA-MB-231 cells changes when exposed to gemcitabine in various conditions (GSK3 β knockout; without pyruvate). Our data shows that TNBC cells' sensitivity to chemotherapeutic agents depends on external metabolites and the metabolic regulation of energy by GSK3 β . This reinforces work showing that tumour starvation alters the response to drugs and that DNA replication stress is sensitive to metabolic signalling.

016

EVOLVED CHANGES IN PULMONARY VASCULAR FUNCTION IN HIGH-ALTITUDE DEER MICE

Jessica C. Yemen*¹, Kayla M. Garvey¹, Graham R. Scott¹

¹*Department of Biology, McMaster University, Hamilton Ontario, Canada*

High-altitude environments present extreme challenges for endotherms, including severe cold and low oxygen availability, which impact cardiorespiratory function and aerobic metabolism. Hypoxic pulmonary hypertension (HPH) is a debilitating condition that occurs in low-altitude humans, other mammals, and birds that travel to high altitude. In mammals, HPH results from pulmonary vasoconstriction and arterial remodeling in response to hypoxia, increasing blood pressure and cardiac workload, which can lead to edema and, in severe cases, death. Prior research suggests that high-altitude deer mice (*Peromyscus maniculatus*) exhibit an attenuated HPH response compared to low-altitude conspecifics. Here, we investigated whether evolved changes in pulmonary vascular function mitigate HPH in high-altitude mice. Deer mice from high- and low-altitude populations were born and raised to adulthood in captivity, then acclimated for >6 weeks to either warm normoxia (25°C, 20 kPa O₂) or cold hypobaric hypoxia (5°C, 12 kPa O₂). *Ex vivo* wire myography was used to evaluate vascular sensitivity to low oxygen (1% O₂, 5% CO₂, 94% N₂) and to stimulation of alpha-adrenergic receptors (phenylephrine), beta-adrenergic receptors (isoproterenol), and endothelium-derived nitric oxide (acetylcholine). Among normoxic mice, preliminary results indicate that highlanders exhibit reduced sensitivity to the vasoconstricting effects of phenylephrine and increased sensitivity to the vasodilating effects isoproterenol and acetylcholine as compared to lowlanders. These findings suggest that evolved changes in adrenergic receptor sensitivity may promote vasodilation in pulmonary vessels and avoid maladaptive HPH in high-altitude deer mice. Supported by NSERC.

017

ELEVATED DIRECT BILIRUBIN DOES NOT PREDICT ELEVATED CONJUGATED BILIRUBIN IN NEONATES

Pooja Samaraweera*^{1,2}, Herbert Brill²,

¹Toronto Metropolitan University

²William Osler Health System

Neonatal cholestasis, characterized by elevated conjugated bilirubin, is a serious condition requiring prompt identification and treatment. Current guidelines use direct bilirubin, which includes both conjugated and delta bilirubin, as a proxy for conjugated bilirubin. However, this equivalence has not been well established. This study evaluated whether direct bilirubin accurately reflects conjugated bilirubin levels in neonates and assessed its utility as a reliable screening tool for neonatal cholestasis. A retrospective analysis was conducted on data from neonates under three months old at William Osler Health System, from 2015 to 2024, with direct bilirubin levels of 20 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ or higher, where samples were sent for conjugated bilirubin testing. Results demonstrated no significant correlation between direct and conjugated bilirubin levels, especially when direct bilirubin was below 22 $\mu\text{mol/L}$, and showed no significant differences in the rate of further investigations based on direct versus conjugated bilirubin ($\chi^2 = 0.0719$, $p = 0.7887$). These findings suggest that direct bilirubin is not a reliable proxy for conjugated bilirubin and may lead to unnecessary investigations. Future research should compare these results with historical data to refine neonatal bilirubin testing protocols and improve clinical decision-making in neonatal care.

018

THE ROLE OF ADAPTOR PROTEIN COMPLEXES IN PHAGOCYTOSIS OF OPSONIZED PARTICLES.

Alacea Yerxa*¹, Melanie Mansat², Muhammad Butt², Roberto J. Botelho^{1,2}

¹Department of Chemistry and Biology, Toronto Metropolitan University, Toronto, Ontario, Canada, M5B 2K3.

²Toronto Metropolitan University MaRS Biomedical Research Facility, MaRS Discovery District, Toronto, Ontario, Canada, M5G 1M1.

Immune cells called macrophages play a major role in eliminating dangerous particles like microbes through phagocytosis. Phagocytosis encompasses several stages: recognition and engulfment of target particle into a phagosome, phagosome maturation (particle digestion), and phagosome resolution to recycle phagosomal membrane. Each stage of phagocytosis requires key proteins. Phagosome formation requires clathrin, a protein characterized for its role in endocytosis and recently, phagosome resolution. Clathrin depends on adaptor protein (AP) complexes to select cargo and assemble onto membranes during fission. There are at least four AP complexes, where AP1 and AP2 associate with the Golgi and plasma membrane. However, AP complexes may work at other sites like endosomes and lysosomes. Since clathrin was found to drive phagosome resolution, this raised the hypothesis that AP complexes could be involved in phagocytosis or subsequent stages. To test this hypothesis, I silenced AP1 or AP2 with siRNA-oligonucleotides against the mu subunit in RAW macrophage cell lines, obtaining 50% protein silencing. After challenging macrophages with non-opsonized *E. coli* or antibody-opsonized polystyrene beads, we observed a significant decreased in uptake of *E. coli* in AP1 or AP2-silenced cells through microscopy. However, phagocytosis of IgG-coated beads was not significantly affected by AP1 or AP2-silencing. These findings suggest AP1 and AP2 may modulate phagocytic uptake in a manner dependent on particles and/or receptor. To expand our understanding, we will measure the levels and recruitment of phagocytic receptors to the plasma membrane, during phagocytosis. Additionally, we will examine the role of AP1 and AP2 in phagosome maturation and resolution.

019

CONCENTRATION DEPENDENT EFFECTS OF BENZALKONIUMCHLORIDES ON FRESHWATER BENTHIC INVERTEBRATE COMMUNITIES

Anastasia Cornea^{1*}, Claire Estey¹, Jose Luis Rodriguez², Lauren Timlick², and Karen Kidd¹

¹McMaster University, Department of Biology, Hamilton, ON, ²International Institute for Sustainable Development, Experimental Lakes Area, Winnipeg, MB

The use of antimicrobials has increased considerably in recent years. Benzalkonium chlorides (BACs) are a common ingredient in non-alcohol-based disinfectants worldwide. After their use in products, most BACs go down the drain and enter municipal wastewater systems. During wastewater treatment, they adsorb to organic molecules which prevents their degradation and facilitates their release into aquatic ecosystems. BACs have shown toxicity to a variety of low-trophic organisms, but the literature lacks *in situ* data on benthic organisms. We investigated the effects of environmentally relevant concentrations of benzalkonium chloride on the makeup of benthic invertebrate communities. We expect to see a decrease in abundance and diversity as BAC concentration increases. In 2023, an eleven-week mesocosm study was conducted at the IISD-Experimental Lakes Area where we compared five environmentally relevant concentrations of BACs (nominal 20, 112, 632, 3556, and 20 000 ng/L, plus three controls of 0 ng/L). Hester-Dendy traps were deployed in each mesocosm and sampled for benthic invertebrate community composition six times over the study. Invertebrates were quantified and identified to the lowest possible taxonomic level. The most common taxa found were from orders Amphipoda and Diptera, with the majority of Diptera represented by the family Chironomidae. Results will help quantify the effects of BACs on the invertebrates that live in the sediment where these compounds tend to adsorb. Shifts in the benthic zone can cause cascading changes, so by identifying concentrations at which invertebrates experience adverse effects, we can help inform guidelines that favour the health of the entire ecosystem.

020

NEUROMUSCULAR JUNCTION MORPHOLOGY IS MODESTLY INFLUENCED THROUGH AMPK ACTIVATION IN AGED MICE

Ricky K Hong^{*}, Andrew I Mikhail, Sean Y Ng, Stephanie R Mattina, Magda Lesinski, Vladimir Ljubicic
Department of Kinesiology, McMaster University, Ontario, Canada L8S 4L8

Introduction: The neuromuscular junction (NMJ) facilitates the electrochemical communication between an α -motor neuron and myofiber that is crucial for the induction of a muscle contraction. Accompanying the age-related loss of muscle mass, i.e., sarcopenia, are deleterious alterations to NMJ morphology. Interventions such as exercise and caloric restriction can ameliorate age-associated deficits at the NMJ due, in part, to the stimulation of upstream proteins that are directly or indirectly regulated by AMP-activated Protein Kinase (AMPK). Hence, the purpose of this study is to investigate the effects of chronic AMPK activation on NMJ morphology and health within aged mice. **Methods:** Old C57BL/6 mice (n = 16) were randomized at 18-months of age to receive either a vehicle (Old-Veh) or 10 mg/kg of body weight of a small molecule AMPK agonist MK8722 (old-MK) every other day for a total of 6-months. The epitrochleoanconus muscle was collected, stained and further analyzed. Young 3-month-old mice served as a healthy control **Results:** Our preliminary data (n=2-4 per group) demonstrate a significantly greater nerve terminal perimeter (p<0.05) in Old-Veh relative to young mice, which tended to decrease (p=0.09) with MK treatment. Furthermore, we observed a greater number of polyinnervated NMJs, and pre-synaptic branch length in Old-Veh mice only. Age also exacerbated post-synaptic fragmentation (p<0.05) which was partially decreased in old-MK mice. **Conclusion:** This study provides evidence implicating AMPK's role as an influential molecular regulator at the level of the NMJ. Further work is aimed to achieve a full data set to grasp the extent of this relationship.

021

EFFECTS OF PIKFYVE LIPID KINASE INHIBITION ON ENDOPLASMIC RETICULUM IN THE CONTEXT OF ER-REMODELING

Lomiyev, Sharifa*, Jenkins, Nicala, Adamji, Zainab, Almasri, Nourhan, Botelho, Roberto J.
Department of Chemistry and Biology, Toronto Metropolitan University, Toronto, Ontario, Canada M5B 2K3

Lysosomes are important for molecular degradation and regulation of other organelles through membrane contact sites (MCS), including the endoplasmic reticulum (ER), the largest organelle in the cells responsible for protein and lipid synthesis, and calcium signaling. The ER is highly dynamic, constantly changing shape, partly through ER-hitchhiking, a process of ER-remodeling driven by ER-anchoring to motile lysosomes. A key effector of lysosomal dynamics is the kinase PIKfyve, responsible for synthesizing phosphatidylinositol 3,5-bisphosphate. Inhibition of PIKfyve disrupts lysosome shape and dynamics by lysosomal coalescence, reduced motility, and diminished endocytic trafficking and autophagic flux. However, the specific effects of PIKfyve inhibition on lysosomal cross-talk with the ER are unclear. We discovered that PIKfyve inhibition causes a collapsed ER morphology with reduced dynamics and reduced ER hitchhiking. My work aimed to understand these observations by asking if PIKfyve inhibition altered microtubules and contact sites between ER-lysosomes, both needed for ER hitchhiking.

Utilizing high-resolution microscopy of EB1 (a microtubule plus-end marker) and α -tubulin (a standard microtubule marker), we noted that upon PIKfyve inhibition, there are no significant differences in microtubule morphology or dynamics. This suggests that alteration of ER-remodeling via ER-hitchhiking is not influenced by microtubule instability upon PIKfyve inhibition. Given what we discovered, we are utilizing high-resolution microscopy using GCEP1A-ER (an ER-calcium biosensor) to explore the functional consequences of PIKfyve-inhibition on ER-lysosome MCS. Investigating this aims to link lysosomal dysfunction to altered organelle cross-talk and impaired ER functions, offering potential insights for therapeutic intervention in diseases driven by organelle disruption.

022

INVESTIGATING PMK1'S ROLES IN THE FISSION YEAST CELL CYCLE

Shikha Narula*¹, Cindy Ong¹, Sarah A. Sabatinos¹
Department of Chemistry and Biology, Toronto Metropolitan University, Toronto, Ontario, Canada M5B 2K3

Mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK) pathways play a crucial role in cellular stress responses, metabolism, and cell cycle regulation. Pmk1, a MAPK homolog of ERK in *Schizosaccharomyces pombe*, is known to contribute to cell integrity, metabolism, and cytokinesis. Yet, the precise role of Pmk1 in cell cycle regulation is unclear. We examined the function(s) of Pmk1 in fission yeast cell cycle response. We used single and double mutants of *pmk1* Δ , and checkpoint kinases (*cds1* Δ , *chk1* Δ , *rad3* Δ , *mrc1* Δ). Through mutagenesis assays, we found that *pmk1* Δ strains show lower mutation rates than single checkpoint kinase mutant strains. We conclude that Pmk1 influences cell survival and may allow mutated cells to survive. We are testing the impact of *pmk1* Δ on drug sensitivity using half-maximal inhibitory concentration (IC₅₀) tests. IC₅₀ doses of *pmk1*⁺ and *pmk1* Δ strains will compare the impact of Pmk1 in surviving DNA replication instability caused by hydroxyurea, or DNA damage stress caused by phleomycin, and camptothecin. Since these chemotherapy drugs induce replication stress and DNA damage, our study provides insights into how MAPK signaling influences cellular responses to genotoxic agents. Given the conservation of MAPK pathways across eukaryotes, understanding Pmk1's role may help uncover mechanisms of drug resistance in cancer cells. This research enhances our understanding of stress adaptation mechanisms in the cell cycle, with broader implications for genomic stability and therapeutic strategies targeting MAPK signaling.

023

THE ROLE OF SHP-1 IN MACROPHAGE PHAGOCYTOTIC CAPACITY DURING Fc γ RIIB MEDIATED INHIBITORY SIGNALLING

Raina Fatima*, Elijah Urdaneta, Roberto Botelho

Department of Chemistry and Biology, Toronto Metropolitan University, Toronto, Ontario, Canada, M5B 2K3

The maximal phagocytic capacity of macrophages is governed by various factors, including enzyme and membrane availability. However, there are many gaps in literature regarding the signaling mechanisms that limit the maximal phagocytic capacity of macrophages. Fc γ Rs are critical surface receptors found on macrophages and other immune cells that signal the process of phagocytosis and trigger subsequent immune responses. We have previously found that SHP-1, a downstream protein of the inhibitory receptor Fc γ RIIB, exhibits maintained activity and phosphorylation levels as macrophages approach capacity. We sought to further investigate the role of SHP-1 by first determining whether the inhibitory effects of SHP-1 during phagocytosis require a continuous feeding source or can be triggered by a brief uptake event. To explore this, we fed macrophages 2.97 μ m polystyrene beads for 30 minutes, followed by varying chase times. We show that SHP-1 activation diminishes after a macrophage's food source is removed, suggesting that SHP-1 activity may be crucial for regulating phagocytosis in the presence of a continuous feeding supply. Additionally, we aim to visualize the engulfment of beads before and after SHP-1 inhibition using TPI-1, hypothesizing that macrophages may be able to engulf additional particles upon inhibition. Overall, this study provides new insights into the molecular mechanisms regulating macrophage phagocytic capacity, highlighting the inhibitory role of SHP-1.

024

THE ROLE OF ESTROGEN-RELATED RECEPTOR ON EXERCISE TRAINING IN ZEBRAFISH.

Simer Gill*, Riley Mantulak, and Alexander Little.

Department of Biology, McMaster University, Hamilton, Ontario, Canada L8S 4L8

Zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) are valuable biomedical models for metabolic and cardiovascular disease due to their genetic tractability, scalability, and rapid development. Exercise training has been explored as a therapeutic intervention for metabolic and cardiovascular disease in this species, but mechanisms underlying physiological responses remain poorly characterized. In mammals, the nuclear receptor estrogen-related receptor (ERR) mediates exercise-induced remodelling by enhancing vascularization, oxidative phosphorylation (OXPHOS), and cell proliferation in metabolically active tissues, such as skeletal muscle and brain. In mammals, these effects are primarily driven through ERR's interaction with peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor gamma coactivator 1 α (PGC1 α). However, sequence analyses suggest that PGC1 α of fish lacks the functional domains that promote metabolic regulation (e.g., NRF1 binding and AMPK phosphorylation sites) in mammals. We exercise-trained zebrafish for 6 weeks (forced swimming protocol) to test whether exercise enhances performance via an ERR-mediated pathway. Specifically, we hypothesized that exercise training would enhance swim performance, aerobic scope, and boldness. Although exercise training improved these performance traits, global proteomics (skeletal muscle and brain) suggests that ERR-mediated exercise remodelling is not conserved in fish. These data highlight fundamental differences in the molecular mechanisms underlying exercise-induced plasticity between fish and mammals. Therefore, careful consideration is needed when applying zebrafish as biomedical models of metabolic and cardiovascular diseases, and alternative pathways regulating physical activity responses in vertebrates warrant further investigation.

025

THE EFFECTS OF PATERNAL PRE-FERTILIZATION THC EXPOSURE ON FERTILIZATION SUCCESS AND EARLY EMBRYONIC DEVELOPMENT

Tayin Seeton*¹, Jonathan Stone¹

¹Department of Biology, McMaster University, Hamilton, Ontario, Canada L8S 4L8

THC, or *Δ9-tetrahydrocannabinol* usage among the reproductively active (ages 18-44) has increased significantly since its legalization in 2018. THC reduces fertilizing capacity of male gametes by inhibiting the acrosomal reaction while also reducing sperm count and sperm motility. While the impacts of THC-influenced sperm on fertilization is widely studied, the influence of THC on early embryonic development is largely understudied. Given the evolutionary similarities of the endocannabinoid system in sperm, first discovered in sea urchins, we used *Strongylocentrotus droebachiensis* as a model organism to investigate this relationship. Sperm were exposed to different concentrations of THC, attempting to mimic therapeutic (0.032uM), medium (0.32uM) and heavy cannabis use (3.2uM). The sperm were then mixed with healthy eggs to achieve fertilization. It was observed that, consistent with previously observed decreased fertilization, that as the concentrations increased, there was decreased survivorship, coupled with abnormal development. These findings suggest that paternal THC exposure may negatively impact early embryonic development, warranting further research.

026

Effect of Arbuscular Mycorrhizal Fungi on Bacterial Metabolism in an Active Hydroponic Green Wall System

Nojan Shishechiha*, and Dr. Stephanie Melles.

Department of Chemistry and Biology, Toronto Metropolitan University, Toronto, Ontario, Canada, M5B 2K3.

Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (AMF) are symbiotic soil microorganisms that enhance plant nutrient uptake and stress resistance in exchange for carbohydrates. While extensively studied in traditional soil systems, their role in hydroponics remains underexplored. AMF has shown potential in hydroponic systems by improving plant health, reducing chemical input dependence, and modulating microbial interactions. This study investigates the impact of AMF inoculation on bacterial metabolic activity in active wet hydroponic systems, addressing a critical knowledge gap in soilless agriculture. Precisely, we assess how AMF influences bacterial communities by modifying root exudates, potentially suppressing pathogenic bacteria while promoting beneficial ones. Unlike prior studies that focus primarily on plant growth, this research takes a comprehensive approach, evaluating shifts in bacterial metabolism in AMF-inoculated hydroponic systems. Our findings aim to enhance plant health, foster beneficial bacterial activity, mitigate non-beneficial microbial growth, and promote sustainable hydroponic practices. By elucidating the multifaceted interactions between AMF, plants, and microbial communities, this study contributes to the broader understanding of AMF applications beyond soil-based agriculture.

027

SPECIES IN FECES: EXAMINING THE EFFECTS OF PER- AND POLYFLUOROALKYL SUBSTANCES ON THE MICE GUT MICROBIOME

Arianna Stanley-Harrison¹, Amélie Blais², Lauren Bradford², Matt Meier², Euguene Fletcher¹, and Azam Tayabali^{1,2}.

¹Department of Biology, Carleton University, Ottawa, Ontario, Canada K1S 5B6

²Environmental Health Science and Research Bureau, Health Canada, Ottawa, Ontario, Canada K1A 0K9

Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS), commonly known as "forever chemicals", are synthetic environmentally persistent contaminants. Historically, PFAS were widely utilized in consumer products such as non-stick cookware, water-repellent textiles, firefighting foams, and cosmetics. However, the PFAS accumulation in environmental matrices and human systems has raised significant health concerns. Previous *in vivo* and epidemiological studies have identified potential adverse health effects, including immune suppression, metabolic dysfunction, and delayed developmental outcomes. Moreover, PFAS may also influence the gut microbial homeostasis. This study investigates the effects of perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) and perfluorooctane sulfonate (PFOS) exposure on the gut microbiome of mice exposed to PFOA or PFOS by oral gavage (doses: 0.166, 0.5, 10, or 1.5 mg/kg/day) for 28 or 56 days. Fecal samples were collected, and DNA was extracted using the QIAGEN PowerFecal Pro DNA Kit. DNA quality and concentration were assessed with a Nanodrop spectrophotometer and an Agilent TapeStation system. To analyze changes in the gut, full-length 16S ribosomal ribonucleic acid (rRNA) gene was sequenced on a PacBio Sequel 2 sequencer. The library preparation and sequencing were performed by the Integrated Microbiome Resource (Dalhousie, NS). Sequencing is currently ongoing, and preliminary results are presented here. 16s rRNA sequencing data will provide valuable insights into the mechanisms by which PFAS affect gut microbial communities and host health. These findings will contribute to the understanding of PFAS toxicity, predicting potential human health risks, and informing future public health strategies and regulatory policies.

028

CHARACTERIZING THE FUNCTION OF THE AKNA GENE USING DELETION AND KNOCK-IN CRISPR METHODS IN THE ZEBRAFISH.

Priscilla Fung*¹, Kevin Ban², Sergey V. Prykhozhiy², Jason N. Berman².

¹Department of Biology, University of Ottawa, Ottawa, Ontario, Canada K1N 6N5

²Children's Hospital of Eastern Ontario Research Institute, Ottawa, Canada K1J 8L1

Following the diagnosis of a fatal inflammatory disorder involving profound immune system dysregulation in an Inuit child, whole genome sequencing determined the child to be homozygous for a missense variant in the *AKNA* gene. In humans, *AKNA* is hypothesized to regulate both neurogenesis and immune cell maturation and function as an AT-hook transcription factor. Due to the limited knowledge of *AKNA*'s roles in development and disease, we used Cas9-directed mutagenesis to create 3 zebrafish models: a deletion (Del) line causing *Akna* LOF, a knock-in (KI) reporter line employing superfolder green fluorescent protein (sfGFP), and a CRISPR insertional mutagenesis protocol (CRIMP) line involving both *Akna* LOF and an amplified reporter signal of *Akna*. Whole-mount in-situ hybridization (WISH) found *akna* mRNA to be expressed in the head region of zebrafish embryos at 2 to 3 days-post-fertilization (dpf), with concentrated expression in the retinal nuclear layers, olfactory bulb, and neuromasts by 5 to 6 dpf. In homozygous Del mutants, DNA and RNA sequencing confirmed the deletion of 13kb from the *akna* gene which prevented mRNA transcription. The consequences of *Akna* LOF on neurogenesis and immune function will be quantified. Fluorescence microscopy of heterozygous KI mutants determined *Akna* protein to be expressed in the nervous system until 30 hours-post-fertilization. Homozygous KI embryos will be subsequently studied. The CRIMP line will be used to clarify *Akna* LOF phenotypes without inducing genetic compensation and enable better visualization of *Akna* expression patterns using a Gal4/UAS system.

029

ANALYSING SEX-DEPENDENT EFFECTS OF MONOCROTALINE (MCT) THROUGH GLYCOGEN STORAGE

Pakin Pongpaiboon

Department of Biology, Trent University, Peterborough, ON, Canada

Contact Email: pakinpongpaiboon@trentu.ca

The monocrotaline (MCT) model is a pharmaceutical approach to studying cardiac cachexia, a multiorgan syndrome that results in extreme lean body mass and skeletal muscle loss in heart failure patients. Although the MCT model of cardiac cachexia is prevalent, the physiological basis for sex-dependent effects is not well-studied. Previously, our lab has detected results that suggest that male mice are more adversely affected by MCT-induced cachexia as the whole-body weight of male but not female mice was reduced. It was found that the cross-sectional area of skeletal muscle was reduced in male and female samples while fat was reduced in male samples. As skeletal muscles are a site for glycogen storage and many skeletal wasting conditions are associated with reduced glycogen, it was suspected that glycogen could be different in MCT-treated mice, particularly in males with reduced body and adipose mass.

It is hypothesized that males' skeletal muscle glycogen storage will be more adversely affected than females treated with MCT. Greater glycogen storage in females will provide support that skeletal muscle and body weight are lost in a sex-dependent fashion through glycogen changes in the MCT model of cardiac cachexia. Periodic Acid Schiff (PAS) stain was applied to paraffin-embedded skeletal muscle sections of the tibialis anterior and gastrocnemius from the previous study to quantify glycogen. The results and analysis, which are in progress, will verify the potential sex-dependent effects of skeletal muscle loss in MCT-induced cachexia.

030

EXPLORING THE EFFICACY OF PROBIOTIC TREATMENTS IN REDUCING *PSEUDOGYMNOASCUS DESTRUCTANS* CONCENTRATIONS IN BATS AFFECTED BY WHITE-NOSE SYNDROME.

Celeste Abraham*¹, Chadabhorn Insuk¹, Heather Yoell¹, Abby Tobin², Cori Lausen³, Jianping Xu¹.

¹Department of Biology, McMaster University, Hamilton, Ontario, Canada L8S 4L8

²Wildlife Ecology, School of Forestry, Northern Arizona University, Flagstaff, Arizona, United States of America 86011

³Wildlife Conservation Society Canada, Kaslo, BC, Canada V0G 1M0

White-nose syndrome, caused by *Pseudogymnoascus destructans* (*Pd*), poses a significant threat to bat populations across North America. Previous research suggests that probiotics may mitigate the impact of *Pd*, but evidence of their efficacy remains limited. This study investigates the correlation between probiotic treatments and *Pd* concentrations in Yuma myotis (*Myotis yumanensis*) and little brown bats (*Myotis lucifugus*) from Washington State. This research focuses on a probiotic cocktail consisting of *Pseudomonas lactis* A&B, *Pseudomonas synxantha*, and *Pseudomonas antarctica*. 478 samples from March to August 2024 were analyzed using quantitative PCR to assess *Pd* and probiotic concentrations. We test the hypothesis that the presence of probiotic bacteria on bat wings will be associated with low *Pd* concentrations. Results show that high probiotic concentrations align with lower *Pd* concentrations, supporting probiotics' potential to mitigate WNS in bat populations. Spearman's rank correlation demonstrated a significant negative correlation between total probiotic and *Pd* concentrations. This study provides insights into probiotic effectiveness and lays a foundation for further research.

031

EXPLORING THE IMPACT OF INTERFERENCE COMPETITION ON FOOD ACCESS IN HUMMINGBIRDS

Sydney Williams*, and Roslyn Dakin.

Department of Biology, Carleton University, Ottawa, Ontario, Canada K1S 5B6

An uneven distribution of food is expected to increase competitive interactions, yet the relationship between aggression and food access remains underexplored. One form of such competition is interference competition, where one individual directly interacts with another while competing for the same resource. These interactions can reduce a subordinate individual's access to resources. This study examines whether wild-caught hummingbirds would engage in interference competition during competition trials in captivity, where three individuals had to rely on a single food source. We defined interference as instances where an aggressor displaced a competitor at the feeder, but did not stop to feed itself afterward. Our results show that interference was frequent, occurring in 56% of interactions at the feeder, suggesting that displacements were often driven by a motivation to exclude competitors. Next, we assessed whether individual birds differ in their tendency to interfere with others across repeated trials, and whether this behaviour is also associated with aggression at perches. Individual differences explained approximately 20% of variation in interference frequency, and hummingbirds that performed more interference at the feeder also performed more aggression at the perches. Finally, we investigated whether hummingbirds encountered each other at the feeder more often than expected, based on a null model. We find that some, but not all, of the hummingbirds exhibited significantly higher co-occurrence at the feeder than expected. These findings indicate that interference competition can occur in captive hummingbirds, and highlight individual variation in competitive behaviours within the same species.

032

EXPLORING THE ECOLOGICAL NICHE OF EUROPEAN STARLINGS (*STURNUS VULGARIS*), TREE SWALLOWS (*TACHYCINETA BICOLOR*) AND INSECT COMMUNITIES THROUGH STABLE ISOTOPE ANALYSIS TO IDENTIFY FOOD WEB LINKAGES FOR PFAS-TRANSFER AT CONTAMINATED AND NON-CONTAMINATED SITES IN SOUTHERN ONTARIO.

Danielle MacNeil*¹, Julianna Colafranceschi¹, Kim Fernie², Emily Choy¹.

¹ Department of Biology, McMaster University, Hamilton, Ontario, Canada L8S 4E1

² Ecotoxicology and Wildlife Health Division, Environment and Climate Change Canada, Burlington, Ontario, Canada L7S 1A1

Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) are anthropogenic chemicals widely used in consumer and industrial products. Due to their persistence, toxicity, and bioaccumulative properties, PFAS pollution is of growing concern, with increasing evidence of adverse effects on wildlife and human health. While emergent aquatic insects are recognized as vectors for PFAS transfer to terrestrial predators, the role of terrestrial insects in PFAS transfer remains understudied. Additionally, although birds are effective biological indicators of ecological health, little is known about PFAS toxicity in avian species. Therefore, this study aims to identify potential PFAS transfer routes from terrestrial insects to avian predators by examining ecological niches using carbon ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$) and nitrogen ($\delta^{15}\text{N}$) stable isotope (SI) analysis at PFAS contaminated and non-contaminated sites in southern Ontario. Diet plays a key role in PFAS transfer within food webs, and SI analysis is widely used for characterizing ecological niches, thereby providing insight into PFAS contamination pathways. This study also evaluated the use of bird feather SI analysis as a less invasive alternative to blood SI analysis. Results showed that feather SI values significantly predict blood values ($R^2 = 0.98$ for both $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$, $p < 0.0001$), demonstrating the reliability of feathers for ecological niche characterization. This finding supports the use of feather SI analysis as a viable, less invasive method, particularly useful for studying endangered bird populations. By mapping ecological

37th Annual Ontario Biology Day Poster Presentation Abstracts

niches, this study clarifies predator-prey dynamics and potential PFAS transfer pathways, providing a roadmap for future research to directly quantify PFAS contamination and its ecological impact.

033

ANTIBIOTICS AND THEIR EFFECTS ON DEER MICE (*PEROMYSCUS MANICULATUS*) SMALL INTESTINE HISTOMORPHOLOGY

Benjamin Winchester*¹, Caileigh Tomas¹, Graham Scott¹

¹Department of Biology, McMaster University, Hamilton, Ontario, Canada L8S 4K1

Gut microbiome research is a diverse and rapidly growing field focusing on the wide array of roles the microorganisms of the digestive tract can have. A common research method to study these roles is through the administration of antibiotics with the goal of disrupting the gut microbiome. Previous studies have shown that antibiotics can have unintended effects on the digestive tract, particularly the small intestine. Moreover, such studies often combine antibiotic treatments with different environmental factors, which may further amplify these effects. We hypothesized that antibiotic treatment would result in a remodeling of both small intestine morphology and digestive function. To test this, two populations (high- and low-altitude natives) of deer mice (*Peromyscus maniculatus*) were acclimated to either warm (25°C) normoxia or cold (5°C) hypoxia (12 kPa O₂) for six weeks. A subset of the deer mice received a broad-spectrum antibiotic in their drinking water for the final four weeks of acclimation. Following treatment, small intestine samples were collected and prepared for histological analysis or stored for enzyme assays. Our results showed that neither antibiotic administration nor environment significantly affected the small intestine histological parameters of both populations. The functional effects of antibiotics on the small intestine are still under investigation. These findings will contribute to our understanding of how antibiotic treatments and environmental factors interact to influence small intestine health.

034

IMPACT OF FLEXIBLE GRADING SCHEME ON LEARNING ENVIRONMENT AND CLASSROOM DYNAMICS IN BIOLOGY COURSES AT UNIVERSITY OF TORONTO MISSISSAUGA (UTM)

Laiba Jamal*, Ilyas Wilson, Khaled Fawal, Sharleen Bains, and Sanja Hinic-Frlog

Department of Biology, University of Toronto Mississauga, Mississauga, ON, L5L 1C6

Traditional grading schemes may not always accurately reflect student performance, leading to the increasing adoption of flexible grading in university courses. These alternative grading structures allow students to tailor assessments to their strengths, fostering a more personalized and equitable learning experience. Research suggests that flexible grading enhances student autonomy, motivation, and engagement while reducing stress and anxiety. Additionally, instructors report improved student understanding and higher-quality work. However, there is limited empirical research on how flexible grading influences student perceptions of learning and classroom dynamics, particularly in STEM disciplines. This study aims to assess the impact of flexible grading schemes on student experiences in university biology courses. Surveys will be conducted in Winter 2025 across five biology courses at the University of Toronto Mississauga. A two-part anonymous survey, administered via Quercus, will evaluate key factors such as learning retention, perceived fairness, stress levels, motivation, and overall autonomy in coursework. Data will be analyzed using R, incorporating both descriptive statistics and thematic analysis to provide a comprehensive assessment of the effectiveness of flexible grading. The findings will contribute to ongoing discussions on assessment strategies in higher education, offering valuable insights into the potential benefits and challenges of flexible grading in STEM courses. Understanding these impacts can help educators design grading policies that better support diverse student needs and promote a more inclusive learning environment.

035

THE EFFECT OF *DE NOVO* MUTATION ON PHOTOTACTIC RATE IN *CHLAMYDOMONAS REINHARDTII*

Ayesha S Syeda*¹, Eniolaye J Balogun^{1,2}, Rob W Ness^{1,2,3}

¹ Department of Biology, University of Toronto, Mississauga L5L-1C6, Canada

² Department of Ecology and Evolutionary Biology, University of Toronto, Toronto M5S-3B2, Canada

³ Department of Cell & Systems Biology, University of Toronto, Toronto, ON M5S-3G5, Canada

Chlamydomonas reinhardtii, a unicellular green alga, is a model organism commonly used in evolutionary studies due to its culturing simplicity and flexible genetics. The species demonstrates phototaxis, or directed movement toward light, facilitated by eyespot and ciliary organelles. Previous studies have not thoroughly experimentally validated motility genes specific to *C. reinhardtii*. The motility phenotype additionally allows the exploration of mutational variance (V_m). The V_m metric quantifies the increase of variance in a trait per generation due to mutation. It is a part of genetic variance (V_g), the absolute variance in a trait due to genetic differences among individuals. Comparison of V_g and V_m can be used to measure the strength of selection acting on a trait, as it involves comparing the amount of variance introduced by mutation to what is remaining after selection in a natural population. By utilizing faster and slower motility phenotypes and their underlying genetics, it is therefore possible to quantify V_g and V_m , to determine the effect of *de novo* mutation on phototactic rate. This study thus aimed to develop a protocol quantifying phototactic rate across natural and mutation accumulation (MA) strains of *C. reinhardtii*, validate candidate genes for motility in a post-assay variant mapping experiment, and calculate V_g and V_m . Preliminary results suggest that differentiation in phototactic rate across MA strains is comparable to that seen in natural strains and that there is not a notable difference in the variance of the phototactic rate in both strain types.

036

IMPLICATING THE SEROTONERGIC SYSTEM IN FEEDING AND GROWTH IN ZEBRAFISH (*DANIO RERIO*).

Kristen Huang*, Michael Tea, Kathleen Gilmour.

Department of Biology, University of Ottawa, 30 Marie Curie Pvt, Ottawa, ON, K1N 6N5, Canada

Zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) have two paralogues of the serotonin transporter (Sert) uniquely expressed in the brain, *Serta* and *Sertb*, which re-uptake serotonin from the synapse into the presynaptic neuron. Zebrafish lines lacking the expression of either *serta*, *sertb*, or both were generated using CRISPR/Cas9 technology. To investigate the consequences of Sert knockouts on feeding behaviour and growth as a function of food intake, feeding behaviour in adults as well as growth indices in larval, juvenile, and adults were measured. The *serta*^{-/-} and *sertab*^{-/-} adult zebrafish consumed less food than their *sertb*^{-/-} and *sertab*^{+/+} counterparts. This feeding result corresponds to adult *serta*^{-/-} averaging less total body weight than *sertab*^{+/+} fish. However, both *sertb*^{-/-} and *sertab*^{-/-} displayed intermediate body masses. Similarly, at 1 day post fertilization, *serta*^{-/-} fish exhibit smaller growth indicators (yolk sac area) compared to the other genotypes. These differences in food intake and growth rate indicators between genotypes provides insight into the complementary and distinct roles of the serotonin transporter paralogues in altering growth by regulating food intake and metabolism in unique areas.

037

TWO-EYED SEEING CASE STUDY: INUIT AND MARINE ECOLOGY

Chilyn Fenton-Stickle*, Helene Wagner

Department of Biology, University of Toronto Mississauga, Mississauga, Ontario, Canada

L5L 1C6

This case study aims to apply the Mi'kmaw Two-Eyed Seeing concept to explore how the Inuit Way of Knowing (Qaujimaqatuqangit) and Western Science can come together to improve our understanding on climate change impacts on the Arctic marine ecosystem. As a teaching material for university-level ecology courses, the study focuses on providing scholars and learners with perspectives on how one could look at ecosystem functions. By referring to interactive maps, the case study asks users to explore and discuss key questions: When does the ice-free season open? How does the ice coverage shift over seasons and years? How has the interspecific interaction shifted between the sub-Arctic species Orca whale (*Orcinus orca*) and the Arctic species narwhal (*Monodon monoceros*) as a result of ice coverage changes? How can the Inuit Way of Knowing inform ecological monitoring? This study provides the opportunity to reflect on how Indigenous methods and approaches can contribute to conservation strategies, as well as moving towards reconciliation in higher education. It emphasizes the importance of Indigenous Knowledge in climate change research and ecosystem monitoring, that can inform strategies to mitigate the impacts of Arctic warming on the ecosystem.

038

ELECTRICAL IMPEDANCE TOMOGRAPHY (EIT) AS A TOOL TO ANALYZE AQUATIC VENTILATION IN DIVING

Paige Mutsuko Yoshida*¹, Jeff W. Dawson¹, Andy Adler²

¹Department of Biology, Carleton University, Ottawa, Ontario, Canada, K1S 5B7

²Department of Systems and Computer Engineering, Carleton University, Ottawa, Ontario, Canada, K1S 5B7

Electrical Impedance Tomography (EIT) is a non-invasive imaging technique that is used to monitor lung function. While it has proved itself beneficial in clinical settings, its application and reliability underwater are unknown. To test this, participants were assessed under different water depths and body positions. Our findings indicate that ventilation and air distribution patterns are correlated to both varying water depth and body positioning. This research represents the first study of underwater ventilation using EIT and can provide a foundation for future studies. The findings have implications for individuals working in aquatic environments and those who partake recreationally, contributing to a better understanding of respiratory physiology in these conditions.

039

UNDERSTANDING THE CRYPTIC REGULATION OF GLYCOLYSIS IN CHLOROPLASTS OF *ARABIDOPSIS THALIANA*

Anya Hu*¹, Sonia E. Evans², Anya E. Franks², and Michael A. Phillips^{1,2}

¹Department of Biology, University of Toronto - Mississauga, Mississauga, ON L5L 1C6, Canada

²Department of Cell and Systems Biology, University of Toronto, Toronto, ON M5S 3G5, Canada

Phosphoenolpyruvate (PEP) and pyruvate constitute key precursors for the synthesis of terpenoids, phenolics, and fatty acids in plants. Mature chloroplasts cannot synthesize PEP due to the downregulation of two key enzymes of glycolysis, enolase (ENO) and phosphoglycerate mutase (PGM). Instead, PEP is synthesized in the cytosol and transported into chloroplasts through the PPT1 transporter, where it is used in the biosynthesis of aromatic amino acids. The physiological factors that necessitate this arrangement are unknown. The *Arabidopsis cue1* mutant is a powerful tool to understand the regulation of glycolysis in plants. It has a defective PPT1 transporter and is therefore unable to supply chloroplasts with PEP. Its distinctive reticulated phenotype was exploited in this study to visually track the effects of restoring the glycolytic pathway in chloroplasts. Stably transformed lines of *Arabidopsis thaliana* were created that overexpress plastidial forms of both ENO and PGM in the wild type and *cue1* mutant background. Partial complementation of the mutant phenotype in ENO/PGM transformed plant lines suggest that downregulation of glycolysis in the chloroplast is an adaptation that permits otherwise competing biosynthetic processes to function together seamlessly in the same compartment.

040

THE EFFECTS OF FEEDING ON HEART RATE AND BODY TEMPERATURE IN BLACK-LEGGED KITTIWAKES (*RISSA TRIDACTYLA*)

Abby Eaton*¹, Flynn O'Dacre¹, Shannon Leone Fowler², Shannon Whelan³, Scott Hatch³, Kyle Elliott⁴, Emily Choy¹.

¹Department of Biology, McMaster University, Hamilton, Ontario, Canada

²School of Life and Health Sciences, University of Roehampton, London, United Kingdom

³Institute for Seabird Research and Conservation, Anchorage, Alaska, USA

⁴Department of Natural Resources Sciences, McGill University, Ste-Anne-de-Bellevue, Québec, Canada

Accelerating climate change is causing a shift in prey availability for many species of seabirds, which could affect their daily energy expenditure. Several seabird species have shown an increase in metabolic rate, heart rate, and body temperature with digestion. Known as the heat increment of feeding, this effect contributes to the energy budget of seabirds. The pelagic seabird, the black-legged kittiwake (*Rissa tridactyla*), is widespread throughout the northern Atlantic and Pacific oceans. The objectives of our study were to investigate the physiological response to feeding in kittiwakes by comparing heart rate and body temperature between groups of supplementary fed and unfed kittiwakes. We deployed heart rate biologgers in 60 kittiwakes from May 2024 to July 2024 on Middleton Island, Alaska. We supplementally fed 30 kittiwakes for ten days, providing unlimited capelin (3x per day). Heart rate and body temperature were determined before and after individual feeding events. The difference in these values determined the change in heart rate and body temperature associated with feeding. The difference in heart rate and body temperature associated with the feeding period significantly differed between the 'fed' and 'unfed' conditions. Additionally, the physiological response increased in magnitude with the amount of fish consumed.

041

CHARACTERIZING THE DEVELOPMENTAL BIRTH ORIGINS OF PM NEURONS IN THE DROSOPHILA OPTIC LOBE

Nicolas Andres Fragoso Wandurraga¹, Ted Erlik¹

Department of Biology, University of Toronto Mississauga, Mississauga, ON¹.

In the *Drosophila* optic lobe, neural progenitors, termed neuroblasts are patterned by independent temporal and spatial inputs to generate >200 neuron types, making it an excellent model for understanding how neuronal diversity is generated. In the temporal axis, transcription factors (TFs) (Hth, Ey, Slp, D) are sequentially expressed in medulla neuroblasts as they age. Additionally, a set of TFs (Vsx1, Optix, Rx) compartmentalize the outer proliferation center, the stem cell pool from which neuroblasts are generated. As a result, neuroblasts generate different neurons based on their spatial-temporal identity. To date, several proximal medulla (Pm) neuron types have been found to possess similar spatial (Vsx1 or Rx) and temporal (Hth or Ey) birth origins. This study aims to map the spatial-temporal birth address of additional Pm neurons (Pm5, Pm6 and Pm11) to determine if they too share developmental similarities. To do this, I used the transgenic split-Gal4 system to independently label each Pm neuron with GFP. Using immunohistochemistry techniques and confocal microscopy, I visualized the expression of different patterning TFs in the Pm neurons to uncover their spatial-temporal origins. Pm5, Pm6 and Pm11 all express Tfap2, a TF only expressed in neurons born in the Hth window. However, these neurons do not express Vsx1, indicating that they are not born from the Vsx1 region. Based on these results, the Pm neurons of this study are born from the early Hth temporal window and are likely to originate from the Rx spatial region, suggesting that all Pm-class neurons possess similar developmental origins.

042

SYNERGISTIC EFFECTS OF SPZ² AND GDI^{N7-3} MUTATIONS ON DEVELOPMENT OF THE NEUROMUSCULAR JUNCTION IN DROSOPHILA MELANOGASTER

Niha Sohail*¹, Kathryn Harris-Howard², Bryan Stewart¹

¹ Department of Cell & Systems Biology, University of Toronto Mississauga, Mississauga, Ontario, Canada L5L 1C6

² Office of the Vice-Principal Research, University of Toronto Mississauga, Mississauga, Ontario, Canada L5L 1C6

The neuromuscular junction (NMJ) is a site of information transfer between motor neurons and muscle fibers, where various proteins regulate synaptic development and plasticity. This study investigates the effects of knocking down GDI, a Rab regulator protein, using RNA interference (RNAi) at the NMJs of *Drosophila melanogaster*. Additionally, the study examines the impact of spz² and GDI^{N7-3} mutations on NMJ morphology. NMJs from muscles 6 and 7 of third instar larvae were analyzed for changes in NMJ length, bouton number, and synaptic debris accumulation. By creating three heterozygous genotypes—spz^{2/+}, GDI^{N7-3/+}, and a double-heterozygote carrying both mutations—alongside the GDI knockdown by RNAi, the aim is to uncover any potential combined effects on the NMJ, suggesting that these genes interact to regulate NMJ morphology. Results show that the double heterozygote had a significantly increased bouton count, and all experimental genotypes had decreased amounts of synaptic debris compared to the control genotype (w-). These results indicate a novel genetic interaction, implying that Spätzle and GDI have similar and synergistic effects on the NMJ. Further studies may determine the underlying molecular mechanisms by which Spätzle and GDI interact to regulate synaptic development and maintenance at the NMJ.

044

INVESTIGATING THE ROLE OF PIKFYVE INHIBITION ON LYSOSOME-MITOCHONDRIA CO-MIGRATION

Connie Di Raimo*¹, Maria Narciso¹, Roberto J. Botelho¹

¹Department of Chemistry and Biology, Toronto Metropolitan University, Toronto, Ontario, Canada M5B 2K3

Lysosomes and mitochondria are essential organelles that maintain cellular homeostasis. Lysosomes function as signalling hubs and are the terminal site of the endolysosomal pathway for cargo degradation, while mitochondria drive cellular energy metabolism and production. These organelles can communicate through membrane contact sites, which are key for bidirectional regulation to maintain cellular function and survival. Membrane contact sites hold these organelles together, which allows for their co-migration. However, the mechanisms underlying lysosome-mitochondria co-migration remain poorly understood. PIKfyve is a lipid kinase complex that regulates lysosomal morphology and motility by phosphorylating phosphatidylinositol-3-phosphate into phosphatidylinositol-3,5-bisphosphate. PIKfyve inhibition leads to enlarged vacuoles due to lysosome coalescence. New research from our lab has discovered that PIKfyve inhibition decreases lysosome-mitochondria proximity, impairs organelle motility and increases mitochondrial fragmentation. We hypothesized that PIKfyve inhibition will decrease lysosome-mitochondria co-migration. To test this, we used live cell fluorescence imaging in COS-7 cells and quantified co-migration events by assessing lysosomal influence of mitochondrial displacement. Our results suggest that PIKfyve inhibition using apilimod significantly reduces the amount of lysosome-mitochondria co-migration events, supporting previous unpublished findings. Since mitochondria appear fragmented in PIKfyve-inhibited cells, we are now assessing whether PIKfyve inhibition with apilimod and APY0201 impairs mitochondrial fusion using two HeLa cell lines, each expressing a TOMM20-mCherry or COX8A-emiRFP mitochondrial marker. These two cell populations will then be co-cultured and fused together with polyethylene glycol to measure intermixing of mitochondrial markers to determine fusion rates of mitochondria. Overall, our findings suggest that while PIKfyve controls lysosomes directly, its activity is also critical for mitochondria dynamics.

045

INVESTIGATING A DUAL-FLUORESCENT mCHERRY-GFP SYSTEM FOR TRACKING *SALMONELLA* VIABILITY DURING PHAGOSOMAL MATURATION

Qing Gui Queenie Chung*, Subothan Inpanathan, Maria Narciso, and Roberto J. Botelho.

Department of Chemistry and Biology, Toronto Metropolitan University, Toronto, Ontario, Canada M5B 2K3

Phagocytes play a critical role in host defense by engulfing and degrading pathogens within phagosomes, which undergo acidification and maturation into microbicidal compartments. *Salmonella enterica* sv. Typhimurium (*S. Typhimurium*), a facultative intracellular pathogen, has evolved mechanisms to survive this process, complicating efforts to determine bacterial viability within phagosomes. Conventional methods, such as colony counting and gentamicin protection assays, provide endpoint measurements but lack the capability to monitor bacterial death dynamically. To address this, we are investigating a dual-fluorescent mCherry-GFP reporter system to monitor bacterial viability in real time. GFP is pH-sensitive and loses fluorescence in acidic environments, whereas mCherry remains stable providing a reliable reference across different viability states. Our findings indicate that the GFP-to-mCherry ratio declines at pH 5 in both live and dead bacteria, with a more pronounced drop in Sytox-masked, dead *S. Typhimurium*, confirming its ability to distinguish viable from non-viable cells. Live bacteria retain a higher GFP/mCherry ratio at pH 5, though the observed reduction may result from direct exposure to pH 5 PBS, a relatively infinite system with sustained acidity. In contrast, the phagosomal lumen is a more confined and dynamic environment, where bacteria may better regulate their response to acidification. These results suggest the mCherry-GFP system has the potential to track bacterial viability during phagosomal maturation. Ongoing work aims to validate this system in macrophage infections and assess its reliability in studying intracellular *S. Typhimurium* survival. If successful, this method could provide a powerful tool for investigating host-pathogen interactions and antimicrobial strategies.

046

IDENTIFYING EQUIVALENT GENES ACROSS THE E. COLI PANGENOME

Saniya Bhalla*¹ and Gabriel Moreno-Hagelsieb²

¹Department of Biology, Wilfrid Laurier University, Waterloo, Ontario, Canada N2L 3C5

Understanding what makes *Escherichia coli* strains harmless or harmful starts with decoding their genetic blueprint. The *E. coli* pangenome consists of core genes shared across all strains and accessory genes that influence traits like antibiotic resistance and virulence. Identifying orthologous, or equivalent, genes across strains is the first step for studying genetic conservation and functional differences. This study compares sequence clustering methods to determine the most effective one for identifying equivalent genes across multiple *E. coli* strains. To this end, we tested implementations under MMseqs2 and Diamond of two clustering algorithms: (i) standard clustering, which uses strict similarity thresholds, and (ii) linear-time clustering, a heuristic method optimized for speed and scalability. The tests included speed to obtain results, as well as the similarity of the protein clusters obtained. The study determined that Linclust significantly reduced computational time while maintaining clustering accuracy, making it a viable option for large-scale genomic analyses. Though less than 60% of all complete protein groups were found by all four procedures, deeper comparisons revealed that close to 80% of all protein pairs were kept together. This study advances bioinformatics methods for comparative genomics, providing insights into *E. coli* gene organization and evolutionary conservation. Efficient clustering approaches will facilitate large-scale microbial genome analyses, improving our understanding of bacterial evolution, adaptation, and pathogenicity.

047

INVESTIGATING THE ROLE OF THE CHROMATIN REMODELLING COMPLEX COMPONENT ACTIN-RELATED PROTEIN 6 (ARP6) IN TEMPERATURE-REGULATED PLANT IMMUNITY IN *ARABIDOPSIS*.

Shahmeen Farooqi*, Christina AM. Rossi and Christian Danve M. Castroverde

Department of Biology, Wilfrid Laurier University, Waterloo, ON N2L 3C5.

Plants possess two interconnected immune responses – pathogen-associated pattern-triggered immunity (PTI) and effector-triggered immunity (ETI) – which can be regulated by the defence hormone salicylic acid (SA). SA plays a critical role in activating immune responses to infection by various pathogens and pests, while also enhancing tolerance to different abiotic stresses. Transcription factors, CALMODULIN BINDING PROTEIN 60g (CBP60g) and SYSTEMIC ACQUIRED RESISTANCE DEFICIENT 1 (SARD1), promote SA biosynthesis; however temperature-sensitive CBP60g/SARD1 expression results in reduced SA production under moderately elevated temperatures associated with climate warming. The histone variant H2A.Z and its associated epigenetic regulators like ACTIN RELATED PROTEIN 6 (ARP6) are known to mediate temperature-related growth and development, wherein ARP6 facilitates H2A.Z incorporation into nucleosomes. However, their functional roles in temperature-sensitive immunity remains underexplored. To address this, our study investigated the potential role of ARP6 (a core component of the SWR1 chromatin remodelling complex) in temperature-modulated immunity in *Arabidopsis thaliana* plants. Using *arp6* mutants and wild-type Col-0 plants, we assessed disease progression, immune gene expression, and SA levels of these plants following infection with the model bacterial pathogen *Pseudomonas syringae* pv. *tomato* (*Pst*) DC3000 at ambient (23°C) and elevated temperature (28°C). Preliminary results showed that *arp6* mutants exhibit temperature-sensitive disease susceptibility to *Pst* DC3000, suggesting that ARP6 is not involved in temperature-modulated plant immunity. Our findings have clarified the possible role of chromatin remodelling and histone variants in temperature-mediated immune responses under warming conditions. Follow-up investigations with other histone variants and epigenetic factors will provide insights into plant resilience mechanisms.

049

A BACTERIAL VAGINOSIS MODEL: FOLLOWING DISEASE PROGRESSION

Morgane Brading*, Robin Slawson, and Joel Weadge

Department of Biology, Wilfrid Laurier University, Waterloo, ON.

Bacterial vaginosis (BV) is the most common vaginal dysbiotic condition of women of reproductive age. BV is characterized clinically by a vaginal flora not abundant in *Lactobacillus* spp.. It is a recurrent and persistent condition due to the overgrowth of commensal anaerobic bacteria such as *Gardnerella vaginalis*. Current BV studies are restricted to cell cultures, which can be costly and timely, and the temperamental nature of cell lines requires strict aseptic techniques and highly trained researchers. Furthermore, although studies have investigated the role of BV on clinical reproductive outcomes and the tolerance profiles of specific BV-associated bacteria (BVAB), none have highlighted the progression of the disease through time from complete *Lactobacilli* dominance to BVAB dominance. Thus, we present an in-vitro media-based BV model. A co-culture of *L. gasseri*, *L. jensenii*, *L. crispatus*, and *G. vaginalis* was successfully grown and monitored via pH readings, crystal violet biofilm assays, and Nugent scoring on days 3, 10, 16 and 26. This study determined that biofilm production showed only a significant difference on day 10 compared to other sample times, showing no significant increase in biofilm formation with increasing bacterial growth. The pH 7 broth media exhibited a drop in pH to 5 at day 0 and persisted at 4 for the remaining sampling days. Finally, Nugent score analysis via gram-staining will permit *G. vaginalis* growth to be assessed throughout the study period. Model optimization will enable cost-efficient research and a novel method for studying the condition.

050

DETERMINING THE CELLULAR LOCATION OF WSSF AND ITS ROLE IN PHENOTYPIC EXPRESSION OF ACETYLATED CELLULOSE BIOFILMS

Katrina Pegg*, Joel T. Weadge

Department of Biology, Wilfrid Laurier University, Waterloo, Ontario, Canada N2L 3C5

Post-synthesis modifications of exopolysaccharides in both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria lend unique properties to biofilms for colonization of certain niches. The *wss* operon (and specifically the WssF terminal acetyltransferase protein) is a great model system for observation of these biofilm modification pathways and is the focus of this research. Uncovering more information about the specific location of the WssF terminal acetyltransferase *in vivo* will aid our understanding of the role of this protein and its place in the Wss pathway. To detect the location of WssF, a plasmid construct was generated where GFP (green fluorescent protein) is arranged so that it is expressed as a fusion onto the C-terminus of the WssF protein. Following transformation and expression, cells positive for the WssF-GFP fusion were found to glow under ultraviolet light. Successfully expressed fusion protein was also verified using SDS-PAGE separation and Western immunoblots. Cell cultures containing expressed fusion protein were grown and fractionation processes were used to track the presence of the WssF-GFP fusion protein from the cytoplasm to the membrane. However, the GFP portion was lost between the membrane and the periplasm, as visualized based on size differences by SDS-PAGE. Identified GFP fragments in the periplasm indicate possible GFP degradation by proteases upon periplasm entry. Protocol modification with more stringent techniques and the use of protease inhibitors is currently being conducted to troubleshoot this process. Furthermore, the use of WssF activity assays will be used with each fraction to specifically verify its location in the absence of GFP.

051

LIGHTS, FISH, ACTION: INVESTIGATING THE EFFECTS OF LIGHT SETTINGS ON ATTRACTING DIFFERENT FISH SPECIES AND SIZES

Alyssa Dupuis*, Kristen Cyr, Isabelle Tormasi, Holly Mosco, Christina Semeniuk
Department of Integrative Biology, University of Windsor, Windsor, Ontario, Canada N9B 3P4

Studying nocturnal behaviours of fish presents challenges for researchers, as observing animals in aquatic systems is difficult in the absence of light. Tools, such as acoustic telemetry, or infrared cameras have helped overcome these challenges, yet are often expensive, collect data that is difficult to interpret, and provide limited insight into fine-scale behaviors, like prey preferences. Underwater lights with cameras are a cost-effective alternative that can directly observe fish behaviors. However, artificial lights may affect the natural behaviour of fish, and research is lacking in understanding how the use of lights may affect communities composed of individuals with varying abilities to perceive light intensity and colour. To address this knowledge gap, this study deployed fyke nets overnight under 3 replicated treatments of light conditions (white, red, or no lights) to compare differences in species, life history stages (i.e., adult vs. juvenile), and trophic levels (i.e., predator vs. prey) of fish captured in the Margaree River, Nova Scotia. Results indicated that different light colours influence fish community composition and trophic structure. Specifically, a greater number of adult predatory fish were captured in nets with no light, while a greater number of juvenile prey fish were captured using white light. Red light produced the most similar results to no light, as it captured a greater number of adult predators. Understanding the effects of artificial lighting on fish communities can help future studies collect data that better reflect natural nocturnal behaviors, improving conservation efforts and informing strategies that employ lights to help manage fish, like invasive species.

052

UNDERGRADUATE STUDENT KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDES TOWARDS SCIENCE, PERCEPTIONS, AND EXPERIENCES WITH VACCINES AND RECREATIONAL IV DRIPS

Tiffany Huang* and Tanya Noel
Department of Integrative Biology, Faculty of Science, University of Windsor, Windsor, Ontario, Canada N9B 3P4

Public perceptions of medical and wellness interventions are shaped by many factors, some of which include personal experiences, scientific literacy, education, and social media influence. While vaccines have been well-studied and play an essential role in disease prevention, hesitancy persists, often due to misinformation and/or misconceptions. On the other hand, recreational IV drips have gained popularity as wellness treatments despite requiring injections and having limited scientific evidence supporting their efficacy (but many celebrity lifestyle endorsements). This study examines how undergraduate students at the University of Windsor perceive and experience both interventions, comparing the perspectives of students in Integrative Biology programs versus non-majors enrolled in biology courses. A survey will assess students' microbiology knowledge related to vaccines/immunity, their general attitude toward science, and trust in scientific information that guides their decisions on vaccines and recreational IV drips. It also explores students' personal experiences with both interventions. By identifying potential factors that contribute to vaccine hesitancy and the relative acceptance of recreational IV therapies, this study aims to inform future public health communication and educational initiatives. Findings may provide insights into improving science-based messaging to foster more informed health choices among young adults offer guidance for healthcare providers in enhancing patient communication strategies regarding medical and wellness interventions and improve education in microbiology/health sciences.

053

DOES STRUCTURAL ENRICHMENT AFFECT THE GROWTH AND BEHAVIOUR OF CAPTIVE-REARED CHINOOK SALMON?

Laura Middleton^{*1}, Dane Roberts¹, and Trevor Pitcher¹.

¹Department of Biology, University of Windsor, Windsor, Ontario, Canada N9B 3P4

There are evident differences in morphology and behaviour when comparing wild and captive-reared fish. Structural enrichment may serve as an effective strategy to mitigate mismatches between captive and wild environments, potentially enhancing the success of captive-reared individuals upon reintroduction. To improve conservation efforts for species that rely on captive-rearing, such as Chinook salmon, we evaluated the effects of rearing juvenile Chinook salmon in structurally enriched environment versus a barren, non-enriched environment (control) to compare aspects of their growth and behaviour. We measured the growth rate and condition factor of the fish reared in each environment over a 49-day period. We assessed the behaviour of fish reared in enriched and non-enriched environments before and after exposure to a novel hatchery stressor (handling stress), focusing on ecologically relevant metrics for reintroduction. Specifically, we measured environmental preference (substrate habitat vs. barren habitat) and overall swimming activity (active swimming vs immobility). These results may inform rearing facilities of the potential benefits of enrichment in minimizing behavioural disparities between wild and hatchery-reared fish. By addressing these differences, enrichment strategies could contribute to conservation efforts by improving the post-release success of endangered species such as Chinook salmon.

054

PERCEPTIONS OF CLIMATE CHANGE LEARNING AMONG UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS AND INSTRUCTORS.

Linda Nguyen^{*} and Tanya Noel.

Department of Integrative Biology, Faculty of Science, University of Windsor, Windsor, Ontario, Canada N9B 3P4

Despite growing recognition of climate change as a global priority, significant gaps remain in its integration across academic disciplines. Although science programs often address climate change, it is often not a central component of core curricula, leading to disparities in coverage across disciplines. This pilot study evaluates climate change education in selected programs at the University of Windsor, focusing on upper year undergraduates in programs offered by the Integrative Biology (IBio) and School of the Environment (SoE) departments. Through student surveys and interviews, we are examining students' perceptions of their learning and how climate change topics are incorporated and contextualised in courses. We hypothesized that IBio students will perceive lower climate change knowledge and curriculum integration than SoE students. SoE students may engage more with climate policy and real-world applications in Environmental Science courses, gaining greater awareness and integration of this knowledge into their lives. Survey and preliminary student interview analyses did reveal differences between the programs: SoE students reported greater inclusion of climate change, its impacts, and environmentally responsible habits in their courses, while IBio students did not report the same extent of climate change education. Instructor perspectives on challenges and opportunities related to integrating climate change content are also being explored. By identifying gaps and considering student and instructor viewpoints, the study may offer insights into how universities can strengthen climate change education, better equipping students with the knowledge, skills, and motivation to take meaningful action on climate change.

055

EXPLORING THE MECHANISMS OF *RHIZOBIUM LEGUMINOSARUM* BIOFILM FORMATION UNDER BACTERIOPHAGE SELECTIVE PRESSURES: AGRICULTURAL APPLICATIONS

Zahava Dworkin^{1*}, Zahra Salehimoghaddam¹, and Rebecca Doyle¹

¹Department of Biology, McMaster University, Hamilton, Ontario, Canada L8S 2G1

Environmental stressors like drought and nitrogen deficiencies negatively impact soil microbiomes and reduce crop yields in Ontario agriculture. Chemical nitrogen fertilizers, a common solution, contribute to greenhouse gas emissions and hinder *Rhizobium leguminosarum*, a nitrogen-fixing microbe that forms root nodules on legumes. Replacing fertilizers with rhizobia inoculants could promote sustainable agriculture, but their effectiveness is limited by competition from native microbes. Co-inoculation with bacteriophages—viruses that infect bacteria—may enhance rhizobia's competitiveness. Some rhizobial strains produce biofilms as a defense against bacteriophages, which also protect them from environmental stressors like drought. This research explores whether bacteriophage-induced biofilms improve rhizobia survival and competitiveness. By analyzing biofilm production across rhizobial strains using plaque assays, crystal violet staining, growth curve analysis, and 16S rRNA sequencing, this study will determine whether biofilm formation results from pre-existing plasticity or novel genetic mutations. The goal is to harness bacteriophages as selective agents to enhance biofilm-producing rhizobia, improving their ability to outcompete native strains, enhance nitrogen fixation, and support plant growth.

056

THE EFFECT OF INTERSTRAIN COMPETITION ON THE NODULE OCCUPANCY OF GREEN PEA PLANTS

Sofiyyah Oladipupo^{1*}, Emily Perry¹, and Rebecca Doyle¹

¹Department of Biology, McMaster University, Hamilton, Ontario, Canada L8S 2G1

Rhizobia, nitrogen-fixing bacteria commonly used in biofertilizers, form beneficial relationships with legumes such as peas, alfalfa, and clover. These bacteria infect plant roots, forming nodules and supplying nitrogen (N) to their hosts. However, the growth benefits conferred by rhizobia, known as partner quality, vary significantly among strains. While high-quality strains enhance plant growth in greenhouse conditions, they often struggle to establish nodules in field environments due to competition with other strains, a challenge known as the rhizobium competition problem. This issue limits the widespread adoption of beneficial strains as biofertilizers, despite their potential to replace chemical fertilizers. This study aims to address this gap by evaluating the effects of inter-strain competition among four field-collected rhizobia isolates. First, partner quality was assessed through single-strain inoculations in pea plants. Second, host responses to co-inoculation were examined by measuring leaf count, plant height, chlorophyll content, and shoot biomass. Third, inter-strain interactions were analyzed by determining final nodule occupancies. The experimental results show that one isolate consistently promoted the best plant growth under both single- and co-inoculation conditions, while other strains had minimal effects when co-inoculated with this high-quality strain. These findings suggest that inter-strain competition does not necessarily reduce the benefits provided by a superior isolate. However, further investigation is needed to determine whether nodule occupancy by the high-quality strain is affected. This study provides insight into rhizobia interactions, contributing to the development of more effective biofertilizer applications in agriculture.

057

A GENETIC APPROACH TO UNDERSTANDING PHAGE-RHIZOBIUM INTERACTIONS

Hanin Al-Ezzi^{1*}, Zahra Salehimoghaddam¹, and Rebecca Doyle¹

¹Department of Biology, McMaster University, Hamilton, Ontario, Canada L8S 4K1

Rhizobium leguminosarum are essential proteobacteria that form symbiotic relationships with legumes by infecting roots and establishing nodules for biological nitrogen fixation. While rhizobial inoculants are designed to enhance nitrogen fixation and crop yields, they often struggle to outcompete native strains in soil. Native rhizobia, though well-adapted to local environments, do not always contribute effectively to nitrogen fixation, leading to inconsistent crop growth. This study explores the use of bacteriophage (aka phage), viruses that infect bacteria, to selectively modulate rhizobial populations, promoting high-performing inoculant strains over less beneficial native strains. The first objective is to isolate and characterize 18 *R. leguminosarum* phages through genome sequencing and bioinformatics analyses. Using Illumina short-read sequencing and annotation tools (e.g., VIBRANT, PHASEST), we aim to identify genetic signatures associated with phage infectivity and host specificity. The second objective involves sequencing and annotating the genomes of 19 *R. leguminosarum* strains to uncover genetic elements linked to phage resistance. Integrating these genomic insights with phage resistance assays will determine which rhizobial strains are susceptible to specific phages. If phages can be used to selectively reduce uncooperative rhizobial populations, they could improve the effectiveness of rhizobial inoculants, enhancing nitrogen fixation while reducing reliance on chemical fertilizers. Understanding the genetic diversity of *R. leguminosarum* phages and their hosts provides critical insights into rhizobial population dynamics and their potential applications in sustainable agriculture.

058

RESILIENCE IN SYMBIOSIS: HOW RHIZOBIA SURVIVING PHAGE ATTACKS ENHANCE PLANT GROWTH

Olivia Robillard^{1*}, Zahra Salehimoghaddam¹, and Rebecca Doyle¹

¹Department of Biology, McMaster University, Hamilton, Ontario, Canada L8S 2G1

As the demand for sustainable agriculture grows, eco-friendly alternatives to chemical fertilizers are pressing. Rhizobia, soil microbes that convert atmospheric nitrogen into ammonia through biological nitrogen fixation (BNF), offer a natural solution but face competition from other soil microbes that limits their effectiveness. Bacteriophages (phages), viruses that infect bacteria, have been proposed to enhance rhizobial competitiveness by selecting for resilient strains, stimulating biofilm formation, and reducing microbial competition. This study examines whether phage exposure improves rhizobial competitiveness and nodulation efficiency in pea plants using a single-strain inoculation experiment. Plants were individually inoculated with strains that were susceptible to phage (parents) and evolutionary derivatives of these strains that could survive phage infection (survivors). The results showed that plants exhibited consistent leaf growth, with no significant differences between parents and survivors, though shoot biomass varied slightly among strains. Nodule counts were generally high but small, indicating a strong but potentially inefficient symbiotic relationship as a consequence of phage survival. However, root biomass was lower in inoculated plants compared to controls, possibly due to the energy cost of nodule formation. These findings suggest that while phage survival may negatively impact plant-microbe symbiosis, its effects on nitrogen fixation efficiency and plant growth require further study. Investigating phage-rhizobia coevolution could provide deeper insights into their interactions and long-term agricultural benefits.

059

MICROBIALLY-MEDIATED IMPACTS OF CONTAMINANTS PRESENT IN RECLAIMED WATER AND BIOSOLIDS ON GREEN PEA GROWTH

Emily Cacchione^{1*}, Isabella Ippolito¹, Harmanpreet Sidhu², Greg Slater², and Rebecca Doyle¹

¹Department of Biology, McMaster University, Hamilton, Ontario, Canada L8S 4K1

²School of Earth, Environment, and Society, McMaster University, Hamilton, Ontario, Canada L8S 4K1

The global rise in antibiotic use has increased selective pressures on bacteria, leading to the accumulation and spread of antibiotic resistance genes (ARGs) in microbial populations. ARGs have been detected in biosolids, reclaimed water, both of which are increasingly being used as alternatives to chemical fertilizers and fresh water, respectively. The accumulation of ARGs and other contaminants within agricultural systems raises concerns about their potential impacts on soil microbiomes and plant health. However, research on both the direct and indirect effects of contaminant exposure on crop growth remains limited. This study investigates how contaminants present within biosolids and reclaimed water influence the soil microbiome and plant growth. Pea, lettuce, and radish plants were exposed to environmentally relevant and elevated contaminant levels through biosolid or reclaimed water amendments. Soil samples were analyzed using 16S rRNA amplicon sequencing prior to and after contaminant exposure, and soil slurries were cross-inoculated onto pea plants to assess microbiome-mediated effects on plant growth, measured by plant height, leaf chlorophyll content, and biomass. Results showed no significant plant growth differences following cross-inoculation, suggesting that contaminants in biosolids and reclaimed water did not disrupt the established microbiome or that the microbiome adapted to buffer plants from potential negative effects. These findings indicate that biosolids and reclaimed water may serve as sustainable nutrient sources for agriculture without significantly altering plant-microbiome interactions.

060

AMPLIFYING BIRDNET'S SPECIES IDENTIFICATION: IS CONFIDENCE SCORE RELATED TO SONG CHARACTERISTICS?

Vaidehi Patel* and Jennifer Foote

Department of Biology, Algoma University, Sault Ste. Marie, Ontario, Canada P6A 2G4

Rapid and accurate species identification is made possible by automated bird song identification technologies like BirdNET, which have completely changed biodiversity monitoring. The accuracy and possible limitations of the software were evaluated in this study by examining the correlation between BirdNET confidence scores and several acoustics characteristics of bird songs. We made Automated recordings at 206 sites in the Hiawatha Highlands for a total of 1,030 hours in May and June. Ten different species were identified using BIRDNET and 360 (positive and negative) detection of each species were sampled across confidence score bins and examined. We selected 10 high quality songs for each species and analyzed maximum and minimum frequency, bandwidth and song length using Raven Pro. We found that, with the exception of one species (Blackburnian Warbler), with a confidence score of <0.3, BIRDNET consistently recognized species with a probability of 95%. Confidence scores (at p=0.99) were not significantly correlated with song attributes (p > 0.05). While our results differ somewhat from earlier research on particular species, they are consistent with results from Western Canada. It is interesting that our detection accuracy of Brown Creeper was higher compared to Western Canada. This could be because BIRDNET's reference data included a higher representation of Eastern subspecies. These results imply that although BIRDNET offers true species identifications, some positive detections might be missed by a universal confidence threshold (0.70). For wider relevance, future studies should refine confidence criteria and include song measurements from more species.

061

BEHAVIOURAL RESPONSE OF ERPOBDELLA OBSCURA TO NA, MG, K AND CA

Kendra Favaro* and William Dew

Department of Biology, Algoma University, Sault Ste. Marie, Ontario, Canada P6A 2G4

Aquatic animals use a wide range of sensory systems to obtain information about their environment, with olfaction playing a crucial role. The olfactory system is essential to aquatic animals, and aids in survival, predation, kinship, mating, and foraging in vertebrates and invertebrates alike. While extensive research has been conducted on vertebrate chemosensory mechanisms and avoidance responses to contaminants that are commonly found in aquatic systems, very little research has been conducted on invertebrate species. This study investigates the chemosensory responses of *Erpobdella obscura*, a freshwater ribbon leech that was the subject for a series of behavioural trials using four metals salts: magnesium nitrate ($Mg(NO_3)_2$), sodium nitrate ($NaNO_3$), calcium nitrate ($Ca(NO_3)_2$), and potassium nitrate (KNO_3) at concentrations of 1 mM, 5 mM, 10 mM, and 50 mM. The objective was to understand if the response was due to charge, specific elemental properties, or a nitrate specific effect. Behavioural trials were conducted using a 3D-printed box maze that tracked the position of the leech and assessed avoidance responses. Results from this study show a strong avoidance to KNO_3 and $Ca(NO_3)_2$ ($p < 0.05$) indicating that avoidance to these chemicals is not solely driven by ionic charge due to the monovalent and divalent nature of these compounds respectively. These findings highlight the ability of aquatic invertebrates to recognize chemical cues that may be physiologically stressful to them and gives a broader understanding of invertebrate chemosensory mechanisms.

062

PHENOTYPIC VARIATION IN POLLEN GERMINATION AND TUBE GROWTH IN STIGMA LIPID MUTANTS OF TOBACCO (*NICOTIANA TABACUM*)

Alicia Bruni*, Richard Bourgault, Deborah Buhlers, and Isabel Molina

Department of Biology, Algoma University, Sault Ste. Marie, Ontario, Canada P6A 2G4

Pollination is a critical biological process in plant reproduction and genetic diversity, requiring precise interactions between pollen and the stigma. In *Nicotiana tabacum*, a species with wet stigmas, lipids polyesters within stigma exudates are believed to play a vital role in pollen adherence, hydration, and pollen tube growth. To evaluate the specific contribution of lipid polyesters to these processes, we used three tobacco mutant lines with reduced lipid exudation compared to wild-type (WT) plants. Controlled pollination experiments were conducted, and pollen tube growth was visualized using aniline blue staining under a fluorescent microscope. Additionally, a subset of mutant plants were treated with oil to assess whether supplementation with neutral, non-polymeric triacylglycerol could restore normal pollen adherence and germination. Statistical analysis assessed differences among WT, untreated mutants, and oil-treated mutants. The results showed that mutants with reduced lipid polyesters experienced significantly lower pollen adhesion and tube growth compared to WT, while oil-treated mutants showed partial recovery of the WT phenotype. These findings highlight the important role of lipid polyesters in both stigma function and successful fertilization. Understanding the biochemical and physiological contributions of lipid polyesters may have broader implications for improving pollination efficiency in related crops and can address agricultural challenges related to plant reproduction.

063

RAPID IDENTIFICATION OF SPECIES AT RISK HABITAT USE WITH BIRDNET

Kristin Hillier* and Jennifer Foote

Department of Biology, Algoma University, Sault Ste. Marie, Ontario, Canada P6A 2G4

Development proposals often have short time-lines for public consultation and review. However, identifying habitat use by species at risk in areas of proposed development can help shape land use changes in urban and suburban areas. New autonomous recording technologies have resulted in large, and often publically available, datasets that contain vocalizations of bird, mammal, amphibian, and insect communities. These recordings can be used to assess the community composition if recordings exist. New developments in machine learning have also made automated species detection a possibility, like the newly developed BirdNET. In Sault Ste Marie, ON, there was an announcement of a Hydro One route passing through a beloved recreational trails system within the city limits. We had made recordings just several months before during the breeding season of the songbird community. We ran these recordings through BirdNET for three species at risk, Eastern Wood Pewee, Wood Thrush, and Canada Warbler. We calculated confidence intervals for 90% probability of positive detections for these species and identified recording sites that met this criteria. Both Wood Thrush and Eastern Wood Pewee were locally abundant throughout the proposed route while Canada Warbler were found along a wetland area. We presented our data to the community and to Hydro One at their local consultation just 10 days after learning about it, revealing that big datasets can be rapidly used for identifying species at risk and informing local management plans using this approach.

064

INVESTIGATING THE ROLE OF SCREEN TIME AND AGE ON TEAR MENISCUS HEIGHT IN DRY EYE DISEASE

Bryanna Zimbaro^{*1,2}, Nikki Shaw¹

¹Department of Biology, Algoma University, Sault Ste. Marie, Ontario, Canada P6A 2G4

²FYidocors, Sault Ste. Marie, Ontario, Canada P6A 3Z9

The tear film protects the front surface of the eye, maintaining ocular health by providing lubrication, removing debris, delivering oxygen to the cornea, and ensuring optical clarity. It consists of three layers: the outermost lipid layer prevents evaporation; the middle aqueous layer maintains hydration; and the innermost mucin layer ensures adherence of the tear film to the corneal surface. When the tear film becomes disrupted, it may lead to Dry Eye Disease (DED)—a common, multifactorial disease that causes discomfort. DED manifests itself in two forms: Aqueous Deficient Dry Eye (ADDE), which results from reduced tear production, and Evaporative Dry Eye (EDE), caused by rapid tear evaporation. Tear Meniscus Height (TMH) plays a crucial role in diagnosing DED, with values less than 0.20 mm considered aqueous deficient. This study aims to explore the relationship between age and screen time, an area with limited research. TMH was measured on 104 patients from FYidocors in Sault Ste Marie, Ontario, where screen time, age, and their interaction were assessed using a multiple linear regression model. The results from the model showed that screen time and age were significantly related to TMH; ten percent of the variation in TMH was explained by screen time, age, and their interaction. Higher screen time was negatively associated with TMH; older respondents with lower screen time may have higher TMH values due to reflex tearing, where low-quality tears are overproduced due to irritation. Limiting screen time and taking frequent breaks, especially for young adults, may help improve TMH.

065

HOW DOES SOIL BIOTA AND FIRE DISTURBANCE AFFECT THE GROWTH RESPONSES OF BOREAL AND TEMPERATE ONTARIO TREE SPECIES?

Roxane Bergeron*¹, Joel Lucenay¹, Stephen Mayor², and Pedro M. Antunes¹

¹Department of Biology, Algoma University, Sault Ste. Marie, Ontario, Canada P6A 2G4

²Ontario Forest Research Institute, Sault Ste. Marie, Ontario, Canada, P6A 2E5

Canada's Boreal Forest is expected to experience rising temperatures and increased wildfire frequency under climate change. Soil biota play a critical role in plant establishment and seedling success, particularly in early successional landscapes. However, the potential northward migration of temperate tree species remains uncertain, as do the effects of novel soil biota associations on their establishment. To investigate these dynamics, we asked: (1) How do tree species respond to soil biota from their home forests versus foreign soil biota? (2) How does fire-disturbed boreal soil biota affect tree growth, and does the addition of temperate soil biota to burnt boreal soil alter this response? We conducted a greenhouse experiment growing three representative boreal and three temperate Ontario tree species in five soil biota inoculation treatments—temperate, boreal unburnt, boreal burnt, boreal burnt mixed with temperate, and a sterile control—measuring stem height over 154 days (n = 300). We found that tree growth responses to soil biota varied among species. Overall, boreal trees generally exhibited a more positive response to soil biota than temperate trees, but there was no significant difference in growth response across treatments.

066

DOES SEED REMOVAL BY GRANIVORES IN AN OLD FIELD PLANT COMMUNITY DIFFER AMONG PLANT SPECIES?

Hailey Frasier* and Brandon Schamp

Department of Biology, Algoma University, Sault Ste. Marie, Ontario, Canada, P6A 2G4

Granivores (seed-eating herbivores) may affect plant communities by altering species abundance or diversity. Seed consumption rate of plant species may vary depending on seed size and abundance, which can determine how easily the seeds are found and consumed. In this study, we set out seed depots of 24 plant species in an old field plant community to test how plant species identity and seed size affect seed removal. We also compared differences in seed removal rates when seeds were on soil to a previous study where seeds were not in substrate and just in a petri dish. Plant species were removed from the seed depots by granivores at significantly different rates, with seeds of varying species-level seed masses also differing in removal rates. When compared to a previous study, fewer seeds of all species were eaten when seeds were on soil, suggesting that search time for seeds is an important factor in granivore food choice and efficiency. Differences in traits among plant species (e.g. seed size, colour) may also be factors in seed removal when soil is present. Results suggest that species differences in seed removal may alter plant communities in a way which may enable coexistence.

067

THE INFLUENCE OF HARD VERSUS SOFT RELEASE METHODS ON EASTERN SAND DARTER (*AMMOCRYPTA PELLUCIDA*) BURROWING BEHAVIOUR IN RESPONSE TO A PREDATOR

Audrey Joan Verra*, Adam Gouge, and Christine Madliger

Department of Biology, Algoma University, Sault Ste. Marie, Ontario, Canada, P6A 2G4

Fishes are among the most endangered taxa in freshwater ecosystems. Reintroduction is one strategy for re-establishing populations, but it often involves transportation, which can introduce stress and behavioural changes. There are two release methods: hard (direct release) and soft release (includes acclimatization via enclosures). Soft release may aid in the recovery of natural behaviours, but its effects following transportation remain understudied, especially for small-bodied species. The Eastern Sand Darter (*Ammocrypta pellucida*), a species at risk, has been proposed for reintroduction to aid population recovery. However, little is known about how release methods influence their behaviour such as burrowing in sand, which is thought to aid in predator evasion. In this study, we examined whether soft release supports behaviours related to predator evasion compared to hard release methods. We assessed substrate preference (sand vs. rock) in a behavioural arena and used a lure (rainbow trout) to simulate a predator event. We calculated time spent on each substrate, burrowing frequency, and swimming behaviours before and after predator introduction. Results from this study show that release methods following transport did not significantly influence burrowing behaviour and substrate preference in response to a predator. Evasion was slightly lower in the hard release group, but not statistically significant. Hard release may be suitable for this species, but future work including a larger sample size and other endpoints should be done to verify the optimal release method.

068

THE BEHAVIOURAL EFFECTS OF ARTIFICIAL LIGHT AT NIGHT IN BIRDS: A META-ANALYSIS

Washma Arshad* and Christine Madliger

Department of Biology, Algoma University, Sault Ste Marie, Ontario, Canada, P6A 2G4

Artificial light at night (ALAN) is increasing globally due to the expansion of anthropogenic activities in both terrestrial and aquatic environments. Although artificial light is beneficial for humans, its effects on other species are not fully understood. Excess light can interfere with organismal physiology, behaviour, and fitness, with potential consequences for whole ecosystems. As literature has amassed in avian species over the past 20 years, there is the opportunity to synthesize the effects of ALAN on key traits, such as behaviour. The objective of my study was to perform a meta-analysis to determine the types and extent of behaviours that can be affected by ALAN in birds. I used a structured search in Web of Science to establish a dataset of 245 journal articles. I collected information from each publication on the type of behaviour, species, year of publication, location of study, type of light, and effect on behaviour. I found that behaviourally focused research on ALAN has been steadily increasing over time. In addition, the majority of studies reported negative effects of ALAN on avian behaviour. Finally, certain behavioural traits were more extensively researched than others, with migration, vocalization, and sleep being the most prevalent. Further research is needed to establish the influence of ALAN on other behaviours, such as habitat selection and vigilance. My results reinforce the importance of considering ALAN as a threat for birds across multiple parts of their life cycles.

069

ASSESSING SWIMMING PERFORMANCE OF THE EASTERN SAND DARTER FOLLOWING HARD AND SOFT RELEASE TECHNIQUES

Anton Peter*, Adam Gouge, and Christine Madliger

Department of Biology, Algoma University, Sault Ste. Marie, Ontario, Canada P6A 2G4

Aquatic ecosystems are among the most threatened habitats worldwide, with habitat degradation and fragmentation significantly impacting freshwater fish populations. The Eastern Sand Darter (*Ammocrypta pellucida*), a small benthic fish listed as a species at risk in Canada, relies on sandy substrates and undisturbed flow conditions, making it highly vulnerable to habitat disturbances. Translocation is an emerging conservation strategy for this species, yet the effect of transport and success of different release techniques remains unclear. A proxy for swim performance was assessed in summer and fall by measuring swimming distance across three groups: control (not transported), hard release (immediately following transport), and soft release (following 24-hours in an in-river enclosure after transport). In summer, fish released in the soft release treatment swam significantly farther than those in the hard release group ($p = 0.003$), suggesting a potential benefit of a gentler release method. However, in fall, both release groups swam significantly farther than the control group ($p = 0.005$), with no significant difference between the two techniques. These findings indicate that the effectiveness of release methods may be season-dependent, with soft release showing greater benefits in summer. Understanding the influence of release strategies on post-translocation performance is crucial for conservation planning. This study emphasizes the significance of adjusting conservation efforts to seasonal circumstances in freshwater environments and contributes guidance on how to best reintroduce the Eastern Sand Darter.

070

AN ANALYSIS OF GLAUCOUS GULL (*LARUS HYPERBOREUS*) DIET FROM CORNWALLIS ISLAND, NUNAVUT.

Lucy van Haften*¹, Mark Mallory², Jennifer Provencher³, and Sarah Jamieson¹

¹Department of Biology, Trent University, Peterborough, Ontario, Canada K9L 0G2

²Department of Biology, Acadia University, Wolfville, Nova Scotia, Canada, B4P 2R6

³Science and Technology Branch, Environment and Climate Change Canada, Ottawa, Ontario, Canada K1A 0H3

Glaucous Gulls (*Larus hyperboreus*) are diet generalists that usually nest in coastal colonies with other seabird species, often preying upon their neighbours' eggs and young. On Cornwallis Island, Nunavut, a colony of Glaucous Gulls inhabits a small island within a lake, where they are the only seabird species nesting. Given this unique non-coastal habitat not shared with other birds, we wanted to determine whether their diet differs from other more typical nearby populations. To assess this, we collected 79 regurgitated Glaucous Gull pellets from this colony, dissected them, and identified prey items to the lowest possible taxonomic level. We found that this population was feeding predominantly on northern collared lemmings (*Dicrostonyx groenlandicus*), which is unusual for the species which usually feeds mostly on marine prey and young of other seabird species. Other prey items found include bivalve and gastropod shells, bird eggshells, and garbage from the nearby landfill. This study provides evidence for a specialized diet of Glaucous Gulls in this unique environment. Since this population feeds largely on terrestrial prey, this information could be used for future studies that compare the contaminants ingested by gulls that feed in terrestrial vs. marine environments.

The Conference Venue

Richcraft Hall, 3rd Floor

Thank you!